

Triangular-Type Selfie Numbers¹

Inder J. Taneja²

Abstract

Numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations are considered as *selfie numbers*. There are many ways of writing *selfie numbers*, such as, numbers written in digit's order or its reverse just with basic operations. We can extend them by use of other operations, such as, *factorial, square-root, Triangular numbers, Fibonacci sequence values, etc.* In this work, the *selfie numbers* are written by use of *triangular numbers* in digit's order and reverse.

Contents

1	Selfie Numbers	1
1.1	Selfie Numbers with Factorial	1
1.2	Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root	2
1.3	Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence	2
1.4	Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root	2
1.5	Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence	3
1.6	Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients	3
1.7	Selfie Numbers with S-gonal numbers	4
1.8	Selfie Numbers with Centered Polygonal Numbers	4
1.9	Binomial Coefficients, S-gonal, and Centered Polygonal Numbers	5
2	Triangular Numbers	5
3	Palindromic Number Representations	6
4	Symmetric Representations	6
4.1	Symmetric Representations in Both Ways	6
4.2	Symmetric Representations in Digit's Order	15
4.3	Symmetric Representations in Reverse Order of Digits	16
5	Patterns with Triangle Numbers	16
6	Non Symmetric Selfie Numbers with Triangle Numbers	27
6.1	Both Ways Representations	27
6.2	Digit's Order	81
6.3	Reverse Order of Digits	84
7	Complete Selfie Numbers	87
7.1	Digit's Order	87
7.2	Reverse Order of Digits	88

¹It is revised version of author's [24] previous work <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a54.pdf> done in 2017.

²Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978). **E-mail:** ijjtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-site:** <https://inderjtaneja.com>; **Twitter:** @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

1 Selfie Numbers

Recently, author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers** and **centered polygonal numbers**.

1.1 Selfie Numbers with Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial. See below some examples:

$$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$$

$$733 := 7 + 3!! + 3!$$

$$5177 := 5! + 17 + 7!$$

$$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$$

$$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$$

$$403199 := 40319 + 9!$$

$$1463 := -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!!$$

$$10077 := -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!$$

$$40585 := 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!$$

$$80518 := 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!$$

$$317489 := -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!$$

$$352797 := -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!$$

$$357592 := -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!$$

$$357941 := 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!$$

$$361469 := 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!$$

$$364292 := 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!$$

$$397584 := -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!$$

$$398173 := 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!$$

$$408937 := -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!$$

$$715799 := -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!$$

$$720599 := -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!$$

For more details refer author's work [15].

1.2 Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial and/or square-root. See below some examples:

$$936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}}$$

$$1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} = 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)}$$

$$2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2$$

$$331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3$$

$$342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3$$

$$759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}$$

$$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.$$

Examples given above are with **factorial** and **square-root** [20, 21]. First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [8, 9, 10, 13, 14].

1.3 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence

The examples given in subsections, 1.1 and 1.4 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 := 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 := 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [17, 18, 19].

1.4 Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial and/or square-root. See below some examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 936 := (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! & = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 := \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} & = 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 := 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) & = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 := 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} & = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 := (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 & = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 := (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 & = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\
 \\
 759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 & = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7
 \end{array}$$

Examples given above are with **factorial** and **square-root** [20, 21]. First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [8, 9, 10, 13, 14].

1.5 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence

The examples given in subsections, 1.1 and 1.4 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 235 = 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 = 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 = 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 = 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 = (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 = F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 = F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3 & 54128 = 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))
 \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [17, 18, 19].

1.6 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 1.5 and 1.6 are with **Fibonacci sequence** and **Triangular numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!) & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)) \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [15].
 The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

1.7 Selfie Numbers with S-gonal numbers

The examples given in subsection 1.6 are with **binomial coefficients**. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **s-gonal numbers**. See below some examples in **digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 \\ 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\ 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\ 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\ 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \end{aligned}$$

$$49548 := -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4$$

$$53995 := (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5$$

$$50424 := 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!})$$

$$52895 := (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5$$

The symbol P used for **s-gonal numbers** and is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

For more details refer author's work [23].

1.8 Selfie Numbers with Centered Polygonal Numbers

The examples given in subsection 1.6 and 1.7 are with **binomial coefficients** and **s-gonal numbers** respectively. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **centered polygonal numbers**. See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$2883 := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$$

$$01051 := K(15, 010)$$

$$2888 := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$$

$$01199 := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$$

$$3640 := K(3!, 6) \times 40$$

$$59938 := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$$

$$14939 := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$$

$$62424 := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$$

$$14959 := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$$

$$63384 := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$$

$$15144 := K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4!$$

$$63744 := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$$

$$15347 := (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$$

$$63973 := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6)$$

$$15399 := K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9$$

$$00938 := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$$

The symbol K used for **centered polygonal numbers** and is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

For more details refer author's work [23]. For summary of author's work on numbers refer [25, 26, 27]. For study on **s-gonal numbers** and **centered polygonal numbers** refer to [1, 3, 6, 7]. Also refer [2, 4] for historical books on numbers.

1.9 Binomial Coefficients, S-gonal, and Centered Polygonal Numbers

There are very few selfie numbers connecting three formulas: **binomial coefficients**, **s-gonal** and **centered polygonal numbers**

In some cases the ordered in not same, it is either in digit's order or reverse

$$13448 := 8 + (4 + 4)!/C(3, 1) = (8! + 4!)/\sqrt{P(4, 3) - 1} = K(-1 + 3!, 4)^{\sqrt{4}} \times 8$$

$$39435 := C(5 + 3!, \sqrt{4}) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 3!!) = (3!! - \sqrt{9}) \times (4 + P(3!, 5)) = (K(5, 3) + 4!) \times (-\sqrt{9} + 3!!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39648 &:= 8! - (\sqrt{4} + 6) \times C(9, 3) &= -P(3 + 9, 6 \times \sqrt{4}) + 8! &= K(3!, \sqrt{9}) - 6! + \sqrt{4} + 8! \\ 98464 &:= C(9 + 8, \sqrt{4}) \times (6! + 4) &= (4 + 6!) \times P(4! - 8, \sqrt{9}) &= (4 + 6!) \times K(\sqrt{4} + 8, \sqrt{9}) \end{aligned}$$

From above, we observe that there is not a even a single numbers that connects above three formulas in digit's order or in reverse

Two by two there are many numbers given in [23]

2 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics [5]. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "C" represents as "**binomial coefficient**" as seen in subsection 1.8.

In this paper our aim is to bring **selfie numbers** by used of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections

Due to high quantity of numbers, we restricted our work up to four digits, i.e.

from 1 to 9999. There are different ways of calling these numbers, such as, **tri-gonal**, **triangular** or **triangle selfie numbers**. For simplicity, we shall call them as **triangular selfie numbers**.

3 Palindromic Number Representations

This section brings *selfie palindromic numbers* by use of triangular numbers. The idea of starting the work with palindromic numbers is as they are symmetric in itself, i.e., remains the same by changing the order of digits. Below are *selfie palindromic numbers*:

$$\begin{aligned} 66 &:= T(T(T(6)))/T(6) & 696 &:= T(T(6)) + T(9 + T(6)) \\ 171 &:= T(17 + 1) & 777 &:= T(7) \times T(7) - 7 \\ 222 &:= T(T(2))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) & 969 &:= T(T(9)) - T(6) - T(9) \\ 232 &:= -2 + T(T(T(3))) + T(2) & 2222 &:= (T(T(2))^{T(T(2))} + T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2))) \\ 242 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4) + T(T(T(2))) & 2332 &:= T(2^{T(3)}) + T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2))) \\ 252 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2 & 2442 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2) \\ 525 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5 & 2552 &:= (T(T(2))^5 - T(T(5)))/T(2) \\ 666 &:= T(-6 + T(6) + T(6)) & 2662 &:= 2 \times (T(T(6))/T(6))^{T(2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$2772 := -T(2) + T(77 - T(2))$$

$$3003 := T(T(T(T(3))))/003$$

$$3333 := T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(T(T(3) + T(3)))$$

$$3773 := T(T(T(3))) - T(7) + T(T(7) \times 3)$$

$$3993 := -T(3 \times 9) + T(93)$$

$$4224 := T(42) + T(T(2)^4)$$

$$4334 := T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(4))$$

$$4884 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - 4$$

$$5445 := T(54) \times T(T(4))/T(5)$$

$$5665 := T(5) \times T(T(6) + 6) - 5$$

$$5775 := T(5) \times 77 \times 5$$

$$5995 := 5 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(9) - 5)$$

$$6336 := (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6$$

$$9339 := T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(T(3)) - T(T(9))$$

4 Symmetric Representations

In this section, we shall give **selfie numbers** in terms of **triangular numbers** along with basic operations. These representations are in symmetric way, i.e., all is same except the digits 0 to 9. This happens in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits. In some cases numbers can written in both the ways.

4.1 Symmetric Representations in Both Ways

Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order and its reverse:

$$120 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$121 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$122 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$123 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$124 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$125 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$126 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$127 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$128 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$129 := T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$$

$$210 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 0 = 0 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$211 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 1 = 1 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$212 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 2 = 2 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$213 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 3 = 3 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$214 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 4 = 4 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$215 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 5 = 5 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$216 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 6 = 6 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$217 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 7 = 7 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$218 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 8 = 8 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$219 := T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) + 9 = 9 + T(-1 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 990 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 0 = 0 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 991 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 1 = 1 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 992 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 2 = 2 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 993 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 3 = 3 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 994 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 4 = 4 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 995 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 5 = 5 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 996 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 6 = 6 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 997 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 7 = 7 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 998 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 8 = 8 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \\ 999 &:= T(T(9)) - T(9) + 9 = 9 + T(T(9)) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1260 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1261 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1262 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1263 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1264 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1265 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1266 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1267 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1268 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1269 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1540 &:= T(1 + 54) + 0 = 0 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1541 &:= T(1 + 54) + 1 = 1 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1542 &:= T(1 + 54) + 2 = 2 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1543 &:= T(1 + 54) + 3 = 3 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1544 &:= T(1 + 54) + 4 = 4 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1545 &:= T(1 + 54) + 5 = 5 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1546 &:= T(1 + 54) + 6 = 6 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1547 &:= T(1 + 54) + 7 = 7 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1548 &:= T(1 + 54) + 8 = 8 + T(4 + 51) \\ 1549 &:= T(1 + 54) + 9 = 9 + T(4 + 51) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1680 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1681 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1682 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1683 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1684 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1685 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1686 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \\ 1687 &:= T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times T(T(6)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$1688 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1)$$

$$1689 := T(-1 + T(6)) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times T(T(6) - 1)$$

$$1740 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 0 = 0 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1741 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 1 = 1 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1742 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 2 = 2 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1743 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 3 = 3 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1744 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 4 = 4 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1745 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 5 = 5 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1746 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 6 = 6 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1747 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 7 = 7 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1748 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 8 = 8 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1749 := T(1 + T(7)) \times 4 + 9 = 9 + 4 \times T(T(7) + 1)$$

$$1770 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1771 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1772 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1773 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1774 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1775 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1776 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1777 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1778 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1779 := T(1 + T(T(7))/7) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(7))/7 + 1)$$

$$1830 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 0 = 0 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1831 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 1 = 1 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1832 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 2 = 2 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1833 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 3 = 3 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1834 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 4 = 4 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1835 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 5 = 5 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1836 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 6 = 6 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1837 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 7 = 7 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1838 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8 = 8 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1839 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3)))) + 9 = 9 + T(-T(T(3)) + 81)$$

$$1980 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 0 = 0 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)$$

$$1981 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 1 = 1 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)$$

$$1982 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 2 = 2 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)$$

$$1983 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 3 = 3 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)$$

$$1984 := T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 4 = 4 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1985} &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 5 = 5 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\ \mathbf{1986} &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 6 = 6 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\ \mathbf{1987} &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 7 = 7 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\ \mathbf{1988} &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 8 = 8 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \\ \mathbf{1989} &:= T(1 + 9) \times T(8) + 9 = 9 + T(8) \times T(9 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2210} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2211} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2212} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2213} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2214} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2215} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2216} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2217} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2218} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2219} &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2310} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 0 = 0 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2311} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 1 = 1 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2312} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 2 = 2 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2313} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 3 = 3 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2314} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 4 = 4 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2315} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 5 = 5 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2316} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 6 = 6 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2317} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 7 = 7 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2318} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 8 = 8 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ \mathbf{2319} &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(3 + 1) + 9 = 9 + T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2340} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 0 = 0 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2341} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 1 = 1 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2342} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 2 = 2 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2343} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 3 = 3 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2344} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 4 = 4 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2345} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 5 = 5 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2346} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 6 = 6 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2347} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 7 = 7 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2348} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 8 = 8 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2349} &:= (T(2) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) + 9 = 9 + T(4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{2520} &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ \mathbf{2521} &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2522 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2523 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2524 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2525 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2526 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2527 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2528 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \\ 2529 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(5 \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2850 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 0 = 0 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2851 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 1 = 1 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2852 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 2 = 2 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2853 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 3 = 3 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2854 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 4 = 4 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2855 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 5 = 5 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2856 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 6 = 6 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2857 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 7 = 7 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2858 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 8 = 8 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 2859 &:= T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5)) + 9 = 9 + T(T(5) \times (8 - T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2940 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 0 = 0 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2941 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 1 = 1 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2942 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 2 = 2 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2943 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 3 = 3 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2944 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 4 = 4 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2945 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 5 = 5 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2946 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 6 = 6 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2947 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 7 = 7 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2948 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 8 = 8 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \\ 2949 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + 9 = 9 + (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3150 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 0 = 0 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3151 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 1 = 1 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3152 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 2 = 2 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3153 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 3 = 3 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3154 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 4 = 4 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3155 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 5 = 5 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3156 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 6 = 6 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3157 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 7 = 7 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3158 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 8 = 8 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \\ 3159 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 1) \times T(5) + 9 = 9 + T(5) \times T(-1 + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3240 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 0 = 0 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3241 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 1 = 1 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3242 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 2 = 2 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3243 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 3 = 3 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3244 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 4 = 4 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3245 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 5 = 5 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3246 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 6 = 6 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3247 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 7 = 7 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3248 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 8 = 8 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \\ 3249 &:= T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4)) + 9 = 9 + T(T(4) \times 2^3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3450 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 0 = 0 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3451 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 1 = 1 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3452 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 2 = 2 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3453 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 3 = 3 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3454 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 4 = 4 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3455 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 5 = 5 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3456 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 6 = 6 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3457 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 7 = 7 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3458 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 8 = 8 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \\ 3459 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(T(5)) + 9 = 9 - T(T(5)) + T(4 \times T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3570 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 0 = 0 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3571 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 1 = 1 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3572 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 2 = 2 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3573 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 3 = 3 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3574 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 4 = 4 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3575 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 5 = 5 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3576 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 6 = 6 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3577 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 7 = 7 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3578 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 8 = 8 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 3579 &:= T(T(3) + T(5 + 7)) + 9 = 9 + T(T(7) \times T(5 - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3780 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 0 = 0 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3781 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 1 = 1 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3782 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 2 = 2 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3783 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 3 = 3 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3784 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 4 = 4 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3785 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 5 = 5 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3786 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 6 = 6 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3787 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 7 = 7 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3788 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 8 = 8 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \\ 3789 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 7) \times T(8) + 9 = 9 + T(8) \times T(-7 + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4140 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 0 = 0 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4141 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 1 = 1 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4142 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 2 = 2 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4143 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 3 = 3 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4144 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 4 = 4 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4145 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 5 = 5 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4146 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 6 = 6 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4147 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 7 = 7 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4148 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 8 = 8 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \\ 4149 &:= 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) + 9 = 9 + 4 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4270 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 0 = 0 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4271 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 1 = 1 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4272 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 2 = 2 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4273 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 3 = 3 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4274 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 4 = 4 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4275 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 5 = 5 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4276 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 6 = 6 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4277 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 7 = 7 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4278 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 8 = 8 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \\ 4279 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7))) + 9 = 9 + (T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4290 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 0 = 0 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4291 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 1 = 1 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4292 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 2 = 2 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4293 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 3 = 3 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4294 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 4 = 4 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4295 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 5 = 5 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4296 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 6 = 6 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4297 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 7 = 7 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4298 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 8 = 8 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4299 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2) + 9) + 9 = 9 + T(9 + T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4560 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 0 = 0 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4561 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 1 = 1 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 4562 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 2 = 2 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4563 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 3 = 3 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4564 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 4 = 4 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4565 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 5 = 5 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4566 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 6 = 6 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4567 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 7 = 7 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4568 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 8 = 8 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4)) \\4569 &:= T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6)) + 9 = 9 + T(T(6) \times 5 - T(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4620 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 0 = 0 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4621 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 1 = 1 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4622 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 2 = 2 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4623 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 3 = 3 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4624 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 4 = 4 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4625 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 5 = 5 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4626 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 6 = 6 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4627 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 7 = 7 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4628 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 8 = 8 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4)) \\4629 &:= T(4) \times T(T(6)) \times 2 + 9 = 9 + T(2) \times T(T(6+4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4650 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 0 = 0 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4651 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 1 = 1 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4652 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 2 = 2 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4653 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 3 = 3 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4654 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 4 = 4 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4655 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 5 = 5 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4656 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 6 = 6 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4657 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 7 = 7 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4658 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 8 = 8 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4) \\4659 &:= T(4) \times T(6 \times 5) + 9 = 9 + T(5 \times 6) \times T(4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4950 &:= T(4 + 95) + 0 = 0 + T(5 + 94) \\4951 &:= T(4 + 95) + 1 = 1 + T(5 + 94) \\4952 &:= T(4 + 95) + 2 = 2 + T(5 + 94) \\4953 &:= T(4 + 95) + 3 = 3 + T(5 + 94) \\4954 &:= T(4 + 95) + 4 = 4 + T(5 + 94) \\4955 &:= T(4 + 95) + 5 = 5 + T(5 + 94) \\4956 &:= T(4 + 95) + 6 = 6 + T(5 + 94) \\4957 &:= T(4 + 95) + 7 = 7 + T(5 + 94) \\4958 &:= T(4 + 95) + 8 = 8 + T(5 + 94) \\4959 &:= T(4 + 95) + 9 = 9 + T(5 + 94)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6930 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 0 = 0 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6931 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 1 = 1 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6932 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 2 = 2 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6933 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 3 = 3 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6934 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 4 = 4 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6935 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 5 = 5 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6936 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 6 = 6 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6937 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 7 = 7 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6938 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 8 = 8 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\ 6939 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(3))) + 9 = 9 + (T(T(3)) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8280 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 0 = 0 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8281 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 1 = 1 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8282 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 2 = 2 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8283 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 3 = 3 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8284 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 4 = 4 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8285 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 5 = 5 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8286 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 6 = 6 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8287 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 7 = 7 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8288 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 8 = 8 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \\ 8289 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) + 9 = 9 + T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8460 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 0 = 0 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8461 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 1 = 1 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8462 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 2 = 2 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8463 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 3 = 3 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8464 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 4 = 4 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8465 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 5 = 5 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8466 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 6 = 6 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8467 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 7 = 7 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8468 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 8 = 8 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \\ 8469 &:= T(8) \times (4 + T(T(6))) + 9 = 9 + (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9240 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9241 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9242 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9243 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9244 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9245 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9246 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9247 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9248 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\ 9249 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9450 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 0 = 0 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9451 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 1 = 1 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9452 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 2 = 2 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9453 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 3 = 3 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9454 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 4 = 4 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9455 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 5 = 5 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9456 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 6 = 6 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9457 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 7 = 7 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9458 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 8 = 8 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \\ 9459 &:= T(9) \times T(4 \times 5) + 9 = 9 + T(5 \times 4) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Symmetric Representations in Digit's Order

Below are examples of numbers written in digit's order:

$$\begin{array}{ll} 190 := T(19) + 0 & 1090 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 0 \\ 191 := T(19) + 1 & 1091 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 1 \\ 192 := T(19) + 2 & 1092 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 2 \\ 193 := T(19) + 3 & 1093 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\ 194 := T(19) + 4 & 1094 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 4 \\ 195 := T(19) + 5 & 1095 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 5 \\ 196 := T(19) + 6 & 1096 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 6 \\ 197 := T(19) + 7 & 1097 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 7 \\ 198 := T(19) + 8 & 1098 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 8 \\ 199 := T(19) + 9 & 1099 := T(10) + T(T(9)) + 9 \end{array}$$

4.3 Symmetric Representations in Reverse Order of Digits

Below are examples of numbers written in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{array}{lll} 0150 := 0 + T(5) \times 10 & 0156 := 6 + T(5) \times 10 & 0192 := 2 + T(9 + 10) \\ 0151 := 1 + T(5) \times 10 & 0157 := 7 + T(5) \times 10 & 0193 := 3 + T(9 + 10) \\ 0152 := 2 + T(5) \times 10 & 0158 := 8 + T(5) \times 10 & 0194 := 4 + T(9 + 10) \\ 0153 := 3 + T(5) \times 10 & 0159 := 9 + T(5) \times 10 & 0195 := 5 + T(9 + 10) \\ 0154 := 4 + T(5) \times 10 & & 0196 := 6 + T(9 + 10) \\ 0155 := 5 + T(5) \times 10 & 0190 := 0 + T(9 + 10) & 0197 := 7 + T(9 + 10) \\ & 0191 := 1 + T(9 + 10) & \end{array}$$

$$0198 := 8 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0199 := 9 + T(9 + 10)$$

$$0210 := 0 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0211 := 1 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0212 := 2 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0213 := 3 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0214 := 4 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0215 := 5 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0216 := 6 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0217 := 7 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0218 := 8 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$0219 := 9 + T(1 \times 20)$$

$$1660 := 0 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1661 := 1 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1662 := 2 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1663 := 3 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1664 := 4 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1665 := 5 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1666 := 6 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1667 := 7 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1668 := 8 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$1669 := 9 - T(T(6)) + T(61)$$

$$2080 := 0 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2081 := 1 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2082 := 2 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2083 := 3 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2084 := 4 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2085 := 5 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2086 := 6 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2087 := 7 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2088 := 8 + T(8^{02})$$

$$2089 := 9 + T(8^{02})$$

$$4190 := 0 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4191 := 1 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4192 := 2 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4193 := 3 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4194 := 4 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4195 := 5 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4196 := 6 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4197 := 7 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4198 := 8 + T(91) + 4$$

$$4199 := 9 + T(91) + 4$$

5 Patterns with Triangle Numbers

There are numbers that can be extended just multiplying by 10 without loss of properties of numbers. This type we call as **number patterns**. This kind of numbers first introduced by Madachy [4], 1966, pp. 174-175. This section deals with numbers patterns in selfie numbers having **triangular values**. This kind of numbers are only in terms of digit's order.

$$21 := T(T(T(2))) \times 1$$

$$210 := T(T(T(2))) \times 10$$

$$2100 := T(T(T(2))) \times 100$$

$$24 := T(T(2)) \times 4$$

$$240 := T(T(2)) \times 40$$

$$2400 := T(T(2)) \times 400$$

$$36 := T(3) \times 6$$

$$360 := T(3) \times 60$$

$$3600 := T(3) \times 600$$

$$63 := T(6) \times 3$$

$$630 := T(6) \times 30$$

$$6300 := T(6) \times 300$$

$$147 := T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 7$$

$$1470 := T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 70$$

$$14700 := T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 700$$

$$168 := 1 \times T(6) \times 8$$

$$1680 := 1 \times T(6) \times 80$$

$$16800 := 1 \times T(6) \times 800$$

$$185 := (1 + T(8)) \times 5$$

$$1850 := (1 + T(8)) \times 50$$

$$18500 := (1 + T(8)) \times 500$$

$$225 := T(T(2)^2) \times 5$$

$$2250 := T(T(2)^2) \times 50$$

$$22500 := T(T(2)^2) \times 500$$

$$231 := T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 1$$

$$2310 := T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 10$$

$$23100 := T(T(2 \times 3)) \times 100$$

$$35100 := T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 100$$

$$241 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 1$$

$$396 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 6$$

$$2410 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 10$$

$$3960 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60$$

$$24100 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 100$$

$$39600 := (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 600$$

$$243 := T(2)^4 \times 3$$

$$525 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 5$$

$$2430 := T(2)^4 \times 30$$

$$5250 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 50$$

$$24300 := T(2)^4 \times 300$$

$$52500 := 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 500$$

$$244 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$528 := T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 8$$

$$2440 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$5280 := T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 80$$

$$24400 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$52800 := T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 800$$

$$245 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 5$$

$$564 := (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 4$$

$$2450 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 50$$

$$5640 := (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 40$$

$$24500 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 500$$

$$56400 := (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 400$$

$$248 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 8$$

$$572 := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 2$$

$$2480 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 80$$

$$5720 := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 20$$

$$24800 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 800$$

$$57200 := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 200$$

$$252 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 2$$

$$728 := T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 8$$

$$2520 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 20$$

$$7280 := T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 80$$

$$25200 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(5))) \times 200$$

$$72800 := T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 800$$

$$273 := T(T(T(2)) + 7) \times 3$$

$$735 := 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 5$$

$$2730 := T(T(T(2)) + 7) \times 30$$

$$7350 := 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 50$$

$$27300 := T(T(T(2)) + 7) \times 300$$

$$73500 := 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 500$$

$$275 := T(T(2) + 7) \times 5$$

$$741 := (T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times 1$$

$$2750 := T(T(2) + 7) \times 50$$

$$7410 := (T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times 10$$

$$27500 := T(T(2) + 7) \times 500$$

$$74100 := (T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times 100$$

$$279 := (T(2) + T(7)) \times 9$$

$$812 := T(T(8 - 1)) \times 2$$

$$2790 := (T(2) + T(7)) \times 90$$

$$8120 := T(T(8 - 1)) \times 20$$

$$27900 := (T(2) + T(7)) \times 900$$

$$81200 := T(T(8 - 1)) \times 200$$

$$351 := T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 1$$

$$864 := T(8) \times 6 \times 4$$

$$3510 := T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 10$$

$$8640 := T(8) \times 6 \times 40$$

$$86400 := T(8) \times 6 \times 400$$

$$\begin{aligned} 924 &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) \times 4 \\ 9240 &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) \times 40 \\ 92400 &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1122 &:= T(11 \times T(2)) \times 2 \\ 11220 &:= T(11 \times T(2)) \times 20 \\ 112200 &:= T(11 \times T(2)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1125 &:= (-T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\ 11250 &:= (-T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 50 \\ 112500 &:= (-T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1144 &:= (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 11440 &:= (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 40 \\ 114400 &:= (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1165 &:= (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5 \\ 11650 &:= (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 50 \\ 116500 &:= (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1197 &:= T((1 + 1) \times 9) \times 7 \\ 11970 &:= T((1 + 1) \times 9) \times 70 \\ 119700 &:= T((1 + 1) \times 9) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1235 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 5 \\ 12350 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 50 \\ 123500 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1365 &:= 13 \times T(6) \times 5 \\ 13650 &:= 13 \times T(6) \times 50 \\ 136500 &:= 13 \times T(6) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1368 &:= T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 8 \\ 13680 &:= T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 80 \\ 136800 &:= T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1539 &:= T((1 + 5) \times 3) \times 9 \\ 15390 &:= T((1 + 5) \times 3) \times 90 \\ 153900 &:= T((1 + 5) \times 3) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1575 &:= T(1 + 5) \times 75 \\ 15750 &:= T(1 + 5) \times 750 \\ 157500 &:= T(1 + 5) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1617 &:= 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 7 \\ 16170 &:= 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 70 \\ 161700 &:= 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1632 &:= T(16) \times T(3) \times 2 \\ 16320 &:= T(16) \times T(3) \times 20 \\ 163200 &:= T(16) \times T(3) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1645 &:= (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ 16450 &:= (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 164500 &:= (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1648 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 8 \\ 16480 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 80 \\ 164800 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1656 &:= T(T(1 + 6) - 5) \times 6 \\ 16560 &:= T(T(1 + 6) - 5) \times 60 \\ 165600 &:= T(T(1 + 6) - 5) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1722 &:= T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \\ 17220 &:= T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2))) \times 20 \\ 172200 &:= T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1755 &:= T(T(-1 + 7) + 5) \times 5 \\ 17550 &:= T(T(-1 + 7) + 5) \times 50 \\ 175500 &:= T(T(-1 + 7) + 5) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1764 &:= T(-1 + 7) \times T(6) \times 4 \\ 17640 &:= T(-1 + 7) \times T(6) \times 40 \\ 176400 &:= T(-1 + 7) \times T(6) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1844 &:= (T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ 18440 &:= (T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(4))) \times 40 \\ 184400 &:= (T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(4))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1848 &:= T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 8 \\ 18480 &:= T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 80 \end{aligned}$$

$$184800 := T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 800$$

$$1864 := (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 4$$

$$18640 := (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 40$$

$$186400 := (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 400$$

$$1895 := (1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 5$$

$$18950 := (1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 50$$

$$189500 := (1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 500$$

$$1932 := (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 2$$

$$19320 := (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 20$$

$$193200 := (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 200$$

$$2079 := T(T(2) \times 07) \times 9$$

$$20790 := T(T(2) \times 07) \times 90$$

$$207900 := T(T(2) \times 07) \times 900$$

$$2135 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(3)))) \times 5$$

$$21350 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(3)))) \times 50$$

$$213500 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(3)))) \times 500$$

$$2169 := (T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times 9$$

$$21690 := (T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times 90$$

$$216900 := (T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times 900$$

$$2175 := T(2 - 1 + T(7)) \times 5$$

$$21750 := T(2 - 1 + T(7)) \times 50$$

$$217500 := T(2 - 1 + T(7)) \times 500$$

$$2208 := T(T(2) + 20) \times 8$$

$$22080 := T(T(2) + 20) \times 80$$

$$220800 := T(T(2) + 20) \times 800$$

$$2244 := T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times 4$$

$$22440 := T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times 40$$

$$224400 := T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times 400$$

$$2275 := (2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 5$$

$$22750 := (2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 50$$

$$227500 := (2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 500$$

$$2288 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + 8)) \times 8$$

$$22880 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + 8)) \times 80$$

$$228800 := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + 8)) \times 800$$

$$2355 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times 5)) \times 5$$

$$23550 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times 5)) \times 50$$

$$235500 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times 5)) \times 500$$

$$2376 := (-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6$$

$$23760 := (-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 60$$

$$237600 := (-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 600$$

$$2432 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 32$$

$$24320 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 320$$

$$243200 := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 3200$$

$$2444 := (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$24440 := (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$244400 := (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$2457 := T(T(2 + 4) + 5) \times 7$$

$$24570 := T(T(2 + 4) + 5) \times 70$$

$$245700 := T(T(2 + 4) + 5) \times 700$$

$$2462 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6)) \times 2$$

$$24620 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6)) \times 20$$

$$246200 := (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6)) \times 200$$

$$2465 := (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 5$$

$$24650 := (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 50$$

$$246500 := (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 500$$

$$2495 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 5$$

$$24950 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 50$$

$$249500 := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 500$$

$$2595 := (T(2^5) - 9) \times 5$$

$$25950 := (T(2^5) - 9) \times 50$$

$$259500 := (T(2^5) - 9) \times 500$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2648 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 8 \\ 26480 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 80 \\ 264800 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2667 &:= (T(2) + T(T(6) + 6)) \times 7 \\ 26670 &:= (T(2) + T(T(6) + 6)) \times 70 \\ 266700 &:= (T(2) + T(T(6) + 6)) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2688 &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 8 \\ 26880 &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 80 \\ 268800 &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2709 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 9 \\ 27090 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 90 \\ 270900 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2728 &:= (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \times 8 \\ 27280 &:= (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \times 80 \\ 272800 &:= (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2768 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 8 \\ 27680 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 80 \\ 276800 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2805 &:= T(-T(2) + T(8)) \times 05 \\ 28050 &:= T(-T(2) + T(8)) \times 050 \\ 280500 &:= T(-T(2) + T(8)) \times 0500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2812 &:= 2 \times T(T(8) + 1) \times 2 \\ 28120 &:= 2 \times T(T(8) + 1) \times 20 \\ 281200 &:= 2 \times T(T(8) + 1) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2835 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(8) - 3)) \times 5 \\ 28350 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(8) - 3)) \times 50 \\ 283500 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(8) - 3)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2877 &:= (-T(2) + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 7 \\ 28770 &:= (-T(2) + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 70 \\ 287700 &:= (-T(2) + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2884 &:= (T(2 + 8) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\ 28840 &:= (T(2 + 8) + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\ 288400 &:= (T(2 + 8) + T(T(8))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2928 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))/T(2)) \times 8 \\ 29280 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))/T(2)) \times 80 \\ 292800 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))/T(2)) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2958 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times 58 \\ 29580 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times 580 \\ 295800 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times 5800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2975 &:= T(T(2) \times 9 + 7) \times 5 \\ 29750 &:= T(T(2) \times 9 + 7) \times 50 \\ 297500 &:= T(T(2) \times 9 + 7) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3122 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 31220 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 312200 &:= (T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3185 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 5 \\ 31850 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 50 \\ 318500 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3285 &:= (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 32850 &:= (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 328500 &:= (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3297 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9) \times 7 \\ 32970 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9) \times 70 \\ 329700 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9) \times 700 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3321 &:= T((3 \times 3)^2) \times 1 \\ 33210 &:= T((3 \times 3)^2) \times 10 \\ 332100 &:= T((3 \times 3)^2) \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3355 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\ 33550 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 50 \\ 335500 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$3366 := T(3^3 + 6) \times 6$$

$$33660 := T(3^3 + 6) \times 60$$

$$336600 := T(3^3 + 6) \times 600$$

$$3375 := T(3 \times 3) \times 75$$

$$33750 := T(3 \times 3) \times 750$$

$$337500 := T(3 \times 3) \times 7500$$

$$3385 := (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$33850 := (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$338500 := (T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$3422 := T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 2$$

$$34220 := T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 20$$

$$342200 := T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 200$$

$$3432 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 2$$

$$34320 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 20$$

$$343200 := (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 200$$

$$3442 := (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2$$

$$34420 := (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 20$$

$$344200 := (T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 200$$

$$3484 := (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 4$$

$$34840 := (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 40$$

$$348400 := (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 400$$

$$3485 := (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$34850 := (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 50$$

$$348500 := (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 500$$

$$3515 := T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 5$$

$$35150 := T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 50$$

$$351500 := T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 500$$

$$3525 := (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 25$$

$$35250 := (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 250$$

$$352500 := (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 2500$$

$$3528 := (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8$$

$$35280 := (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 80$$

$$352800 := (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 800$$

$$3542 := (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2$$

$$35420 := (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 20$$

$$354200 := (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 200$$

$$3624 := (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 4$$

$$36240 := (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 40$$

$$362400 := (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 400$$

$$3648 := T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8$$

$$36480 := T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 80$$

$$364800 := T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 800$$

$$3846 := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) - 4) \times 6$$

$$38460 := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) - 4) \times 60$$

$$384600 := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) - 4) \times 600$$

$$3855 := (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 5$$

$$38550 := (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 50$$

$$385500 := (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 500$$

$$3885 := (T(38) + T(8)) \times 5$$

$$38850 := (T(38) + T(8)) \times 50$$

$$388500 := (T(38) + T(8)) \times 500$$

$$3927 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7$$

$$39270 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 70$$

$$392700 := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 700$$

$$3944 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$39440 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 40$$

$$394400 := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 400$$

$$3968 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 8$$

$$39680 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 80$$

$$396800 := T((T(T(T(3))) - T(9))/6) \times 800$$

$$3969 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9$$

$$39690 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 90$$

$$396900 := T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 900$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3978 &:= (T(3) + T(9)) \times 78 \\ 39780 &:= (T(3) + T(9)) \times 780 \\ 397800 &:= (T(3) + T(9)) \times 7800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3996 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 6 \\ 39960 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 60 \\ 399600 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4131 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(13))) \times 1 \\ 41310 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(13))) \times 10 \\ 413100 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(13))) \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4164 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 4 \\ 41640 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 40 \\ 416400 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4185 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 5 \\ 41850 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 50 \\ 418500 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4239 &:= (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 9 \\ 42390 &:= (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 90 \\ 423900 &:= (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4256 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 56 \\ 42560 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 560 \\ 425600 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 5600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4323 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) \times 3 \\ 43230 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) \times 30 \\ 432300 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4368 &:= T(T(4) + 3) \times 6 \times 8 \\ 43680 &:= T(T(4) + 3) \times 6 \times 80 \\ 436800 &:= T(T(4) + 3) \times 6 \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4385 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 43850 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 438500 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4386 &:= (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 6 \\ 43860 &:= (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 60 \\ 438600 &:= (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4422 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 2 \\ 44220 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 20 \\ 442200 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4443 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times 3 \\ 44430 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times 30 \\ 444300 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4))) - 4) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4446 &:= T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 6 \\ 44460 &:= T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 60 \\ 444600 &:= T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4484 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4 \\ 44840 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 40 \\ 448400 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4485 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ 44850 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 50 \\ 448500 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4488 &:= (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 88 \\ 44880 &:= (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 880 \\ 448800 &:= (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 8800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4532 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2 \\ 45320 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 20 \\ 453200 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4584 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\ 45840 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 40 \\ 458400 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4595 &:= (4 - T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\ 45950 &:= (4 - T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 50 \\ 459500 &:= (4 - T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4615 &:= (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 5 \\ 46150 &:= (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

$$461500 := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 500$$

$$494200 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 200$$

$$4662 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 2$$

$$4962 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2$$

$$46620 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 20$$

$$49620 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 20$$

$$466200 := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 200$$

$$496200 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 200$$

$$4682 := (-T(4) + T(68)) \times 2$$

$$4985 := (-T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 5$$

$$46820 := (-T(4) + T(68)) \times 20$$

$$49850 := (-T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 50$$

$$468200 := (-T(4) + T(68)) \times 200$$

$$498500 := (-T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 500$$

$$4687 := (4 + T(6) + T(T(8))) \times 7$$

$$4995 := (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 5$$

$$46870 := (4 + T(6) + T(T(8))) \times 70$$

$$49950 := (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 50$$

$$468700 := (4 + T(6) + T(T(8))) \times 700$$

$$499500 := (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 500$$

$$4697 := (-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times 7$$

$$5112 := T(5 + T(11)) \times 2$$

$$46970 := (-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times 70$$

$$51120 := T(5 + T(11)) \times 20$$

$$469700 := (-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times 700$$

$$511200 := T(5 + T(11)) \times 200$$

$$4744 := (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 4$$

$$5133 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3$$

$$47440 := (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 40$$

$$51330 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 30$$

$$474400 := (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 400$$

$$513300 := T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 300$$

$$4762 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(7)) \times 6) \times 2$$

$$5195 := (5 - 1 + T(T(9))) \times 5$$

$$47620 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(7)) \times 6) \times 20$$

$$51950 := (5 - 1 + T(T(9))) \times 50$$

$$476200 := (-T(T(4)) + T(T(7)) \times 6) \times 200$$

$$519500 := (5 - 1 + T(T(9))) \times 500$$

$$4837 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7$$

$$5244 := (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 4$$

$$48370 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 70$$

$$52440 := (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 40$$

$$483700 := (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 700$$

$$524400 := (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 400$$

$$4866 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6$$

$$5288 := (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 8$$

$$48660 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 60$$

$$52880 := (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 80$$

$$486600 := (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 600$$

$$528800 := (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 800$$

$$4924 := (T(49) + T(T(2))) \times 4$$

$$5324 := (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 4$$

$$49240 := (T(49) + T(T(2))) \times 40$$

$$53240 := (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 40$$

$$492400 := (T(49) + T(T(2))) \times 400$$

$$532400 := (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 400$$

$$4942 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2$$

$$5368 := (5 + T(36)) \times 8$$

$$49420 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 20$$

$$53680 := (5 + T(36)) \times 80$$

$$536800 := (5 + T(36)) \times 800$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5432 &:= (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2 \\ 54320 &:= (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 20 \\ 543200 &:= (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5448 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8 \\ 54480 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 80 \\ 544800 &:= (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5568 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 8 \\ 55680 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 80 \\ 556800 &:= (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5616 &:= T(5 + T(6)) \times 16 \\ 56160 &:= T(5 + T(6)) \times 160 \\ 561600 &:= T(5 + T(6)) \times 1600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5625 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 5 \\ 56250 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 50 \\ 562500 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5664 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 4 \\ 56640 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 40 \\ 566400 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5676 &:= T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 6 \\ 56760 &:= T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 60 \\ 567600 &:= T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5688 &:= (T(T(5) - 6) + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\ 56880 &:= (T(T(5) - 6) + T(T(8))) \times 80 \\ 568800 &:= (T(T(5) - 6) + T(T(8))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5775 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 5 \\ 57750 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 50 \\ 577500 &:= T(5) \times 77 \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5848 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ 58480 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 80 \\ 584800 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5852 &:= T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \times 2 \\ 58520 &:= T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \times 20 \\ 585200 &:= T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5922 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 59220 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 20 \\ 592200 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5928 &:= T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 8 \\ 59280 &:= T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 80 \\ 592800 &:= T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5949 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9 \\ 59490 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 90 \\ 594900 &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6125 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 5 \\ 61250 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 50 \\ 612500 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6162 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 2 \\ 61620 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 20 \\ 616200 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6216 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 6 \\ 62160 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 60 \\ 621600 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6244 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\ 62440 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 40 \\ 624400 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6336 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 6 \\ 63360 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 60 \\ 633600 &:= (T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3))) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6375 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 5 \\ 63750 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 50 \\ 637500 &:= T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6399 &:= (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 9 \\ 63990 &:= (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 90 \end{aligned}$$

$$639900 := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 900$$

$$665700 := (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 700$$

$$6453 := (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3$$

$$6696 := 6 \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 6$$

$$64530 := (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 30$$

$$66960 := 6 \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 60$$

$$645300 := (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 300$$

$$669600 := 6 \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 600$$

$$6489 := (T(6 + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 9$$

$$6732 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 2$$

$$64890 := (T(6 + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 90$$

$$67320 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 20$$

$$648900 := (T(6 + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 900$$

$$673200 := T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 200$$

$$6492 := (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 2$$

$$6844 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 4$$

$$64920 := (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 20$$

$$68440 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 40$$

$$649200 := (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 200$$

$$684400 := T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 400$$

$$6528 := T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 8$$

$$6888 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 8$$

$$65280 := T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 80$$

$$68880 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 80$$

$$652800 := T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 800$$

$$688800 := (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 800$$

$$6545 := (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5$$

$$7224 := T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$65450 := (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50$$

$$72240 := T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \times 40$$

$$654500 := (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500$$

$$722400 := T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \times 400$$

$$6552 := (6 + T(T(5))) \times 52$$

$$7288 := (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 8$$

$$65520 := (6 + T(T(5))) \times 520$$

$$72880 := (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 80$$

$$655200 := (6 + T(T(5))) \times 5200$$

$$728800 := (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 800$$

$$6615 := T(6) \times T(6) \times 15$$

$$7296 := (T(7^2) - 9) \times 6$$

$$66150 := T(6) \times T(6) \times 150$$

$$72960 := (T(7^2) - 9) \times 60$$

$$661500 := T(6) \times T(6) \times 1500$$

$$729600 := (T(7^2) - 9) \times 600$$

$$6624 := 6 \times T(T(6) + 2) \times 4$$

$$7326 := (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 6$$

$$66240 := 6 \times T(T(6) + 2) \times 40$$

$$73260 := (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 60$$

$$662400 := 6 \times T(T(6) + 2) \times 400$$

$$732600 := (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 600$$

$$6642 := (T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4))) \times 2$$

$$7353 := (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3$$

$$66420 := (T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4))) \times 20$$

$$73530 := (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 30$$

$$664200 := (T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4))) \times 200$$

$$735300 := (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 300$$

$$6657 := (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 7$$

$$7425 := T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 5$$

$$66570 := (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 70$$

$$74250 := T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 50$$

$$742500 := T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 500$$

$$7443 := (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3$$

$$74430 := (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 30$$

$$744300 := (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 300$$

$$7485 := (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5$$

$$74850 := (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 50$$

$$748500 := (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 500$$

$$7567 := T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 7$$

$$75670 := T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 70$$

$$756700 := T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 700$$

$$7568 := T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 8$$

$$75680 := T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 80$$

$$756800 := T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 800$$

$$7653 := (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 3$$

$$76530 := (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 30$$

$$765300 := (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 300$$

$$7735 := (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 5$$

$$77350 := (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 50$$

$$773500 := (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 500$$

$$7749 := T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 9$$

$$77490 := T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 90$$

$$774900 := T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 900$$

$$7839 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 9$$

$$78390 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 90$$

$$783900 := (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 900$$

$$7845 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5$$

$$78450 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50$$

$$784500 := (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 500$$

$$7847 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 7$$

$$78470 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 70$$

$$784700 := (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 700$$

$$7893 := (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3$$

$$78930 := (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 30$$

$$789300 := (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 300$$

$$8245 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 5$$

$$82450 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 50$$

$$824500 := (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 500$$

$$8372 := T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 2$$

$$83720 := T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 20$$

$$837200 := T(T(8) + T(3 + 7)) \times 200$$

$$8379 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9$$

$$83790 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 90$$

$$837900 := (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 900$$

$$8424 := T(T(8) - T(4)) \times 24$$

$$84240 := T(T(8) - T(4)) \times 240$$

$$842400 := T(T(8) - T(4)) \times 2400$$

$$8568 := (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times 8$$

$$85680 := (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times 80$$

$$856800 := (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times 800$$

$$8572 := (8 + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 2$$

$$85720 := (8 + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 20$$

$$857200 := (8 + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 200$$

$$8824 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 2))) \times 4$$

$$88240 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 2))) \times 40$$

$$882400 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 2))) \times 400$$

$$8827 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 7$$

$$88270 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 70$$

$$882700 := (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 700$$

$$8844 := T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 4$$

$$88440 := T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 40$$

$$884400 := T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 400$$

$$8856 := T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 6$$

$$88560 := T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 60$$

$$885600 := T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 600$$

$$936900 := (T(T(9)) + T(-3 + 6)) \times 900$$

$$8991 := (-T(8) + T(T(9))) \times 9 \times 1$$

$$9444 := (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 4$$

$$89910 := (-T(8) + T(T(9))) \times 9 \times 10$$

$$94440 := (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 40$$

$$899100 := (-T(8) + T(T(9))) \times 9 \times 100$$

$$944400 := (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 400$$

$$9279 := (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 9$$

$$9522 := (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 2$$

$$92790 := (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 90$$

$$95220 := (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 20$$

$$927900 := (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 900$$

$$952200 := (T(T(9))/T(5))^2 \times 200$$

$$9333 := (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3$$

$$9936 := T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 36$$

$$93330 := (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 30$$

$$99360 := T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 360$$

$$933300 := (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 300$$

$$993600 := T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 3600$$

$$9369 := (T(T(9)) + T(-3 + 6)) \times 9$$

$$93690 := (T(T(9)) + T(-3 + 6)) \times 90$$

6 Non Symmetric Selfie Numbers with Triangle Numbers

This section deals with the numbers not appearing above. Here also we have three subsections, where first one give the representations in both ways, second subsection give numbers in digit's order and the final subsection give the numbers in reverse order of digits.

6.1 Both Ways Representations

$$15 := T(1 \times 5) \\ := T(5) \times 1$$

$$36 := T(3) \times 6 \\ := 6 \times T(3)$$

$$21 := T(T(1 + 2)) \\ := T(T(2 + 1))$$

$$39 := -T(3) + T(9) \\ := T(9) - T(3)$$

$$23 := 2 + T(T(3)) \\ := T(T(3)) + 2$$

$$45 := T(4 + 5) \\ := T(5 + 4)$$

$$24 := T(T(2)) \times 4 \\ := 4 \times T(T(2))$$

$$49 := 4 + T(9) \\ := T(9) + 4$$

$$34 := -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) \\ := T(T(4)) - T(T(3))$$

$$55 := T(5 + 5) \\ := T(5 + 5)$$

$$63 := T(6) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times T(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= T(-1 + T(05)) \\ &:= T(T(5) - 01) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 132 &:= (1 + T(T(3))) \times T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(3)) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T((T(3) - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 136 &:= T(T(1 + 3) + 6) \\ &:= T(6 + T(3 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 147 &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(4 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 152 &:= -1 + T(T(5) + 2) \\ &:= T(2 + T(5)) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 154 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5)))/T(4) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(5 - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 167 &:= -1 + 6 \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times 6 - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 168 &:= 1 \times T(6) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 176 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \\ &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 185 &:= (1 + T(8)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(8) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 186 &:= -T(1 + 8) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - T(8 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 221 &:= -T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 223 &:= -2^{T(2)} + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) - 2^{T(2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 224 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2) - 4 \\ &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 225 &:= T(2 + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (5 \times T(2))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 226 &:= -2 - T(2) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) - 2 - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 227 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) - 7 \\ &:= -7 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 228 &:= T(T(2)) \times (2 + T(8)) \\ &:= (T(8) + 2) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 229 &:= -2 + T(T(-T(2) + 9)) \\ &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 231 &:= T(T(2 \times 3 \times 1)) \\ &:= T(T(1 \times 3 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 233 &:= 2 + T(T(3 + 3)) \\ &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 234 &:= T(2) \times T(3 \times 4) \\ &:= T(4 \times 3) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 236 &:= 2 + 3 + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + 3 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 237 &:= T(T(2)) + T(3 \times 7) \\ &:= T(7 \times 3) + T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4 \times 1) \\ &:= T(1 \times 4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 243 &:= T(2)^4 \times 3 & &:= T(T(6)) + T(7 + 2) \\
 &:= 3^4 \times T(2) \\
 244 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 4 & &279 := (T(2) + T(7)) \times 9 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2))) & &:= 9 \times (T(7) + T(2)) \\
 245 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 5 & &285 := T(T(2) \times 8) - T(5) \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) & &:= -T(5) + T(8 \times T(2)) \\
 248 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 8 & &286 := T(2 + 8) + T(T(6)) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) & &:= T(T(6)) + T(8 + 2) \\
 253 &:= T(25 - 3) & &287 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + 8 \times 7 \\
 &:= T(-3 + 5^2) & &:= 7 \times 8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 254 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + 5 \times T(T(4)) & &294 := T(T(2)) \times (T(9) + 4) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times 5 - T(T(T(2))) & &:= 49 \times T(T(2)) \\
 255 &:= (2 + T(5)) \times T(5) & &295 := T(-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) - 5 \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(5) + 2) & &:= T(59)/T(T(2)) \\
 256 &:= 25 + T(T(6)) & &315 := 3 \times T(-1 + T(5)) \\
 &:= (T(6) - 5)^2 & &:= T(5) \times T(T(1 \times 3)) \\
 264 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6)) \times 4 & &324 := -T(3) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) & &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(2)) - T(3) \\
 268 &:= T(2 + T(6)) - 8 & &325 := T((3 + 2) \times 5) \\
 &:= -8 + T(T(6) + 2) & &:= T(5 \times (2 + 3)) \\
 273 &:= T(2) \times T(7 + T(3)) & &336 := T(3 \times T(T(3)))/6 \\
 &:= T(T(3) + 7) \times T(2) & &:= T(63)/T(3) \\
 274 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(7) \times T(4) & &342 := T(3) \times (T(T(4)) + 2) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(7) - T(T(2)) & &:= (2 + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \\
 275 &:= T(T(2) + 7) \times 5 & &345 := T(3) \times T(T(4)) + T(5) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(7 + T(2)) & &:= T(T(5 + 4))/3 \\
 276 &:= T(2 + 7) + T(T(6)) & &346 := T(T(3)) + T(4 + T(6)) \\
 & & &:= T(T(6) + 4) + T(T(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 348 &:= -3 + T(-T(4) + T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8) - T(4)) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 351 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5 \times 1) \\ &:= T(1 \times 5 + T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 355 &:= 3 \times T(T(5)) - 5 \\ &:= (5 + T(T(5))) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 364 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(-T(6) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(6)) - T(T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 369 &:= -T(36) + T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) - T(6 \times T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 372 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(7) - 2) \\ &:= T(27) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 375 &:= (-3 + T(7)) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times (T(7) - 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 385 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(-8 + T(5))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(5) - 8)) - T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 392 &:= T(3 + T(9))/T(2) \\ &:= T(T(2) + T(9))/3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 396 &:= T(3) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\ &:= (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 399 &:= -T(3) + 9 \times T(9) \\ &:= 9 \times T(9) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 416 &:= T(4) + T(T(1 + 6)) \\ &:= T(T(6 + 1)) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 417 &:= T(4) + 1 + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + 1 + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 427 &:= T(4 + 2) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + T(2 + 4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 433 &:= T(T(4)) + T(3^3) \\ &:= T(3^3) + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 435 &:= T(4 \times T(3) + 5) \\ &:= T(-5 + 34) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 437 &:= T(4) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(3 \times T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 455 &:= -T(4) + T(T(5) + T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5) + T(5)) - T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 456 &:= 4 \times (T(T(5)) - 6) \\ &:= (-6 + T(T(5))) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 461 &:= T(T(4)) + T(T(6 + 1)) \\ &:= T(T(1 + 6)) + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 462 &:= 4 \times T(T(6))/2 \\ &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(6 - 4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 465 &:= T(4 + T(6) + 5) \\ &:= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 466 &:= 4 + T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(6)) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 467 &:= T(T(4)) + 6 + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + 6 + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 469 &:= 4 + T(T(6) + 9) \\ &:= T(9 + T(6)) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 475 &:= T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times T(7) + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$485 := -T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(8) - T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{492} := T(T(4)) \times 9 - T(2)$$

$$:= -T(2) + 9 \times T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{496} := T(T(4) + T(T(9 - 6)))$$

$$:= T(T(6) - T(9) + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{497} := T(4 + 9) + T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + T(9 + 4)$$

$$\mathbf{528} := T(T(T(5))/T(2) - 8)$$

$$:= T((8 - T(T(2)))^5)$$

$$\mathbf{556} := T(5 \times 5) + T(T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{561} := T(T(1 + 6) + 5)$$

$$:= T(5 + T(6 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{564} := (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(6) + T(T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{572} := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{573} := -T(5) + T(7) \times T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times T(7) - T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{637} := T(T(6)) + T(T(T(3))) + 7$$

$$:= T(7 + T(T(3))) + T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{647} := T(T(6)) + T(4) + T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + T(4) + T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{658} := T(T(6) + T(5)) - 8$$

$$:= -8 + T(T(5) + T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{663} := -3 + T(6 \times 6)$$

$$:= T(6 \times 6) - 3$$

$$\mathbf{672} := (T(T(6)) - 7) \times T(2)$$

$$:= T(2) \times (-7 + T(T(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{687} := T(6) + T(8 + T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7) + 8) + T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{693} := (T(T(6)) \times (9/3))$$

$$:= (-T(3) + 9) \times T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{697} := -6 + T(9 + T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7) + 9) - 6$$

$$\mathbf{722} := -7 + T(2)^{T(T(2))}$$

$$:= T(2)^{T(T(2))} - 7$$

$$\mathbf{728} := T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(T(2)) + 7)$$

$$\mathbf{735} := (T(7) + T(T(3))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= 5 \times T(T(3)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{741} := T(T(7) + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$:= T(T(1 \times 4) + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{756} := T(-7 + T(5)) \times T(6)$$

$$:= T(6) \times T(T(5) - 7)$$

$$\mathbf{758} := -T(7) + T(T(5)) + T(T(8))$$

$$:= T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) - T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{759} := -T(T(7) - 5) + T(T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9)) - T(-5 + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{774} := -T(4) + T(7) \times T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) \times T(7) - T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{812} := 2 \times T(T(-1 + 8))$$

$$:= T(T(8 - 1)) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 825 &:= T(8 + 2) \times T(5) & &:= -T(7 + 5) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(2 + 8) \\
 826 &:= T(T(8) - 2) + T(T(6)) & &966 := T(9) \times T(6) + T(6) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) + T(-2 + T(8)) & &:= T(6) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 842 &:= T(T(8)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) & &972 := T(T(9) - 7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(8)) & &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-7 + T(9)) \\
 861 &:= T(T(8) + 6 - 1) & &977 := T(T(9)) - T(T(7))/7 \\
 &:= T(-1 + 6 + T(8)) & &:= -T(T(7))/7 + T(T(9)) \\
 864 &:= T(8) \times 6 \times 4 & &1122 := T(11 \times T(2)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 4 \times 6 \times T(8) & &:= 2 \times T(T(2) \times 11) \\
 867 &:= -T(8) + T(6 \times 7) & &1125 := (-T(T(1 + 1)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(7 \times 6) - T(8) & &:= T(5)^{T(2)} / T(1 + 1) \\
 874 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(7) \times T(T(4)) & &1128 := T(-1 + 12 + T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(8)) & &:= T(8 \times T(2 + 1) - 1) \\
 882 &:= T(T(8)) + T(8) \times T(T(2)) & &1129 := 1 + T(1 \times 2 + T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(8)) & &:= T(T(9) + 2) + 1 \times 1 \\
 897 &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(T(T(9 - 7)))) & &1134 := -1 \times T(T(1 + T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(-7 + 9)))) + T(T(8)) & &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3) + 1 \times 1)) \\
 903 &:= T(T(9) - 03) & &1144 := (T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) + T(T(4))) \times 4 \\
 &:= T(-3 + T(09)) & &:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) \\
 915 &:= T(T(9)) - T(15) & &1152 := T(T(T(T(1 + 1)))) \times 5 - T(2) \\
 &:= -T(T(5)) \times 1 + T(T(9)) & &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 - T(1 + 1) \\
 924 &:= T(T(9 - T(2))) \times 4 & &1153 := -1 - 1 + 5 \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(-T(2) + 9)) & &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 - T(1 + 1) \\
 946 &:= T(T(9) + 4 - 6) & &1154 := -1 + T(1 + 5) \times T(T(4)) \\
 &:= T(-6 + 49) & &:= T(T(4)) \times T(5 + 1) - 1 \\
 957 &:= T(T(9)) - T(5 + 7) & &1155 := T(T(1 + 1) \times T(5)) + T(T(5)) \\
 & & &:= T(T(5)) + T(T(5) \times T(1 + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1156 &:= 1 + 1 \times 5 \times T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) \times 5 + 1 \times 1 \\ 1165 &:= (1 + 1 + T(T(6))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) + 1 + 1) \\ 1174 &:= -1 - 1 + T(-7 + T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4)) - 7) - 1 - 1 \\ 1176 &:= T((1 \times 1 + 7) \times 6) \\ &:= T(6 \times (7 + 1 \times 1)) \\ 1177 &:= 1 + T(-1 + 7 \times 7) \\ &:= T(7 \times 7 - 1) + 1 \\ 1182 &:= T(T(1 + 1)) + T(8 \times T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(2)) + T(8 \times T(T(1 + 1))) \\ 1188 &:= (-T(1 + 1) + T(8)) \times T(8) \\ &:= T(8) \times (T(8) - T(1 + 1)) \\ 1197 &:= T((1 + 1) \times 9) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(9 \times (1 + 1)) \\ 1217 &:= -1 + T(2) \times T(T(1 \times 7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) \times (1 + 2) - 1 \\ 1218 &:= (1 + 2) \times T(T(-1 + 8)) \\ &:= T(T(8 - 1)) \times (2 + 1) \\ 1222 &:= T((1 + T(T(2)))^2) - T(2) \\ &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)) + 1) \\ 1224 &:= -1 + T(T(T(2)^2) + 4) \\ &:= T((T(4) - T(2))^2) - 1 \\ 1225 &:= T(-1 + 2 \times 25) \\ &:= T((5 + 2)^2 \times 1) \\ 1226 &:= 1 + T(T(T(2 + 2))) - 6 \\ &:= T((T(6)/T(2))^2) + 1 \\ 1227 &:= (1 + 2) \times (T(2) + T(T(7))) \\ &:= T(7^2) + 2 \times 1 \\ 1235 &:= (T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (-T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \\ 1237 &:= 1 + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(T(7))) \\ &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(3))) \times T(2) + 1 \\ 1239 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) - T(3) + T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) - T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1243 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\ 1245 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(45) \\ &:= T(5) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)) + 1)) \\ 1246 &:= T(T(1 + 2)) + T(T(T(4))) - 6 \\ &:= T(6) + T(T(T(4)) - T(2 + 1)) \\ 1247 &:= -1 + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(T(7))) \\ &:= (T(T(7)) + T(4)) \times T(2) - 1 \\ 1248 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))) - 8 \\ &:= T(-8 + T(T(4))) + T(T((T(T(2)) - 1))) \\ 1249 &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + 4 + T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) + 4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1 \\ 1254 &:= -T(T(1 + 2)) + T(5 \times T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4) \times 5) - 21 \\ 1259 &:= -1 + T(2 + 5) \times T(9) \\ &:= T(9) \times T(5 + 2) - 1 \\ 1272 &:= T(T(12) - T(7)) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -T(2) + T(7^2 + 1) \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(6 + T(2^3 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1273} := T(T(1 + T(2))) + T(T(7)) \times 3 \qquad \mathbf{1327} := 1 + T(T(3) + T(2 + 7))$$

$$:= 3 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(2) + 1)) \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(7) + 23) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1274} := -1 + T((-2 + 7) \times T(4)) \qquad \mathbf{1328} := (-1 + 3) \times (-2 + T(T(8)))$$

$$:= T(T(4) \times (7 - 2)) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := (T(T(8)) - 2) \times (3 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1275} := T((1 + 2 + 7) \times 5) \qquad \mathbf{1329} := 1 \times 3 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9))$$

$$:= T(5 \times (7 + 2 + 1)) \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(9) + T(T(2))) + 3 \times 1$$

$$\mathbf{1276} := 1 + T(2 \times T(7) - 6) \qquad \mathbf{1332} := (-1 + 3) \times T(T(3)^2)$$

$$:= T(-6 + T(7) \times 2) + 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := 2 \times T(T(3 \times 3 - 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1291} := T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9) + 1) \qquad \mathbf{1337} := T(T(T((1 + 3)))) - T(T(T(3))) + T(7)$$

$$:= T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(T(2))) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(7) - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(3 + 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1295} := -1 + T(T(2) + T(9)) + T(T(5)) \qquad \mathbf{1338} := (-1 + 3) \times (3 + T(T(8)))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) + T(T(9) + T(2)) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := (T(T(8)) + 3) \times (3 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1296} := T(-1 + T(T(2)) + T(9)) + T(6) \qquad \mathbf{1342} := (1 + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))$$

$$:= 6^{9/T(2)+1} \qquad \qquad \qquad := (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(3)) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1297} := -1 + T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) - T(7) \qquad \mathbf{1343} := -1 + T(T(3)) \times 4^3$$

$$:= (-T(7) + T(T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(3)) \times 4^3 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1322} := -1 + T(T(3))^2 \times T(2) \qquad \mathbf{1345} := T(-1 \times T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(2) \times T(T(3)) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(3 \times 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1323} := T(T(1 \times 3)) \times T(2) \times T(T(3)) \qquad \mathbf{1349} := -1 + 3 \times T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (2^{T(3)} - 1) \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(9) \times T(4) \times 3 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1324} := T(1 + T(3)) + T(T(2))^4 \qquad \mathbf{1356} := T(1 \times 3) \times (-5 + T(T(6)))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (2^{T(3)} - 1) \qquad \qquad \qquad := (T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(3 \times 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1325} := -1 + T(T(3)^2 + T(5)) \qquad \mathbf{1362} := (-1 - 3 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(5) + T(2^3)) - 1 \qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) - 3 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1326} := T(-13 + 2^6) \qquad \mathbf{1364} := T(T(T(1 + 3))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(4))$$

$$\qquad \qquad \qquad := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(6)) + T(T(3 + 1))$$

- 1365** := $13 \times T(6) \times 5$
:= $T(5) \times T(6 + T(3)) + 1$
- 1366** := $1 + T(3) \times T(T(6)) - T(6)$
:= $6 \times T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) + 1$
- 1368** := $T(1 \times 3 \times 6) \times 8$
:= $8 \times T(6 \times 3 \times 1)$
- 1372** := $(1 + 3) \times 7^{T(2)}$
:= $(T(T(T(2))) + T(7)) \times T(T(3)) + 1$
- 1374** := $-1 + (-3 + T(7)) \times T(T(4))$
:= $T(T(4)) \times (T(7) - 3) - 1$
- 1377** := $-1 + T(3 + 7 \times 7)$
:= $T(7 \times 7 + 3) - 1$
- 1378** := $T(-1 - 3 + 7 \times 8)$
:= $T(8 \times 7 - 3 - 1)$
- 1379** := $1^3 + T(7 + T(9))$
:= $T(T(9)) + 7^3 + 1$
- 1384** := $-T(T(-1 + T(3))) - T(8) + T(T(T(4)))$
:= $T(T(T(4))) - T(8) - T(T(T(3) - 1))$
- 1385** := $-1 + T(3) \times T(T(8) - T(5))$
:= $T(-5 + 8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1$
- 1386** := $T(1 \times 3 + 8) \times T(6)$
:= $T(6) \times T(8 + 3 \times 1)$
- 1389** := $-1 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) \times T(9)$
:= $T(9) \times T(8) - T(T(T(3 \times 1)))$
- 1392** := $(1 + T(T(T(3)))) \times (9 - T(2))$
:= $-T(2) + T(9) \times 31$
- 1396** := $1 + 3 \times T(9 + T(6))$
:= $T(T(6) + 9) \times 3 + 1$
- 1421** := $1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)) - 1))$
:= $-T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$
- 1422** := $T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))$
:= $-T(T(T(2))) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
- 1423** := $1 + T(T(T(4)) + 2) - T(T(T(3)))$
:= $-T(T(T(3))) + T(2 + T(T(4))) + 1$
- 1424** := $T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(2)) - T(T(4))$
:= $-T(T(4)) - T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
- 1425** := $-1 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2)) - T(T(5))$
:= $-T(T(5) + T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$
- 1426** := $1 + T(T(T(4)) - 2) - 6$
:= $-6 + T(-2 + T(T(4))) + 1$
- 1428** := $T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2))) - T(8)$
:= $-8 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$
- 1429** := $-1 - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)) \times 9)$
:= $T(9 \times T(T(2))) - T(T(4)) - 1$
- 1431** := $T((-1 + T(4)) \times T(3) - 1)$
:= $T(13 \times 4 + 1)$
- 1432** := $1 + T(T(T(4)) - T(3)/T(2))$
:= $T(-2 + T(T(3) + 4)) + 1$
- 1434** := $1 + T(T(4)) + T(-3 + T(T(4)))$
:= $T(T(T(4)) - 3) + T(T(4)) + 1$
- 1435** := $T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(T(3)) \times 5$
:= $T(53) + 4 \times 1$
- 1442** := $1 + T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 2)$

$$:= T(-2 + T(T(4))) + T(4) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1443} := T(1 + T(T(4))) - T(-4 + T(T(3)))$$

$$:= -T(T(T(3)) - 4) + T(T(T(4)) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1445} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) + T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1446} := T(-1 + 4) \times (T(4) + T(T(6)))$$

$$:= (T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(4 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1447} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(4) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1448} := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8)$$

$$:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1449} := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(4) \times 9$$

$$:= -T(9 + 4) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1455} := T(14) \times T(5) - T(T(5))$$

$$:= -T(5) - T(5) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1456} := (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(5 \times T(4) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1457} := T(-T(1 + T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) + T(54 \times 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1462} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(6) - 2$$

$$:= -T(2 \times 6) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1463} := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(6 + T(3))$$

$$:= -T(T(3) + 6) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1464} := T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - T(6) - T(T(4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) - T(T(4 \times 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1472} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - T(T(2))$$

$$:= -T(T(2)) - 7 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1474} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 7 - 4$$

$$:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) - T(T(4) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1479} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(T(-7 + 9))$$

$$:= -T(T(9 - 7)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1482} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - T(8 - T(T(2)))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(8) \times 41$$

$$\mathbf{1483} := T(-1 + T(T(4))) - 8 + T(3)$$

$$:= -T(T(3)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4 \times 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1484} := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8 - 4)) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1485} := T(1 + 48 + 5)$$

$$:= T(5 + 8 + 41)$$

$$\mathbf{1486} := 1 + T(48 + 6)$$

$$:= T(6 \times T(8)/4) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1487} := T(T(1 \times 4) + T(8)) + T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + T(T(8) + T(4 \times 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1492} := -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) - 2$$

$$:= -2 + 9 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1493} := 1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(9) - 3$$

$$:= -3 - T(9) + T(T(T(4))) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1494} := T(T(T(1 \times 4))) + 9 - T(T(4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + 9 - T(T(4 \times 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1495} := T(T(T(1 \times 4))) - 9 \times 5$$

$$:= T(-5 + 9) + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1496} := 1 + T(4) + T(9 \times 6)$$

$$:= T(6 \times 9) + T(4) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1497 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(7)) & &:= -8 + T(3) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(9)) + T(T(4)) + 1 \\
 1512 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(1 + T(T(2))) & &1539 := T((1 + 5) \times 3) \times 9 \\
 &:= -T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= 9 \times T(3 \times (5 + 1)) \\
 1519 &:= -T(1 + 5) + T(T(1 + 9)) & &1552 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(5) - T(2) \\
 &:= T(T(9 + 1)) - T(5 + 1) & &:= -T(2) + T(5) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 1522 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(2) \times T(T(2)) & &1555 := 15 + T(55) \\
 &:= -T(T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= T(5) + T(55 \times 1) \\
 1524 &:= 1 - T(5) - 2 + T(T(T(4))) & &1556 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 5 + T(6) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 2^{5-1} & &:= T(6) - 5 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 1525 &:= -15 + T(T(2 \times 5)) & &1561 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(6 \times 1) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(T(2 \times 5 \times 1)) & &:= T(1 \times 6) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\
 1526 &:= 1 - T(5) + T(T(T(-2 + 6))) & &1564 := (-1 + 5) \times 6 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(6 - 2))) - T(5) + 1 & &:= T(T(T(4))) + 6 \times (5 - 1) \\
 1527 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(2)) - 7 & &1573 := (1 + T(T(5))) \times (7 + T(3)) \\
 &:= -7 - T(T(2)) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= (T(3) + 7) \times (T(T(5)) + 1) \\
 1529 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 2 - 9 & &1574 := -1 + 5 \times 7 + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= -9 - 2 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= T(T(T(4))) + 7 \times 5 - 1 \\
 1532 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(3) - 2 & &1575 := T(1 + 5) \times 75 \\
 &:= -2^3 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= T(5) \times 7 \times T(5 \times 1) \\
 1533 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(3))/3 & &1576 := 1 + T(5) \times T(-7 + T(6)) \\
 &:= -T(T(3))/3 + T(T(T(5 - 1))) & &:= T(6) \times 75 + 1 \\
 1534 &:= -1 - 5 + T(T(T(3) + 4)) & &1579 := (-1 + 5) \times T(T(7)) - T(9) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(-3 + 5 + 1) & &:= -T(9) + T(T(7)) \times (5 - 1) \\
 1535 &:= T(T(T(1^5 + 3))) - 5 & &1582 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(8) + T(T(2)) \\
 &:= -5 + T(T(T(3) + 5 - 1)) & &:= 2^8 + T(51) \\
 1538 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(3) - 8 & &1593 := T(1 + T(T(-5 + 9))) - 3 \\
 & & &:= -3 + T(T(T(9 - 5)) + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1594 &:= (1 + 5) \times 9 + T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + 9 \times (5 + 1) \\ 1595 &:= T(T(-1 + 5)) + T(T(T(9 - 5))) \\ &:= T(T(-5 + 9)) + T(T(T(5 - 1))) \\ 1596 &:= T(1 \times 5 + T(9) + 6) \\ &:= 6 \times T(9) + T(51) \\ 1616 &:= -1 + T(T(6)) \times (1 + 6) \\ &:= T(T(6)) \times (1 + 6) - 1 \\ 1617 &:= 1 \times T(T(6)) \times 1 \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(1 \times 6 \times 1)) \\ 1618 &:= 1 + T(T(6)) \times (-1 + 8) \\ &:= (8 - 1) \times T(T(6)) + 1 \\ 1623 &:= (1 + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + 1) \\ 1624 &:= (-1 - T(T(6))) \times (T(2) - T(4)) \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(2 + 6 - 1)) \\ 1625 &:= (-1 + 6) \times T(25) \\ &:= 5 \times T(26 - 1) \\ 1637 &:= -1 + (T(T(6)) + 3) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times (3 + T(T(6))) - 1 \\ 1638 &:= -T(-1 + 6) + T(T(T(3))) + T(8) \\ &:= T(T(8)/3) \times T(6 \times 1) \\ 1639 &:= 1 + T(6) \times T(3 + 9) \\ &:= T(9 + 3) \times T(6) + 1 \\ 1645 &:= (-1 + 6 \times T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(T(4)) \times 6 - 1) \\ 1648 &:= (T(-1 + T(6)) - 4) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times (-4 + T(T(6) - 1)) \\ 1652 &:= -1 + T(-T(6) + T(T(5) - T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(T(2) + 5) + T(6)) - 1 \\ 1653 &:= T(T(1 \times 6) + T(5 + 3)) \\ &:= T(T(3 + 5) + T(6 \times 1)) \\ 1654 &:= -1 \times 6 + T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) - 6 \times 1 \\ 1656 &:= T(T(1 + 6) - 5) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(-5 + T(6 + 1)) \\ 1657 &:= 1 + 6 \times T(-5 + T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7) - 5) \times 6 + 1 \\ 1711 &:= T(-1 - 7 + T(11)) \\ &:= T(T(11) - 7 - 1) \\ 1712 &:= 1 + T((T(7) + 1) \times 2) \\ &:= T(2 \times (1 + T(7))) + 1 \\ 1722 &:= T(-1 + 7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times T(T(T(2)) \times 7 - 1) \\ 1728 &:= (-1 + 7^2) \times T(8) \\ &:= T(8)^{T(2)} / (T(7) - 1) \\ 1755 &:= T(T(-1 + 7) + 5) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times T(5 + T(7 - 1)) \\ 1763 &:= -1 + T(7) \times 63 \\ &:= 3 \times T(6) \times T(7) - 1 \\ 1764 &:= T(-1 + 7) \times T(6) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(6) \times T(7 - 1) \\ 1769 &:= -1 + T(-7 + T(6) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(9) + T(6) - 7) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1782} := (-1 + T(7)) \times T(8 + T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2) + 8) \times (T(7) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1785} := (-1 + T(7 + 8)) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times (T(8 + 7) - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1823} := -1 + 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(3))))$$

$$:= (T(T(T(3))) - T(2)) \times 8 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1825} := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(-T(T(T(2))) + 81)$$

$$\mathbf{1826} := -1 + 8 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(6)$$

$$:= -T(6) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 8 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1827} := (1 + 8) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7))/2 \times (8 + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1829} := -1 + T(T(8 - T(2)) + T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9) + T(-T(2) + 8)) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1844} := (T(T(-1 + 8)) + T(T(4))) \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(8 - 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1846} := -T(1 + 8) + T(T(T(4)) + 6)$$

$$:= T(6 + T(T(4))) - T(8 + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1847} := -1 + 8 \times T(T(T(-4 + 7)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(7 - 4))) \times 8 - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1848} := T(T(T(1 + 8/4))) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(T(-4 + 8 - 1)))$$

$$\mathbf{1853} := -1 - T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(8)) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1864} := (1 + T(T(8) - 6)) \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(-6 + T(8)) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1875} := T(T(1 + 8)) + 7 \times T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times 7 + T(T(8 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1883} := -1 + T(8) + 8 \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) \times 8 + T(8) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1895} := (1 + T(T(8) - 9)) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times (T(-9 + T(8)) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1896} := (1 + T(8)) \times T(9) + T(T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(9) \times (T(8) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1922} := -T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)) - T(T(9) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1925} := -T(T(1 + 9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1928} := (-1 + T(9))^2 - 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9 + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1932} := (1 + T(9)) \times T(T(3)) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times T(T(3)) \times (T(9) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1937} := -1 + T(T(9)) + T(T(3) \times 7)$$

$$:= T(7 \times T(3)) + T(T(9)) - 1$$

$$\mathbf{1938} := T(T(1 \times 9)) + T(T(3) + T(8))$$

$$:= T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(T(9 \times 1))$$

$$\mathbf{1939} := 1 + T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9)) + T(-3 + T(9)) + 1$$

$$\mathbf{1944} := -T(1 + T(9)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))$$

$$:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(9) + 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1946} := T(1 + 9) + T(T(T(4)) + 6)$$

$$:= T(6 + T(T(4))) + T(9 + 1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1947 &:= 1 + T(T(9) + T(4)) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + T(T(4) + T(9)) + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1952 &:= -1 + T(T(9) + T(5) + 2) \\ &:= T(T(2) + 59) - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1953 &:= T(1 \times 9 + 53) \\ &:= T(3 + 59 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1967 &:= T(T(1 + 9)) + T(6) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + T(6) + T(T(9 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1975 &:= -T(1 + 9) + T(T(7)) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times T(T(7)) - T(9 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1978 &:= (1 + T(9)) \times (7 + T(8)) \\ &:= (T(8) + 7) \times (T(9) + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1992 &:= T(T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(9) + T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(T(2)) + T(9)) + T(T(9 - 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1995 &:= 19 \times T(9 + 5) \\ &:= T(5) + T(9) \times (T(9) - 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1997 &:= -19 + T(9 \times 7) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(9) \times T(9 \times 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1998 &:= T(1 + 9/9) \times T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) \times T(9/9 + 1) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2016 &:= T((T(2) \times T(0 \times 1 + 6))) \\ &:= T(61 + 02) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2022 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(02) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(02)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2078 &:= -2 + T(T(07) + T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8) + T(7)) - 02 \end{aligned}$$

$$2079 := T(T(2) \times 07) \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times T(7 \times T(02))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2122 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(1 + T(2))) + T(T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2)) + T(T(1 + T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2124 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(4^{T(2)} + 1) - T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2135 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(1 + T(3)))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (T(T(T(3) + 1)) + T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2136 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) - 1)) + T(3 \times T(6)) \\ &:= T(63) + T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2139 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(-1 + T(T(3)) + T(9)) \\ &:= T(93 - 1)/2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2142 &:= T(T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(4))) - T(2) \\ &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4)) + T(1 + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2143 &:= -2 + T(1 + 4^3) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) - 1) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2144 &:= -2 + 1 + T(T(4) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(4) + T(T(4))) - 1^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2145 &:= T(-2 + 1 + T(-4 + T(5))) \\ &:= T(5 \times (T(4) \times 1 + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2147 &:= 2 + T(-1 + T(4 + 7)) \\ &:= T(T(7 + 4) - 1) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2148 &:= -T(2) + T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)) - 1) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2156 &:= -T(T(T(2) + 1)) + T(T(5 + 6)) \\ &:= T(T(6 + 5)) - T(T(1 + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2162 &:= 2 \times T(1 + T(6 + T(2))) \\ &:= T(T(T(2) + 6) + 1) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(3)^2 + 2) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2166} & := T(2)^{1+6} - T(6) \\
 & := T(66 - 1) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2169} & := (T(T(2) + 1) + T(T(6))) \times 9 \\
 & := 9 \times (T(T(6)) + T(1 + T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2175} & := T(2 - 1 + T(7)) \times 5 \\
 & := 5 \times T(T(7) + 1^2) \\
 \mathbf{2177} & := (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times 7 + T(T(7)) \\
 & := -7 + T(7) \times T(12) \\
 \mathbf{2178} & := T(T(T(T(2) + 1))) - T(7) + T(T(8)) \\
 & := T(T(8)) - T(7) + T(T(T(1 + T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2183} & := -T(T(T(2)) + 1) + T(T(8 + 3)) \\
 & := T(T(3 + 8)) - T(1 + T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2184} & := T(T(T(2)) + 1) \times T(8 + 4) \\
 & := T(4 + 8) \times T(1 + T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2196} & := -T(T(T(2)) - 1) + T(T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := T(T(6) + T(9)) - T(-1 + T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2198} & := 2 \times T(1 + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 & := T(8) + T(T(9) + 1) \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{2205} & := -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 05)) \\
 & := 5 \times T(T(T(02))) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2208} & := T(T(2) + 20) \times 8 \\
 & := T(T(8 + T(02))) - T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2209} & := -2 + T(T(2 + 09)) \\
 & := (T(9) + 02)^2 \\
 \mathbf{2221} & := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(2) + 1) \\
 & := T(1 + T(2)) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2223} & := T(2) \times T(2 + T(2^3)) \\
 & := T(T(3)^2 + 2) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2224} & := (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(2) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 & := T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{2226} & := T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 & := T(T(6)) - T(T(T(2))) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\
 \mathbf{2227} & := T(2^{T(T(2))}) + T(T(T(2))) \times 7 \\
 & := 7 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(2^{T(T(2))}) \\
 \mathbf{2229} & := T(T(T(2))) - T(2) + T(T(2 + 9)) \\
 & := T(T(9 + 2)) + T(2) \times T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{2231} & := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(3)) - 1 \\
 & := -1 + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2232} & := T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2 + T(3) + T(2))) \\
 & := (T(T(2)^3) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{2233} & := T(T(T(2 + 2))) + 3 \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 & := 3 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2 + 2))) \\
 \mathbf{2234} & := 2 + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) \\
 & := T(T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))) + 2 + T(T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2235} & := T(2) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 5)) \\
 & := 5 \times (T(T(3))^2 + T(T(2))) \\
 \mathbf{2237} & := -2 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(3)))) + T(7) \\
 & := T(7) + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 2 \\
 \mathbf{2238} & := T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2)) + T(T(3 + 8)) \\
 & := T(T(8 + 3)) + T(2)^{T(2)} \\
 \mathbf{2239} & := T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(9)) \\
 & := T(T(9) + T(T(3))) + T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{2242} & := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) + \\
 & \quad + T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \\
 & := T(T(T(2))) + T(4) +
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(T(2))))))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2243 &:= T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4 + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) - 4 + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2244 &:= T(T(2) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times (T(T(4) \times T(2) + T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2245 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2))) \times T(4) - 5 \\ &:= -5 + (T(4) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2246 &:= -2^{T(T(2))} + T(4) \times T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) \times T(4) - 2^{T(T(2))} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2247 &:= T(2 + T(T(2))) + T(T(4 + 7)) \\ &:= T(T(7 + 4)) + T(2^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2248 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2252 &:= T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2253 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5 + T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3) + (5))) + T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2254 &:= -T(T(T(2) + T(2))) + T(T(5) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(2)) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2256 &:= T(T(2) + T(T(2))) + T(T(5 + 6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + (T(5) \times T(2))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2259 &:= T(2) + T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(9) \\ &:= T(95)/2 - T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2262 &:= T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \times 6 - T(T(2)) \\ &:= -T(T(2)) + 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2264 &:= T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \times 6 - 4 \\ &:= -4 + 6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2265 &:= T(T(2 + T(2))) + T(65) \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T(62 + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2266 &:= T(T(2 + 2)) + T(66) \\ &:= T(66) + T(T(2 + 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2268 &:= -T(T(T(2)) + T(T(2))) + T(68) \\ &:= T(8)/6 \times T(T(2)^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2269 &:= T(T(2) + 2^6) - 9 \\ &:= 9 \times T(6) + T(2^{T(T(2))}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2271 &:= T(2) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(7) - 1) \\ &:= T(-1 + T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2274 &:= T(T(2)) \times (-T(T(2)) + 7 \times T(T(4))) \\ &:= (T(T(4)) \times 7 - T(T(2))) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2275 &:= (2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 7) \times 5 \\ &:= T(-5 + 72) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2277 &:= 2 + T(-T(2) + T(7)) \times 7 \\ &:= 7 \times T(T(7) - T(2)) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2278 &:= T(T(T(2)) - T(2) + T(7) + T(8)) \\ &:= T(-8 + 72 + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2279 &:= 2 + T(-T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times 9 \\ &:= 9 \times T(T(7) - T(T(2))) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2281 &:= T(2) + T(T(T(2) + 8) + 1) \\ &:= T(1 + T(8 + T(2))) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2283 &:= 2^{T(T(2))} \times T(8) - T(T(3)) \\ &:= -T(T(3)) + (8 \times T(T(2)))^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2284 &:= T(2) + T(2 + T(8)) + T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8) + 2) + T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2286 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(8) \times T(6)) &:= 2 \times T(T(5) \times 3 + T(2)) \\
 &:= (T(6) + T(T(8) + 2)) \times T(2) \\
 2288 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + 8)) \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(8 + 2) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 2289 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(8) - 9) \\
 &:= (T(9) + 8^2) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 2292 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2) \times 9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) + T(T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2295 &:= T(2^{T(2)} + 9) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(T(9)/T(2) + 2) \\
 2299 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 2 + T(T(9)) + T(T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9)) + T(T(9)) - 2 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2304 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(04) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(T(03))) - T(T(2)) \\
 2324 &:= 2 \times (-T(3^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2)^3)) \times 2 \\
 2325 &:= (2 + 3) \times T(2 \times T(5)) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(-2 + 32) \\
 2328 &:= -T(T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(2 \times T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(8))/T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) - T(2) \\
 2331 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(T(3) - 1))) \\
 &:= T(1 + 3) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 2334 &:= -T(T(2)) + (3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(4) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3)) + T(2) \\
 2338 &:= -2 + 3 \times T(3 + T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(8) + 3) \times 3 - 2 \\
 2352 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3) + 5) + 2) \\
 2354 &:= -T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times T(4) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5))/3) - T(T(2)) \\
 2355 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) \times 5)) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(5 \times T(3)) + T(T(2))) \\
 2358 &:= T(2) \times (T(3 \times 5) + T(T(8))) \\
 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(5))) \times T(3)/2 \\
 2364 &:= -T(T(2)) + (T(3) + T(T(6))) \times T(4) \\
 &:= T(4) \times (T(T(6)) + (T(3))) - T(T(2)) \\
 2365 &:= T(2^{T(3)} + 6) - T(T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(T(5)) + T((T(T(6)) - T(T(3)))/T(2)) \\
 2373 &:= (T(T(2 + 3)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-7 + T(T(3 + 2))) \\
 2374 &:= -T(2)^3 + 7^4 \\
 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times T(3) - 2 \\
 2375 &:= (2 + T(T(3)) \times (-7 + T(T(5)))) \\
 &:= (T(T(5)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\
 2376 &:= (-T(-2 + T(3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6 \\
 &:= 6 \times (T(T(7)) - T(T(3) - 2)) \\
 2377 &:= T(T(2^3)) + T(T(T(7)))/7 \\
 &:= T(T(T(7)))/7 + T(T(3)^2) \\
 2378 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (-T(8) + T(T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times 2 \\
 2379 &:= -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(T(7)) - 9) \\
 &:= (-9 + T(T(7))) \times T(3) - T(2) \\
 2382 &:= T(-T(2) + T(T(3))) + T(T(8 + T(2))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2) + 8)) + T(T(3) \times T(2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2384 &:= -T(T(2)) + (T(T(T(3))) + 8) \times T(4) \\ &:= T(4) \times (8 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2385 &:= T(2) \times (T(3 + T(8)) + T(5)) \\ &:= (T(5) + T(T(8) + 3)) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2387 &:= T(T(2) + T(3 + 8)) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(T(8 + 3) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2388 &:= 2 \times T(T(3) \times 8) + T(8) \\ &:= T(8) + T(8 \times T(3)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2394 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(3)) \times (9 + T(4)) \\ &:= (T(4) + 9) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2397 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(3) \times (T(9) - T(T(7))) \\ &:= (T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2398 &:= -2 + T(-T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(T(9) - T(T(3))) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2412 &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4) + 1) + T(2)) \\ &:= -T(2) + T(T(1 + T(4)) + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2413 &:= -2 + T(T(T(4) + 1) + 3) \\ &:= T(3 + T(1 + T(4))) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2415 &:= T(T(2) + T(-4 + 15)) \\ &:= T(5 + 1 \times 4^{T(2)}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2421 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))) - T(4))) + T(T(T(T(2))) - 1) \\ &:= T(-1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2422 &:= T(T(T(2))) + (T(T(4)) - T(T(2)))^2 \\ &:= (T(T(T(2)))/T(2))^4 + T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2428 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4) - T(2))) - 8 \\ &:= -8 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4) - T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2432 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) \times 32 \\ &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(T(3))) - T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2433 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T((4 + 3))) - 3 \\ &:= T(3) \times T(T(3 + 4)) - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2435 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) - T(5) \\ &:= -T(5) + (T(-T(3) + T(T(4)))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2436 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(4 - 3 + 6)) \\ &:= 6 \times T(3 \times T(4)) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2437 &:= -T(2) + 4 + T(3) \times T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) \times T(3) + 4 - T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2438 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 4 + T(T(3 + 8)) \\ &:= T(T(8 + 3)) - 4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2439 &:= -T(T(2 \times 4)) + 3 \times T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) \times 3 - T(T(4 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2443 &:= -T(2 + T(T(4))) + 4^{T(3)} \\ &:= T(T(T(3) + 4)) + T(42) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2444 &:= (T(T(2 \times 4)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times (-T(T(4)) + T(T(4 \times 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2445 &:= T(24) + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \\ &:= (-5 + T(T(4) \times 4)) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2446 &:= T(2^4) + T(4) \times T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) \times T(4) + T(4^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2448 &:= T(2^4) \times (T(4) + 8) \\ &:= (8 + T(4)) \times T(4^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2452 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4) + T(T(5 + T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 5)) + T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$2454 := -T(T(T(2))) - T(4) + T(T(5) + T(T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(4)) \times T(5 + 4) - T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2455} := T(2) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(5))) - 5$$

$$:= (-5 + T(-T(5) + T(T(4)))) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2457} := T(T(2 + 4) + 5) \times 7$$

$$:= -T(7) + T(T(5 \times 4)/T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2462} := (T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)) - 6)) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(T(6)) + T(4)^{T(2)})$$

$$\mathbf{2463} := T(T(T(2))) + T(T(-T(4) + T(6))) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2464} := -T(T(T(2))) + T(4 + T(T(6) - T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) + T(6) + T(42)$$

$$\mathbf{2465} := (-T(2) + T(T(4) + T(6))) \times 5$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(T(6)) - T(4)^{T(2)}$$

$$\mathbf{2467} := T(T(T(2))) + T(4) + 6 \times T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(4) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2469} := -T(T(2)) + T(4 + 6) \times T(9)$$

$$:= T(9) \times T(6 + 4) - T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2472} := T(T(2)) + T(4 \times 7) \times T(T(2))$$

$$:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times (4 + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2473} := -T(T(2)) + T(T(4) \times 7) - T(3)$$

$$:= -T(3) + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2474} := -T(T(T(2))) + T(4) + T(7 \times T(4))$$

$$:= T(4) + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2475} := -T(T(2) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(7) - T(5)))$$

$$:= T(5) + (T(T(7)) + 4) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2476} := -T(2) + T(T(4) \times 7) - 6$$

$$:= -6 + T(7 \times T(4)) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2478} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(4 + 7)) + T(8)$$

$$:= -8 + T(T(7)) + T(4^{T(2)})$$

$$\mathbf{2479} := T(2) + T(T(4) \times 7) - 9$$

$$:= T(T(9)) + (T(7) + T(4))^2$$

$$\mathbf{2481} := T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) \times T(8 + 1)$$

$$:= T(1 + 8) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2482} := -T(2) + T(4 + T(8 + T(2)))$$

$$:= -T(2) + T(-8 + T(T(4) + 2))$$

$$\mathbf{2483} := -2 + T(4 + T(8 + 3))$$

$$:= T(T(3 + 8) + 4) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2485} := T(-T(2 + 4) + T(8 + 5))$$

$$:= T(5 \times (8 + 4 + 2))$$

$$\mathbf{2487} := 2 + T(T(T(4)) + 8 + 7)$$

$$:= T(7 \times T(8 - 4)) + 2$$

$$\mathbf{2488} := T(2) + T(T(4 + 8) - 8)$$

$$:= T(-8 + T(8 + 4)) + T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2492} := T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9) - 2)$$

$$:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9) + 4)) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2493} := -T(2) + T(T(4)) \times T(9) + T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) + T(9) \times T(T(4)) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2495} := (-T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times (-T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2496} := T(T(T(2)) + 4) \times T(9) + (T(6))$$

$$:= (-6 + T(9)) \times 4^{T(2)}$$

$$\mathbf{2497} := -T(T(2)) + T(T(4)) \times T(9) + T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) + T(9) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2499} := T(T(T(2))) \times (4 + T(T(9)))/9$$

$$:= (T(T(9))/9 + 4) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2505} := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - T(05)$$

$$:= (-T(5) + T(T(05)) \times T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2513} := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1 - T(3)$$

$$:= (-T(3) - 1 + T(T(5)) \times T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2514} := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - T(-1 + 4)$$

$$:= -T(41) + T(5)^{T(2)}$$

$$\mathbf{2515} := T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1 \times 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(15) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2517} := -T(2) + T(T(5)) \times T(-1 + 7)$$

$$:= T(7 - 1) \times T(T(5)) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2532} := T(T(2)) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2534} := T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - T(T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$:= -T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)) + T(T(5) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2535} := T(T(2) + T(5 + T(3))) + T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2536} := T(25) + T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) + T(5^2)$$

$$\mathbf{2541} := T(T(T(2))) \times (T(5 + T(4)) + 1)$$

$$:= (1 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(5 - 2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2543} := 2 + (T(5) - 4) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3))) \times (-4 + T(5)) + 2$$

$$\mathbf{2544} := -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(5) + 4 + T(T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4)) + 4 + T(5)) - T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2545} := 2 \times T(5 \times T(4)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(T(4) \times 5) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2546} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + 5 + T(4) \times T(T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) \times T(4) + 5 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2547} := T(T(-T(T(2)) + T(5))) + T(T(T(4))) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5) \times T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2548} := T(2 + 5) \times (T(T(4)) + T(8))$$

$$:= (T(8) + T(T(4))) \times T(5 + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2549} := -T(T(T(2))) - 5 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) - 5 - T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2553} := -T(2) + T(5 + T(5 + T(3)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(3) + 5) + 5) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2554} := -2 + T(5 + T(T(5) - 4))$$

$$:= T(-4 + 5 \times T(5)) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2555} := T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - T(55)$$

$$:= -T(55) + T(T(5) \times T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2556} := T(-T(2 + 5) + T(T(5)) - T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6) + 5 \times 5 \times 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2561} := (2 + T(T(5))) \times T(6) - 1$$

$$:= -1 + T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2562} := (2 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(6/2))$$

$$:= T(T(2) \times 6) \times T(5) - T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2563} := -2 + T(5) \times T(6 \times 3)$$

$$:= T(3 \times 6) \times T(5) - 2$$

$$\mathbf{2565} := T((-2 + 5) \times 6) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(6 \times (5 - 2))$$

$$\mathbf{2568} := (T(T(2)) + T(5) \times T(6)) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(6) \times T(5) + T(T(2)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2569 &:= T(T(2 \times 5)) - 6 + T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) - 6 + T(T(5 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(8 \times 9) - T(5) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2572 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5 + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) + T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2617 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 6 - 1)) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) + T((1 + T(6)) \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2574 &:= 2 \times (-T(T(5) + 7) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(7 + T(5))) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2619 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(6 - 1))) - T(9) \\ &:= T(T(9 - 1)) + T(62) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2577 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5) + T(7) + T(7)) \\ &:= T(-7 + T(7 + 5)) + T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2622 &:= T(2 \times 6^2) - T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(2 \times T(2 + 6)) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2579 &:= -2 - T(T(5)) + T(T(7) + T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9) + T(7)) - T(T(5)) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2624 &:= T(2 \times 6^2) - 4 \\ &:= -4 + T(2 \times 6^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2583 &:= (T(2) + T(T(5))) \times T(T(8)/T(3)) \\ &:= 3 \times T(T(8) + T(5)/T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2625 &:= -T(2) + T(6 + T(T(T(2)) + 5)) \\ &:= 5^{T(2)} \times T(T(6/2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2584 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times (-T(8) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= 4 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))/T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2626 &:= -2 + T(6 \times 2 \times 6) \\ &:= T(6 \times 2 \times 6) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2585 &:= T(25) \times 8 - T(5) \\ &:= -T(5) + 8 \times T(5^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2628 &:= T(2 + 62 + 8) \\ &:= T(8 + 2 + 62) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2586 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 + T(86) \\ &:= T(68) + T(T(5)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2634 &:= 2 \times (T(6) + T(3)^4) \\ &:= T(4 \times 3 \times 6) + T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2589 &:= T(T(T(T(2) + 5)) + T(T(8) - 9)) \\ &:= T(-9 + T(8)) + T(T(5 + T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2638 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(T(3)) - 8 \\ &:= -8 + T(3) \times T(6)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2595 &:= (T(2^5) - 9) \times 5 \\ &:= T(T(5)) + T(9) \times T(5 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2643 &:= T(T(2 + 6)) \times 4 - T(T(3)) \\ &:= -T(T(3)) + 4 \times T(6^2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2596 &:= T(T(2 \times 5)) + T(T(9)) + T(6) \\ &:= T(6) + T(T(9)) + T(T(5 \times 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2644 &:= T(2 + T(6)) \times 4 + T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + 4 \times T((T(6) + 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2597 &:= T(2 + T(T(5)) - T(9)) - T(T(7)) \\ &:= -T(T(7)) + T(-T(9) + T(T(5)) + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2646 &:= T(T(2) + T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6 - 4)) \times T(6)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$2598 := -2 \times T(5) + T(9 \times 8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2648 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(6) + 4)) \times 8 \\ &:= (T(T(8)) - 4) \times (6 - 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2652 &:= 2 \times T(T(6) + T(5) \times 2) \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(5) + 6^2) \\
 2664 &:= T(T(2 + 6)) \times (-6 + T(4)) \\
 &:= (T(4) - 6) \times T(6^2) \\
 2667 &:= (T(2) + T(T(6) + 6)) \times 7 \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(6) + 6) + T(2)) \\
 2672 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 6)) - T(T(7)) - T(2) \\
 &:= -T(2) - T(T(7)) + T(T(6 \times 2)) \\
 2673 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= T(3) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(6)) + T(T(2)) \\
 2674 &:= T(T(T(-2 + 6))) - T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(6)) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2681 &:= T(T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(8)) - 1 \\
 &:= -1 + T(T(8)) + T(T(6) \times T(2)) \\
 2682 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(6)) + T(8)^2 \\
 &:= (T(T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2685 &:= (T(T(2) \times 6) + 8) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (T(T(5)) + 8) \times T(6) - T(2) \\
 2688 &:= 2 \times T(6) \times 8 \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times 8 \times T(6) \times 2 \\
 2691 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(9 - 1))) \\
 &:= (T(T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(6))) \times T(2) \\
 2694 &:= -T(T(2)) + 6 \times T(9) \times T(4) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(9) \times 6 - T(T(2)) \\
 2695 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(6) - 9) - 5) \\
 &:= -5 + 9 \times T(T(6) + T(2)) \\
 2697 &:= 2 - 6 + T(T(9) + T(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(7) + T(9)) - 6 + 2 \\
 2701 &:= T(2 + 70 + 1) \\
 &:= T(1 + 072) \\
 2708 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(70) - 8 \\
 &:= 80 + T(72) \\
 2712 &:= (T(T(T(2)) \times 7) + 1) \times T(2) \\
 &:= T(2) \times (1 + T(7 \times T(T(2)))) \\
 2722 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7) + T(T(2) + T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2)^2) + T(7)) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 2723 &:= (2 \times 7)^{T(2)} - T(T(3)) \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + (2 \times 7)^{T(2)} \\
 2728 &:= (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times (-2 + 7^{T(2)}) \\
 2734 &:= (2 \times 7)^3 - T(4) \\
 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(3)) - 7)^{T(2)} \\
 2736 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) + T(3 + T(6)) \\
 &:= (T(T(6) + 3) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2))) \\
 2738 &:= -T(T(2)) + 7^3 \times 8 \\
 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(37)) \times 2 \\
 2742 &:= 2 \times (-7 + T(T(T(4)) - T(2))) \\
 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(T(4))) - 7) \times 2 \\
 2744 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(74) - T(4) \\
 &:= (-4 - T(4) + T(7))^{T(2)} \\
 2745 &:= (2^7 + T(T(4))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times T(2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2747 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(74) - 7 \\ &:= -T(7) + T(-T(4) + T(7) \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (T(T(8) - 7) + T(7)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2748 &:= T(2) \times T(7) + 4 \times T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) \times 4 + T(7) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2779 &:= (-T(T(T(2))) + T(7)) \times (T(T(7)) - 9) \\ &:= (-9 + T(T(7))) \times (T(7) - T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2749 &:= T(2) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) - 9 \\ &:= -9 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2782 &:= T(2)^7 + T(T(8) - 2) \\ &:= T(2) \times T(T(8)) + T(7)^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2754 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7 + 5) - 4) \\ &:= T(4) \times T(-5 + T(7)) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2783 &:= T(-T(T(2)) + T(7)) \times (8 + 3) \\ &:= (3 + 8) \times T(T(7) - T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2756 &:= 2 \times T(7 + T(T(5) - 6)) \\ &:= T(T(-6 + T(5)) + 7) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2784 &:= (2 + T(7)) + T(T(8)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7 - 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2758 &:= -2 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5)) - T(8)) \\ &:= T(-T(8) + T(T(5))) - T(T(7)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2786 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(7)) \times 8 - T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(6) \times (-8 + T(T(7))) / T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2759 &:= -T(T(T(2)) + 7) + T(T(T(5)) - T(9)) \\ &:= T(-T(9) + T(T(5))) - T(7 + T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2787 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(78 - 7) \\ &:= T(78 - 7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2764 &:= T(2) \times T(7 \times 6) + T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) + T(6 \times 7) \times T(2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2789 &:= 2 \times 7 + T(T(T(8)) / 9) \\ &:= T(9) + 8 \times 7^{T(2)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2768 &:= (T(-T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times (T(6) + T(T(7) - T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2793 &:= (-T(2) + T(7 + 9)) \times T(T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(3)) \times (T(9 + 7) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2771 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(77) - 1 \\ &:= -1 + T(77) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2794 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(7) \times (T(9) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= (T(T(4)) + T(9)) \times T(7) - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2773 &:= -2 + T(77 - 3) \\ &:= T(-3 + 77) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2795 &:= -T(T(2) + 7) + T(-T(9) + T(T(5))) \\ &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(9)) - T(7 + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2774 &:= T(T(2)) - 7 + T(74) \\ &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times 7 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2796 &:= T(2 \times (T(7) + 9)) + T(6) \\ &:= T(6) + T((9 + T(7)) \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2775 &:= T(2 + 77 - 5) \\ &:= T(-5 + 7 + 72) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2797 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(7)) - T(9) + T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) - T(9) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$2778 := T(T(2)) + 77 \times T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2805 &:= T(-T(2) + T(8)) \times 05 \\ &:= 5 \times T(T(08) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2808 &:= (-2 + 80) \times T(8) \\
 &:= T(8) \times T(T(08)/T(2)) \\
 2812 &:= 2 \times T(T(8) + 1) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(1 + T(8)) \times 2 \\
 2814 &:= 2 + T(T(8) + 1) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times T(1 + T(8)) + 2 \\
 2823 &:= 2 \times T(8)^2 + T(T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 2 \times T(8)^2 \\
 2826 &:= T(2) \times (T(T(8)) + T(2 + T(6))) \\
 &:= (T(T(6) + 2) + T(T(8))) \times T(2) \\
 2828 &:= 2 \times (T(8^2) - T(T(8))) \\
 &:= (T(8^2) - T(T(8))) \times 2 \\
 2829 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(8) - T(T(2))) + T(9) \\
 &:= T(9 + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 2835 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(8) - 3)) \times 5 \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(3 + T(8) \times 2) \\
 2838 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8) - T(3)) + 8) \\
 &:= (T(T(8) - T(3)) + 8) \times T(T(2)) \\
 2842 &:= T(28) \times (T(4) - T(2)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(8)^2 \\
 2845 &:= T(-T(2) + T(8 + 4)) - 5 \\
 &:= -5 + T(T(4 + 8) - T(2)) \\
 2847 &:= -T(2) + T(-8 + T(T(4))) + T(7) \\
 &:= T(74) + T(8) \times 2 \\
 2862 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(8) + T(6)^2) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) + T(6) \times T(8 \times 2) \\
 2872 &:= 2 \times T(T(8)) + T(T(7 + T(2))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2) + 7)) + T(T(8)) \times 2 \\
 2874 &:= -T(2) + T(T(8)) + T(T(7 + 4)) \\
 &:= T(T(4 + 7)) + T(T(8)) - T(2) \\
 2877 &:= (-T(2) + 8 + T(T(7))) \times 7 \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(7)) + 8 - T(2)) \\
 2883 &:= T(T(2)) + T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3 + 8)) + T(T(8)) + T(T(2)) \\
 2884 &:= (T(2 + 8) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\
 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8/2 \\
 2886 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8 \times T(T(8))/T(6) \\
 &:= (T(6) - 8) \times T(T(8))/T(2) \\
 2887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 &:= T(7) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2889 &:= T(2) \times (-T(8) - T(8) + T(T(9))) \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(8) - T(8)) \times T(2) \\
 2892 &:= 2 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(9) - T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(2))) \times 9 + T(T(T(8)/T(2))) \\
 2894 &:= -T(T(T(2))) + (8 + T(9)) \times T(T(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(9) + 8) - T(T(T(2))) \\
 2895 &:= T(2 + 8 \times 9) + T(T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(9) \times 8^2 \\
 2898 &:= 2 \times T(8 + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 &:= T(8) + T(T(9) + 8) \times 2 \\
 2918 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(9 + 1) - 8 \\
 &:= (-8 + T(T(1 + 9) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 2922 &:= (T(T(2)) \times 9)^2 + T(T(2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + (T(T(2)) \times 9)^2$$

$$\mathbf{2923} := T(-2 + T(9 + T(2))) - 3$$

$$:= -3 + T(-2 + T(9 + T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2924} := -2 + T(T(9 + 2) + T(4))$$

$$:= 4 \times (2 + 9^{T(2)})$$

$$\mathbf{2925} := (T(T(T(2))) \times 9 + T(T(2))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= (-T(T(5))/2 + T(T(9))) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2926} := T(-2 + T(9 - T(2) + 6))$$

$$:= T(T(6 - 2) + T(9 + 2))$$

$$\mathbf{2927} := 2 + 9 \times T(-T(2) + T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7) - T(2)) \times 9 + 2$$

$$\mathbf{2928} := (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(9))/T(2)) \times 8$$

$$:= T(T(8) + T(T(2))) + T(9)^2$$

$$\mathbf{2932} := T(T(2)) + T(T(9 + 3) - 2)$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(T(3 + 9) - 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2937} := T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(3) \times T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) \times T(3) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2952} := T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(5) + 2)$$

$$:= -T(2 + T(5)) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2955} := T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \times T(5) + T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) + T(5) \times 9 \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2957} := T(2) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(5)) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) - T(T(5)) + T(T(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2961} := T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(T(6 - 1))$$

$$:= -T(T(-1 + 6)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2962} := T(-2 + T(9)) + T(T(6) \times T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2) \times T(6)) + T(T(9) - 2)$$

$$\mathbf{2964} := (-T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times (T(6) + T(T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(4)) \times 6 \times 9 - T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2965} := 2 \times T(9 \times 6) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(6 \times 9) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2973} := 2 \times T(T(9)) + T(7 \times T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3) \times 7) + T(T(9)) \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{2975} := T(T(2) \times 9 + 7) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times T(T(7) + 9 - T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2976} := T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(-7 + T(6))$$

$$:= 6 \times T(T(7) + 9/T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2977} := T(2) \times T(9) + T(T(7)) \times 7$$

$$:= T(T(7)) \times 7 + T(9) \times T(2)$$

$$\mathbf{2978} := -T(T(2)) \times T(9) + T(T(7)) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(7)) - T(9) \times T(T(2))$$

$$\mathbf{2982} := -T(T(T(2))) + T(98 - T(T(T(2))))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(9)) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$\mathbf{2985} := T(2) \times T(T(9)) - 8 \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times 8 + T(9)^2$$

$$\mathbf{2988} := (2 + T(9) + T(8)) \times T(8)$$

$$:= T(8) \times (T(8) + T(9) + 2)$$

$$\mathbf{3075} := -T(3) + T(T(07 + 5))$$

$$:= T(T(5 + 7)) - T(03)$$

$$\mathbf{3078} := -3 + T(078)$$

$$:= T(8 + 70) - 3$$

$$\mathbf{3081} := T(T(3 + 08 + 1))$$

$$:= T(1 + 80 - 3)$$

- 3084** := $3 + T(T(08 + 4))$
:= $T(T(4 + 8)) + 03$
:= $((T(T(9)) + T((8 - 1))) \times 3)$
- 3122** := $(T(T(T(3 + 1))) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 2$
:= $2 \times (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(1 + 3))))$
- 3123** := $T(T(3)) + T(T(12)) + T(T(3))$
:= $T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) + (T(T(-1 + T(3))))$
- 3135** := $(T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(T(3))) \times T(5)$
:= $T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(T(3)))$
- 3136** := $T(T(3 + 1)) + T(T(T(3) + 6))$
:= $T(T(6 + T(3))) + T(T(1 + 3))$
- 3139** := $-T(T(3)) + T(1 + T(3 + 9))$
:= $T(T(9 + 3) + 1) - T(T(3))$
- 3145** := $T(T(3 + 1)) \times T(T(4)) + T(T(5))$
:= $T(T(5)) + T(T(4))^{-1+3}$
- 3163** := $3 + T(1 + T(6 + T(3)))$
:= $T(T(T(3) + 6)) + 1 + 3$
- 3164** := $-T(T(T(3) + 1)) + T(T(6) \times 4)$
:= $T(4 \times T(6)) - T(T(1 + T(3)))$
- 3165** := $(-T(T(3)) + 1 + T(T(6))) \times T(5)$
:= $T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + 1 - T(T(3)))$
- 3166** := $T(3) + T(1 + T(6 + 6))$
:= $T(T(6 + 6) + 1) + T(3)$
- 3174** := $T(3) \times (1 + T(T(7) + 4))$
:= $(T(4 + T(7)) + 1) \times T(3)$
- 3185** := $(T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-1 + 8))) \times 5$
:= $5 \times (T(T(8 - 1)) + T(T(T(3))))$
- 3189** := $3 \times (T(-1 + 8) + T(T(9)))$
- 3213** := $T(T(3) \times T(2) - 1) \times T(T(3))$
:= $T(T(3)) \times T(-1 + T(2) \times T(3))$
- 3224** := $T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)$
:= $-T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3)$
- 3225** := $T(T(T(3) + T(T(2))) + 2) - T(5)$
:= $(-T(5) + T(2 + T(2 \times T(3))))$
- 3227** := $-T(T(3)) + 2^{T(2)} \times T(T(7))$
:= $T(T(7)) \times 2^{T(2)} - T(T(3))$
- 3228** := $-T(3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(2)) + 8)$
:= $(T(8) + T(T(T(2))))^2 - T(T(3))$
- 3232** := $T(T(T(3))) - 2 + T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2))$
:= $(-2 + T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))$
- 3234** := $-T(3) + T(2 + T(3 \times 4))$
:= $T(T(4 \times 3) + 2) - (T(3))$
- 3235** := $T(T(T(T(3)))/T(2) + 3) - 5$
:= $5 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(2^{T(3)})$
- 3237** := $3 + 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \times 7$
:= $7 \times T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 3$
- 3252** := $T(T(T(3)) - T(2)) + T(T(T(5) - T(2)))$
:= $T(T(2) + T(5)) + T(T(2 \times T(3)))$
- 3255** := $-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(-T(2) + T(5)) + 5)$
:= $T(T(5) + T(5))/T(2) \times T(T(3))$
- 3258** := $T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) \times T(8))$
:= $(T(8) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3)$
- 3264** := $(T(T(3)) + T(2)) \times T(6 + T(4))$
:= $T(46) \times T(2) + T(T(3))$

$$\begin{aligned} 3272 &:= (T(3) + 2) \times (T(T(7)) + T(2)) \\ &:= (T(2) + T(T(7))) \times 2^3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3276 &:= T(3)^2 \times T(7 + 6) \\ &:= T(6 + 7) \times T(2^3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3277 &:= T(T(T(3) \times 2)) + 7 \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times 7 + T(T(2 \times T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3278 &:= T(3) + (T(2) + T(T(7))) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times (T(T(7)) + T(2)) + T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3279 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 2 \times 7 + T(9) \\ &:= T(9) + 7 \times 2 \times T(T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3283 &:= -T((T(T(3)) + T(T(T(2)))) + \\ &\quad + T(T(-8 + T(T(3)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(T(3)) - 8)) - T(2 \times T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3285 &:= (-3^2 + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times T(T(8)) - T(T(2) \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3288 &:= -T(3) + T(2 \times T(8)) + T(T(8)) \\ &:= (T(8) + 8^{T(2)}) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3297 &:= (T(T(T(3))) \times 2 + 9) \times 7 \\ &:= (T(7 + 9) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3298 &:= -T(T(3)) - 2 + T(T(9) + T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8) + T(9)) - 23 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3312 &:= T(T(3 + 3)) + T(T(12)) \\ &:= T(21) + T(T(T(3) + T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3313 &:= T(T(T(3) + T(3))) + 1 + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) + 1 + T(T(T(3) + T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3315 &:= -T(3) + T(3^{-1+5}) \\ &:= T(5) \times (-T(1 + 3) + T(T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3321 &:= T((3 \times 3)^2) \times 1 \\ &:= T((1 + 2)^3 \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3324 &:= 3 + T(3 + T(2 + T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(4) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(3))) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3327 &:= T(3) + T(3 \times 27) \\ &:= T(T(7) \times T(2) - 3) + T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3336 &:= 3 \times T(T(3 \times 3)) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + 3 \times T(T(3 \times 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3339 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3) + T(3 + 9)) \\ &:= (T(T(9)) + T(T(3) + T(3))) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3342 &:= T(T(3)) + T(3 + T(T(4) + 2)) \\ &:= T(T(2)) \times (-4 + T(33)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3345 &:= 3 \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(5)) \\ &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(3)) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3348 &:= 3 \times (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\ &:= T(8) \times (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3355 &:= (T(T(3) \times T(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times (5 + T(T(3) \times T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3357 &:= -3 + T(3 \times 5) \times T(7) \\ &:= T(7) \times T(5 \times 3) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$3358 := T(T(8)) \times 5 + T(T(T(3))/3)$$

$$3358 := T(T(T(3))/3) + 5 \times T(T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3363 &:= T(33) \times 6 - 3 \\ &:= -3 + 6 \times T(33) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3366 &:= T(3^3 + 6) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(6 + 3^3) \end{aligned}$$

- 3372** := $T(3) \times T(T(T(T(3))))/7 + T(T(2))$
:= $T(-2 + 7)^3 - 3$
- 3384** := $3 \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) - T(4)$
:= $T(T(T(4)) - 8) \times (-3 + T(3))$
- 3385** := $(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 5$
:= $5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))$
- 3388** := $T(T(T(3)))/3 \times (8 + T(8))$
:= $(8 + T(8)) \times T(T(T(3)))/3$
- 3391** := $T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3 + 9)) + 1$
:= $T(1 + T(9 + 3)) + T(T(T(3)))$
- 3396** := $T(3^3) \times 9 - 6$
:= $-6 + 9 \times T(3^3)$
- 3397** := $-T(3) + T(T(3) \times 9 + T(7))$
:= $T(79 + 3) - T(3)$
- 3398** := $T(T(T(3)))/3 + (T(T(9)) + T(8))$
:= $T(T(8) + T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))/3$
- 3399** := $-3 + T(3 \times 9) \times 9$
:= $9 \times T(9 \times 3) - 3$
- 3403** := $T(T(3) + T(T(4)) + T(T(03)))$
:= $T(T(3) + T(T(04)) + T(T(3)))$
- 3405** := $(T(T(T(3))) - 4) \times T(05)$
:= $T(5) \times (-04 + T(T(T(3))))$
- 3421** := $T(3 + T(T(4))) \times 2 - 1$
:= $-1 + 2 \times T(T(T(4)) + 3)$
- 3422** := $T(T(3) \times T(4) - 2) \times 2$
:= $2 \times T(-2 + T(4) \times T(3))$
- 3423** := $(3 \times T(T(4)) - 2) \times T(T(3))$
:= $T(T(3)) \times (-2 + T(T(4)) \times 3)$
- 3424** := $T(T(3)) + T(4 + T(2 + T(4)))$
:= $T(T(T(4))) + T(2 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))$
- 3431** := $T(T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3 + 1)))$
:= $T(T(T(1 + 3))) + T(T(T(4)) + (T(3)))$
- 3432** := $(T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3) \times 2$
:= $2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \times T(3)$
- 3434** := $3 + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(3) + T(T(4)))$
:= $T(T(T(4))) + 3 + T(T(T(4)) + T(3))$
- 3435** := $T(3^4) - T(3) + T(T(5))$
:= $T(5)^3 + T(4) \times T(3)$
- 3436** := $T(-T(3) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(6)))$
:= $T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)) - T(3))$
- 3437** := $T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3 - T(7)$
:= $-T(7) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)) \times 3$
- 3438** := $T(T(T(3))) \times 4 \times 3 + T(T(8))$
:= $8^3 + T(T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))$
- 3442** := $(T(3 + T(T(4))) + T(4)) \times 2$
:= $2 \times (T(4) + T(T(T(4)) + 3))$
- 3444** := $T(-3 + 44) \times 4$
:= $4 \times T(44 - 3)$
- 3462** := $3 \times T(T(4)) \times T(6) - T(2)$
:= $T(2) \times T(6) \times T(T(4)) - 3$
- 3465** := $T(T(3)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5)$
:= $T(5) \times T(6 \times 4 - 3)$
- 3471** := $T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4) \times (7 + 1))$

$$:= T((1 + 7) \times T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3472} := (3 + 4) \times T(T(7) + T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2) + T(7)) \times (4 + 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3474} := T(3^4) + T(7 + T(4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) - 4 \times 3$$

$$\mathbf{3475} := -T(3) + T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(T(7) + T(T(4))) - T(3)$$

$$\mathbf{3478} := T(T(T(3) + 4) + T(7)) - 8$$

$$:= -8 + T(T(7) + T(4 + T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3483} := -T(T(3) - 4) + T(83)$$

$$:= -3 + T(8 \times T(4) + 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3484} := (-3 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times (-T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 3$$

$$\mathbf{3485} := (T(T(3)) + T(4) + T(T(8))) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4) + T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3486} := T(-T(T(3) - 4) + 86)$$

$$:= T(6 + 8 \times T(4) - 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3487} := T(T(-T(3) + T(4) + 8)) + T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) + T(T((8 - 4) \times 3))$$

$$\mathbf{3489} := -T(T(3)) + T(4 + 8) \times T(9)$$

$$:= T(9) \times T(8 + 4) - T(T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3492} := T(3^4) + T(9 \times 2)$$

$$:= T(2) \times (9 + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(3))))$$

$$\mathbf{3495} := T(3 \times 4) \times T(9) - T(5)$$

$$:= -T(5) + T(9) \times T(4 \times 3)$$

$$\mathbf{3497} := T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(9) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) - T(9) + T(4 \times T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3498} := T(T(T(3)) - T(4)) \times (T(9) + 8)$$

$$:= (8 + T(9)) \times T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3515} := T(T(3 + 5) + 1) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times T(1 + T(5 + 3))$$

$$\mathbf{3518} := 3 + 5 \times T(1 + T(8))$$

$$:= T(T(8) + 1) \times 5 + 3$$

$$\mathbf{3522} := T(T(-3 + T(5))) + (T(T(T(2))))^2$$

$$:= T(T(T(2)))^2 + T(T(T(5) - 3))$$

$$\mathbf{3525} := (T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \times 25$$

$$:= 5^2 \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3528} := (T(3) + T(5))^2 \times 8$$

$$:= T(82) + 5^3$$

$$\mathbf{3534} := (-T(3) + T(T(5))) \times (T(T(3)) + T(4))$$

$$:= (T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(5)) - T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3542} := (T(T(3) + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(5) + T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3543} := T(T(T(3))) \times T(5) + T(4 \times 3)$$

$$:= T(3 \times 4) + T(5) \times T(T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3546} := (T(T(3)) + T(5) \times (4 + T(T(6))))$$

$$:= (T(T(6)) + 4) \times T(5) + T(T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3549} := T(T(3)) \times (T(T(5)) + 49)$$

$$:= (T(9) + 4 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$\mathbf{3552} := T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5) + T(5 + T(T(2))))$$

$$:= T(T(T(2)) + 5 \times T(5)) + T(T(T(3)))$$

$$\mathbf{3555} := T(-T(3 + 5) + T(T(5))) - T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(5)) - 3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3557 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(5) + T(T(5)) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(T(5)) + T(5) \times T(T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (T(T(7)) - T(2)) \times (6 + 3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3558 &:= 3 - T(5) + T(T(T(5))) - T(8) \\ &:= T(-T(8) + T(T(5))) - T(5) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3634 &:= T(4^3 + T(6)) - T(T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(6) + T(3) + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3564 &:= -T(3) + T((T(5) + 6) \times 4) \\ &:= T(4 \times T(6)) - T(T(5 - 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3642 &:= T(T(T(T(T(3))))/T(6)) + T(T(T(4)) - 2) \\ &:= T(-2 + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3565 &:= T(T(-3 + T(5)) + 6) - 5 \\ &:= -5 + T(6 \times T(5) - T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3645 &:= -3^6 \times (T(4) - T(5)) \\ &:= 5 \times T(-4 + 6)^{T(3)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3567 &:= -3 + T(56 + T(7)) \\ &:= (7 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3647 &:= 3 \times T(-6 + T(T(4))) - T(7) \\ &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4)) - 6) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3568 &:= (T(T(3)) - 5) \times (T(T(6)) - 8) \\ &:= (8 - T(T(6))) \times (5 - T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3648 &:= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(T(4))) \times 8 \\ &:= T(84) + T(6 + T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3582 &:= T(3) + T(T(T(5))) - T(8) + T(T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(T(8)) \times 5 + T(T(T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3649 &:= -T(3) + T(-6 + T(4 + 9)) \\ &:= T(T(9 + 4) - 6) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3584 &:= -T(T(3)) + 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 5 - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3652 &:= -3 + T(-6 + T(T(5) - 2)) \\ &:= T(T(-2 + T(5)) - 6) - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3585 &:= (T(T(3) + T(5)) + 8) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times (8 + T(T(5) + T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3654 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(6) \times (T(T(5)) + T(T(4))) \\ &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) \times T(6) - T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3587 &:= (3 + (T(T(5)) + 8) \times T(7)) \\ &:= T(7) \times (8 + T(T(5))) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3655 &:= T(3 \times 6 \times 5 - 5) \\ &:= T(-5 + 5 \times 6 \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3591 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(T(5))) - T(9 - 1) \\ &:= T(-T(-1 + 9) + T(T(5))) + T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3657 &:= 3 + (-6 + T(5)) \times T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(5) - 6) + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3612 &:= (T(T(T(3)) + T(6))) \times (1 + T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (1 + T(6 \times 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3658 &:= 3 + T(-6 + T(5 + 8)) \\ &:= T(85) + 6 - 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3624 &:= (3 + T(T(6) \times 2)) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times (T(2 \times T(6)) + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3672 &:= 3 \times T(T(6) + T(7)) - T(2) \\ &:= (2 + T(T(7))) \times (6 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$3627 := (3 + 6) \times (-T(2) + T(T(7)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3675 &:= 3 \times T(6 + T(7) + T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5) + T(7) + 6) \times 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3676} & := T(T(3)) + T(-6 + T(7 + 6)) \\
 & := T(6) + T(T(7 + 6) - T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3688} & := 3 - T(T(6)) + T(88) \\
 & := ((T(88) - T(T(6)))) + 3 \\
 \mathbf{3696} & := T(T(3)) \times (T(6) + T(T(9)))/6 \\
 & := T(T(6)) \times 96/T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3699} & := T(T(3) + T(6)) + T(9 \times 9) \\
 & := T(9 \times 9) + T(T(6) + T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3724} & := -3 + T(T(7)) + T(T(2)^4) \\
 & := T(T(T(4))) + T(2)^7 - 3 \\
 \mathbf{3725} & := -T(T(T(3)) + T(7)) + T(-T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(5)) \\
 & := T(T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(7) + T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3727} & := T(T(3 + 7)) + T(2)^7 \\
 & := T(T(7)) + T(27 \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3729} & := T(T(3)) + (T(T(7)) + T(T(2))) \times 9 \\
 & := 9 \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(7))) + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3732} & := T(3) \times (T(T(7)) + T(3)^{T(2)}) \\
 & := (T(T(2))^3 + T(T(7))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3735} & := -T(3) + T(T(7 + T(3))) - 5 \\
 & := T(T(T(5)) - T(3) - T(7)) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3738} & := T(3 \times T(7)) + T(T(3)) \times 8 \\
 & := 8 \times T(T(3)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3739} & := 3 + T(73) + T(T(9)) \\
 & := T(T(9)) + 3 + T(73) \\
 \mathbf{3741} & := T(T(T(3)) + T(7 + 4) - 1) \\
 & := T(T(T(1 \times 4)) + T(7) + 3) \\
 \mathbf{3745} & := T(3 \times T(7)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(5)) \\
 & := T(T(5)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3746} & := T(3 \times T(7)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(6)) \\
 & := T(T(6)) - T(T(4)) + T(T(7) \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3751} & := (3 + T(7)) \times (T(T(5)) + 1) \\
 & := (1 + T(T(5))) \times (T(7) + 3) \\
 \mathbf{3759} & := -T(T(3)) + T(7) \times T(5) \times 9 \\
 & := (T(T(9))/5 - T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3762} & := (-T(3) + T(7)) \times T(T(6) - T(2)) \\
 & := T(T(2) \times 6) \times (T(7) - T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3774} & := -T(3) - (T(7) - T(T(7))) \times T(4) \\
 & := T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(T(7))) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3775} & := T(T(T(3) + 7)) - T(T(7)) - 5 \\
 & := -5 + T(T(7) + 7) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3792} & := (3 - T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 & := (T(2) + T(T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3795} & := 3 \times T(7) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := (T(5) + T(9) \times T(7)) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{3797} & := T(T(T(3))) + T(79) + T(T(7)) \\
 & := T(79) + T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3798} & := T(3 + T(7)) \times 9 - T(T(8)) \\
 & := -T(T(8)) + 9 \times T((T(7) + 3)) \\
 \mathbf{3816} & := T(3) + T(T(8) - 1) \times 6 \\
 & := (6 + T(-1 + T(8))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3822} & := T(T(T(3)) + T(8 + T(2))) - T(T(2)) \\
 & := -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3824} & := T(T(T(3)) + T(8 + T(2))) - 4 \\
 & := -4 + T(T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := T(2) \times T(8) \times T(8) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3825} & := -3 + T(82 + 5) \\
 & := T(5 \times (2 + 8)) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{3828} & := T(-3 + 82 + 8) \\
 & := T(8/2 + 83) \\
 \mathbf{3834} & := T(3) + T(83 + 4) \\
 & := T(-4 + T(T(3)) - 8) + T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3835} & := T(T(T(3)) - 8) - T(T(3)) + 5 \\
 & := -T(T(5)) - T(T(3)) + T(T(-8 + T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3837} & := T(T(T(3))) + T(8) + T(3 \times T(7)) \\
 & := T(T(7) \times 3) + T(8) + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3843} & := T(3) \times T(T(8)) - T(-4 + T(T(3))) \\
 & := T(T(3)) + 4 \times T(T(8) + T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3846} & := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) - 4) \times 6 \\
 & := (-T(6) - 4 + T(T(8))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3849} & := T(T(3)) + T(T(8 + 4) + 9) \\
 & := T(9 + T(4 + 8)) + T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3855} & := (T(T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times 5 \\
 & := 5 \times (T(5) + T(8) \times T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3856} & := -T(T(T(3))) - 8 + T(T(5) \times 6) \\
 & := T(6 \times T(5)) - 8 - T(T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3858} & := T(3) \times (-8 - T(5) + T(T(8))) \\
 & := (T(T(8)) - T(5) - 8) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3864} & := T(T(T(3)) + T(8)) + T(T(T(6) - T(4))) \\
 & := -(T(T(4)) - T(T(6)) - 8) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3865} & := (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 6 - 5 \\
 & := -5 + (-T(6) + T(T(8))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3882} & := 3 \times (T(8) \times T(8) - 2) \\
 \mathbf{3884} & := 3 \times T(8) \times T(8) - 4 \\
 & := -4 + T(8) \times T(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{3885} & := (T(38) + T(8)) \times 5 \\
 & := 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8))/T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3886} & := T(-3 + 88) + T(T(6)) \\
 & := T(T(6)) + T(88 - 3) \\
 \mathbf{3888} & := 3 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \\
 & := T(8) \times T(8) \times T(8 - T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3906} & := T(T(3)) \times (-T(9) + T(T(06))) \\
 & := (T(T(6)) - T(09)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{3909} & := -T(T(T(3))) + T(90) + T(9) \\
 & := T(90) + T(9) - T(T(T(3))) \\
 \mathbf{3916} & := T(3 + 91 - 6) \\
 & := T(61 + 9 \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3922} & := T(3) + T(T(9) \times 2 - 2) \\
 & := T(-2 + 2 \times T(9)) + T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3927} & := T(3 \times (9 + 2)) \times 7 \\
 & := 7 \times T((2 + 9) \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3942} & := T(3) \times (-9 + T(T(4 \times 2))) \\
 & := (T(T(2 \times 4)) - 9) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3944} & := (T(3) + T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\
 & := 4 \times (-T(T(4)) + T(T(9))) - T(3) \\
 \mathbf{3948} & := T(3) \times (T(9 \times 4) - 8) \\
 & := T(84) + T(9 \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{3963} & := T(T(3)) \times 9 \times T(6) - T(3) \\
 & := T(T(3)) \times T(6) \times 9 - T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3964 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(6)) + T(T(9)) + 3 \\
 3966 &:= -3 + 9 \times T(6) \times T(6) \\
 &:= T(6) \times T(6) \times 9 - 3 \\
 3968 &:= T((T(T(T(3)))) - T(9))/6 \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times T((T(T(6)) - T(9))/T(3)) \\
 3969 &:= T(-3 + 9) \times T(6) \times 9 \\
 &:= 9 \times T(6) \times T(9 - 3) \\
 3975 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(-9 + T(7)) - T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(T(7) - 9) \times T(T(3)) \\
 3978 &:= (T(3) + T(9)) \times 78 \\
 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(-7 + 9)) \times T(3) \\
 3984 &:= T(-3 + T(9)) + T(T(8 + 4)) \\
 &:= T(T(4 + 8)) + T(T(9) - 3) \\
 3988 &:= (-3 + 9) \times T(T(8)) - 8 \\
 &:= -8 + T(T(8)) \times (9 - 3) \\
 3996 &:= T(3 \times 9 + 9) \times 6 \\
 &:= 6 \times T(9 + 9 \times 3) \\
 3997 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(9 + 9) + T(T(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(7)) + T(9 + 9) \times T(T(3)) \\
 4075 &:= T(4) \times T(T(07)) + T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(T(7)) \times T(04) \\
 4092 &:= T(T(4) \times 09) - T(2) \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(9 \times T(04)) \\
 4099 &:= 4 + T(T(09) + T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9) + T(9)) + 04 \\
 4125 &:= T(T(4)) \times (-1 + T(T(2))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(2)) - 1) \times T(T(4)) \\
 4131 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(13 \times 1)) \\
 &:= T(T(13)) - T(T(1 \times 4)) \\
 4134 &:= (4 - 1) \times T(-3 + T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 3) \times (-1 + 4) \\
 4136 &:= 4 \times (-1 + T(T(3 + 6))) \\
 &:= (T(T(6 + 3)) - 1) \times 4 \\
 4164 &:= (T(T(T(4) - 1)) + 6) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (6 + T(T(-1 + T(4)))) \\
 4175 &:= -T(4) - 1 + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) \\
 &:= T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) - 1 - T(4) \\
 4176 &:= -T(4) + T(T(-1 - 7 + T(6))) \\
 &:= T(T(6 + 7)) - T(1 \times 4) \\
 4178 &:= T(T(-4 + 17)) - 8 \\
 &:= -8 + T(T(T(7) - T(1 + 4))) \\
 4182 &:= -4 + T(T(-1 + 8 + T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 8 - 1)) - 4 \\
 4183 &:= T(T(4 + 1 + 8)) - 3 \\
 &:= -3 + T(T(8 + 1 + 4)) \\
 4185 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(1 + T(8))) \times 5 \\
 &:= T(T(5 + 8)) - 1^4 \\
 4186 &:= T(4 + 1 + 86) \\
 &:= T(6 + 81 + 4) \\
 4215 &:= T(T(T(4) + T(2)) - 1) + T(T(5)) \\
 &:= T(T(5)) + T(-1 + T(T(2) + T(4))) \\
 4218 &:= (4 + 2) \times T(1 + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(8) + 1) \times (2 + 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4222} := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(2 + T(T(2)))$$

$$:= T(2^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4223} := -T(T(4)) + T(T(2 + T(T(T(2)))))/3$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(3)) + 2)/T(2)) - T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4225} := (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(25)$$

$$:= T(5^2) \times (T(2) + T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4228} := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(T(2)) + T(8)$$

$$:= T(8) + T(T(2)) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4229} := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) - 2 + T(9)$$

$$:= T(92) + T(T(2)) - T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4232} := T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2))))/3 - T(2)$$

$$:= -T(2) + T(T(T(3)))/T(2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4235} := T(T(4))^2 \times T(T(3))/T(5)$$

$$:= T(T(5) + T(3))/T(2) \times T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4236} := T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3) + 6))$$

$$:= T(T(6 + T(3))) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4238} := T(T(4)) - T(2) + T(T(T(T(3)) - 8))$$

$$:= T(T(-8 + T(T(3)))) - T(2) + T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4239} := (T(T(4) \times T(2)) + T(3)) \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times (T(3) + T(T(2) \times T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4241} := T(T(4)) + T(T(-2 + T(4 + 1)))$$

$$:= T(T(1 \times 4)) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4243} := T(T(4)) + 2 + T(T(T(4) + 3))$$

$$:= T(T(3 + T(4))) + 2 + T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4246} := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(4) \times 6$$

$$:= 6 \times T(4) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4252} := T(T(T(4) + T(2))) + T(5 + T(T(2)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(2)) + 5) + T(T(T(2) + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4257} := -T(4 + 2) + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))$$

$$:= T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) - T(2 + 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4258} := T(4) + (-2 + T(T(5))) \times T(8)$$

$$:= T(8) \times (T(T(5)) - 2) + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4263} := (-T(T(4) - T(2)) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2) + 4))$$

$$\mathbf{4265} := (-T(T(4)) + T(2 + 6) \times T(T(5)))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times 6^2 - T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4267} := 4 + T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) - T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7 + 6)) + T(2)^4$$

$$\mathbf{4269} := T(4 \times (2 + T(6))) - 9$$

$$:= -9 + T((T(6) + 2) \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4282} := T(T(4)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4289} := -4 + (T(2) \times T(8 + T(9)))$$

$$:= T(T(9) + 8) \times T(2) - 4$$

$$\mathbf{4323} := (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(2))) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4324} := 4 \times T(T(3)^2 + T(4))$$

$$:= 4 \times T(T(2^3) + T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4326} := (-T(4) + T(3)^{T(2)}) \times T(6)$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(T(2) \times 3 \times T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4327} := 4^{T(3)} + T(T(2) \times 7)$$

$$:= T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(3) + T(T(4)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4335 &:= (T(T(4)) + 3 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) & &:= 5 \times (-T(T(8)) + 3 + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) + 3 + T(T(4))) \\
 4345 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(3)) \times 4 - 5) \\
 &:= (T(5) + 4^3) \times T(T(4)) \\
 4348 &:= 4 \times (T(3) + T(T(4) + T(8))) \\
 &:= (T(T(8) + T(4)) + T(3)) \times 4 \\
 4352 &:= 2^5 \times T(T(3) + T(4)) \\
 &:= -4 + T(T(3) + 5)^2 \\
 4355 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(3)) \times T(5 + T(5)) \\
 &:= T(5 + T(5)) \times T(T(3)) - T(T(4)) \\
 4356 &:= T(-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times T(5 + 6) \\
 &:= T(6 + 5)^{T(3)-4} \\
 4362 &:= (T(T(4) + T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(4))) \\
 4365 &:= (T(4) \times T(3) + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(6)) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 4367 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times 3 - T(-6 + T(7)) \\
 &:= -T(T(7) - 6) + 3 \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 4368 &:= T(T(4) + 3) \times 6 \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times 6 \times T(3 + T(4)) \\
 4371 &:= T(T(T(4)) + 37 + 1) \\
 &:= T(-1 + T(7) \times 3 + T(4)) \\
 4378 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(7)) - 8) \\
 &:= (-8 + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(3)) - T(4)) \\
 4379 &:= (T(4) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (T(7) - 9) \\
 &:= (-9 + T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) \\
 4385 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + 3 - T(T(8))) \times 5 \\
 & & &:= 5 \times (-T(T(8)) + 3 + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 4392 &:= T(T(T(2))) + T(9 + T(T(3)) \times 4) \\
 &:= T(4 \times T(T(3)) + 9) + T(T(T(2))) \\
 4395 &:= -T(T(4)) \times 3 + T(95) \\
 &:= -5 \times T(9) + 3 \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 4396 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(T(9) - T(6)) \\
 &:= T(6) + T(93) + 4 \\
 4398 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9))) - T(T(8)) \\
 &:= -T(T(8)) + (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 4 \\
 4412 &:= -T(4) + T(T(T(4) + 1)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(1 + T(4))) - T(4) \\
 4422 &:= T(T(4 + 4 + T(2))) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(2) + 4 + 4)) \\
 4425 &:= T(4 + T(T(4))) / T(T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4) + T(4)) \\
 4427 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(2)^4 \times T(T(4)) \\
 4432 &:= T(4) + T(T(-T(4) + T(T(3)))) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(3)) - T(4))) + T(4) \\
 4437 &:= T(T(4) \times T(4) - T(3)) - T(7) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(-T(3) + T(4) \times T(4)) \\
 4442 &:= 4^4 + T(T(T(4) + T(2))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2) + T(4))) + 4^4 \\
 4443 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) - 4 \times 3 \\
 &:= 3 \times (T(T(T(4))) - 4 - T(T(4))) \\
 4445 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)) - T(T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4446 &:= T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \times 6 \\
 &:= 6 \times T(T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(4)) \\
 4455 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(-4 + T(5)) + T(5)) \\
 &:= (T(5)/5)^4 \times T(T(4)) \\
 4462 &:= T(T(4) \times T(4) - 6) - T(2) \\
 &:= -T(2) + T(T(6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\
 4463 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4)) + (T(6))) - 3 \\
 &:= -3 + T(T(6) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4465 &:= T(T(T(4) + 4) - 6 - 5) \\
 &:= T((T(5) + 6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\
 4466 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(4) + 66) \\
 &:= T(T(6) + T(6 + 4)) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4469 &:= 4 + T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9) - 6 + T(T(4))) + 4 \\
 4473 &:= (4 \times T(T(4)) - 7) \times T(T(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-7 + 4 \times T(T(4))) \\
 4482 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times T(2) \\
 &:= T(2) \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(4)) \\
 4484 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(48)) \times 4 \\
 &:= (T(48) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\
 4485 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) + T(T(8))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(-4 + T(4)))) \\
 4488 &:= (-4 + T(T(4))) \times 88 \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4) + 4)) \\
 4495 &:= -T(4) - T(T(4)) + T(95) \\
 &:= -5 + (T(9) \times T(4)) \times T(4) \\
 4497 &:= -4^4 + T(97) \\
 &:= T(7) + T(94) + 4 \\
 4526 &:= -T(T(4) + T(5)) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(6)) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5) + T(4)) \\
 4532 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(5 + T(3)))) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3) + 5)) + T(T(4))) \\
 4536 &:= (T(4 \times 5) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= T(6) \times (T(3) + T(5 \times 4)) \\
 4543 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(5)) - 43) \\
 &:= T((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4)))/T(5)) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4545 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(5) + T(T(4))) - T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(T(4) \times T(5) - T(T(4))) \\
 4555 &:= T(-T(4) - T(5) + T(T(5))) - 5 \\
 &:= -5 + T(5 \times (T(5) + 4)) \\
 4556 &:= -4 + T(5 + T(5) \times 6) \\
 &:= T(6 \times T(5) + 5) - 4 \\
 4575 &:= T(4 + T(-T(5) + T(7))) + T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(7 \times T(5) - T(4)) \\
 4584 &:= (4 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(5)) \times 4) \\
 4585 &:= T(T(4) + T(T(5)) - T(8)) + T(T(5)) \\
 &:= T(T(5)) + T(-T(8) + T(T(5)) + T(4)) \\
 4589 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(5) + T(T(8)) \times 9 \\
 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(5)) - T(T(T(4))) \\
 4595 &:= (4 - T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(9)) - T(T(5)) + 4) \\
 4596 &:= -T(T(4)) - 5 + T(96)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (-6 + T(T(9)) + T(T(5))) \times 4$$

$$\mathbf{4602} := (T(T(T(4))) - 6) \times T(02)$$

$$:= T(2) \times (-06 + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$\mathbf{4615} := (4 \times T(T(6)) - 1) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times (-1 + T(T(6)) \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4616} := -4 + T(T(6)) \times (-1 + T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) \times (-1 + T(6)) - 4$$

$$\mathbf{4632} := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(3)) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(3) + T(T(6)) \times T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4634} := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times 3 - 4$$

$$:= -4 + 3 \times (6 + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$\mathbf{4635} := (T(T(4)) \times 6 - T(T(3))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) + 3 \times T(T(6 + 4))$$

$$\mathbf{4638} := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times T(-T(3) + 8)$$

$$:= T(8 - T(3)) \times (6 + T(T(T(4))))$$

$$\mathbf{4639} := T(T(T(4))) - 6 + 3 \times T(T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9)) \times 3 - 6 + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4641} := (-T(4) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(4 - 1))$$

$$:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times (T(T(6)) - T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4642} := T(T(T(4))) + T(6) + T(T(T(4) + 2))$$

$$:= T(T(2 + T(4))) + T(6) + T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4644} := (T(T(T(4))) + 6) \times 4 - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + 6) - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4646} := -T(4) + T((6 + T(4)) \times 6)$$

$$:= T((6 + T(4)) \times 6) - T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4648} := T(4 \times 6 \times 4) - 8$$

$$:= -8 + T(4 \times 6 \times 4)$$

$$\mathbf{4662} := (T(4) \times T(T(6)) + T(6)) \times 2$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(6 \times (6 + T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4675} := T(T(4)) \times (-6 + T(T(7) - T(5)))$$

$$:= (T(-T(5) + T(7)) - 6) \times T(T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4678} := T(4) + 6 + 7 \times T(T(8))$$

$$:= T(T(8)) \times 7 + 6 + T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{4682} := (-T(4) + T(68)) \times 2$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) + T(T(6) + T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4683} := (T(T(4)) + T(6) \times 8) \times T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times (8 \times T(6) + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4687} := (4 + T(6) + T(T(8))) \times 7$$

$$:= 7 \times T(T(8)) + T(6) + 4$$

$$\mathbf{4692} := (T(T(T(4))) - T(6) + T(9)) \times T(2)$$

$$:= 2 \times T(T(-9 + T(6)) - T(4))$$

$$\mathbf{4694} := -T(T(T(4))) + 6 \times T(T(9)) + 4$$

$$:= (4 + T(T(9))) \times 6 - T(T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4696} := T(T(T(4)) - 6 + T(9)) + T(T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(T(9) - 6 + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4697} := (-T(T(T(4))) + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times 7$$

$$:= 7 \times (T(T(9) + T(6)) - T(T(T(4))))$$

$$\mathbf{4698} := -T(-4 + T(6)) + T(98)$$

$$:= T(T(8)) \times 9 - 6^4$$

$$\mathbf{4704} := 4 \times T(-7 + T(T(04)))$$

$$:= 4 \times T(-07 + T(T(4)))$$

$$\mathbf{4717} := T(T(4)) + 7 \times T(T(1 + 7))$$

$$:= 7 \times T(T(1 + 7)) + T(T(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4722 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + T(7) + T(T(2))) \times T(2) \\ &:= T(2) \times (T(T(2)) + T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= T(T(3) \times T(5) + T(7))/4$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4725 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7) - T(2))) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5)^2 \times T(T(7 - 4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4759 &:= -T(4) - T(T(7)) + 5 \times T(T(9)) \\ &:= T(T(9)) \times 5 - T(T(7)) - T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4726 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) + T(T(2 + 6)) \\ &:= T(6^2) + T(T(7)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4762 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(7)) \times 6) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (6 \times T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4728 &:= T(4) \times T(T(7)) + 2 + T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) + 2 + T(T(7)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4763 &:= T(4) + T(T(7 + 6) + T(3)) \\ &:= T(T(3) + T(6 + 7)) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4729 &:= 4 + T(7 \times 2) \times T(9) \\ &:= T(9) \times T(2 \times 7) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4779 &:= T(-T(4) + T(7)) \times T(7) - 9 \\ &:= -9 + T(7) \times T(T(7) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4732 &:= (T(T(T(4)) + 7 \times T(3))) - T(T(T(2))) \\ &:= -T(T(T(2))) + T(T(3) \times 7 + T(T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4782 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(7)) \times 8 - T(T(2)) \\ &:= -T(2) + 87 \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4733 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(3 \times T(3)) \\ &:= T(3 \times T(3)) \times T(7) - T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4784 &:= -4 + T(7) \times T(8 + T(4)) \\ &:= (T(T(4) + 8) \times T(7)) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4738 &:= T(T(4)) + 7 \times (3 + T(T(8))) \\ &:= (T(T(8)) + 3) \times 7 + T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4785 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(-7 + T(8))/5 \\ &:= 5 \times T(87)/4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4743 &:= (T(T(4) + 7)) \times (T(4) + T(T(3))) \\ &:= (T(T(3)) + T(4)) \times T(7 + T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4788 &:= (T(T(4)) + 78) \times T(8) \\ &:= (-8 + T(8)) \times T(T(7) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4744 &:= (T(4) + T(-7 + T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\ &:= (T(4) + T(T(T(4)) - 7)) \times 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4792 &:= 4 + T(7) \times T(9 \times 2) \\ &:= T(2 \times 9) \times T(7) + 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4746 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \times T(6) \\ &:= T(6) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(7) - T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4795 &:= T(T(T(4))) + 7 \times T(T(9) - T(5)) \\ &:= (T(-T(5) + T(9)) \times 7 + T(T(T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4749 &:= -4 + T(7 + T(4) \times 9) \\ &:= T(9 \times T(4) + 7) - 4 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4796 &:= -T(T(4)) + T(T(T(-7 + 9))) \times T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(9 - 7))) - T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4752 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(7))) \times (T(5) - T(2)) \\ &:= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4832 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(8) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) - T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$4753 := T(T(T(4) + T(7 - 5)) + T(3))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4833 &:= (-T(4) - 8 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)) - 8 - T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4837 &:= (4 + T(T(8)) + T(T(3))) \times 7 & &:= -T(T(2)) + 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) + 4) \\
 4842 &:= -T(4) + T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4) + T(2))) & &4888 := T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(8)) + T(8) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2) + T(4))) + T(T(8)) - T(4) & &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(T(8 - 4))) \\
 4847 &:= -4 + T(T(8) + T(T(4)) + 7) & &4889 := T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(-8 + T(9)) \\
 &:= T(7 + T(T(4)) + T(8)) - 4 & &:= T(T(9) - 8) + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) \\
 4848 &:= 4 \times (T(8) + T(48)) & &4892 := T(T(4)) \times 89 - T(2) \\
 &:= (T(8) + T(48)) \times 4 & &:= (-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9))) \times 8 - T(T(T(4))) \\
 4851 &:= T(T(T(4)) - 8 + 51) & &4895 := T(T(4)) \times (T(T(8))/9 + T(5)) \\
 &:= T(-1 + T(5) + 84) & &:= T(T(5) \times 9 - T(8)) - T(T(4)) \\
 4852 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8)) + T(T(5 + T(2))) & &4898 := T(T(4)) - 8 + T(98) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2) + 5)) + T(T(8) + T(T(4))) & &:= -8 + T(98) + T(T(4)) \\
 4855 &:= T(T(4)) + 8 \times 5 \times T(T(5)) & &4914 := -T(4 + 9) \times (1 - T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(5)) \times 5 \times 8 + T(T(4)) & &:= (T(T(4)) - 1) \times T(9 + 4) \\
 4859 &:= -T(T(4)) + (T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \times 9 & &4924 := (T(49) + T(T(2))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 9 \times (-T(T(5)) + T(T(8))) - T(T(4)) & &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(2) + T(9))) \times 4 \\
 4863 &:= 4 + 8 + T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)) & &4927 := T(T(4)) + (9 + T(2)) \times T(T(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(6)) + 8 + 4 & &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(2) + 9) + T(T(4)) \\
 4866 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(8) \times T(6)) \times 6 & &4935 := -T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) \\
 &:= 6 \times (T(6) \times T(8) + T(T(4))) & &:= (T(T(5)) + T(T(3))) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \\
 4871 &:= (4 + 8) \times T(T(7)) - 1 & &4937 := -T(T(T(4))) + 9 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -1 + T(T(7)) \times (8 + 4) & &:= T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) + 9 - T(T(T(4))) \\
 4872 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(8) + 7) + T(T(T(2))) & &4942 := (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \times 2 \\
 &:= T(2) \times T(T(7)) \times (8 - 4) & &:= 2 \times (T(T(4)) \times T(9) - 4) \\
 4875 &:= T(4 \times 8 - 7) \times T(5) & &4943 := T(T(T(4))) + T(-9 + T(T(4) + 3)) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(-7 + 8 \times 4) & &:= T(T(3 + T(4)) - 9) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 4882 &:= (-T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 - T(T(2)) & &4945 := T(T(4)) \times 9 \times T(4) - 5 \\
 & & &:= T(T(5)) \times 4 + T(94)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4946 &:= -4 + T(T(T(9 - 4)) - T(6)) \\
 &:= T((T(6) - T(4)) \times 9) - 4 \\
 4962 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(9) + 6) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times (6 + T(9) \times T(T(4))) \\
 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) \\
 &:= -T(56) + 9^4 \\
 4972 &:= (T(4) \times T(T(9)) - T(T(7)))/2 \\
 &:= 2 \times (T(T(7)) + T(9 + T(T(4)))) \\
 4973 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(9) + T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) + T(9) - T(T(T(4))) \\
 4985 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 5 \\
 &:= (T(T(5)) - 8) \times T(9) - T(T(4)) \\
 4987 &:= T(4) + (T(9) + T(T(8))) \times 7 \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(T(8)) + T(9)) + T(4) \\
 4992 &:= (T(T(4)) + 9) \times T(9 + T(2)) \\
 &:= (T(T(2) + 9) \times (9 + T(T(4)))) \\
 4995 &:= (-4 \times 9 + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(9)) - T(9) \times 4 \\
 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) \\
 &:= T(9) + T(99) + 4 \\
 5112 &:= T(5 + T(11)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(11) + 5) \\
 5133 &:= T(T(T(5 - 1)) + 3) \times 3 \\
 &:= 3 \times T(3 + T(T(-1 + 5))) \\
 5147 &:= 5 \times T(T(-1 + T(4))) - T(7) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(T(T(4) - 1)) \times 5 \\
 5159 &:= -T(5) - 1 + 5 \times T(T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9)) \times 5 - 1 - T(5) \\
 5166 &:= (T(5) + T(T(1 \times 6))) \times T(6) \\
 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(6)) \times 1 + T(5)) \\
 5175 &:= 5 \times T(T(1 - 7 + T(5))) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(-7 + 1 + T(5))) \\
 5195 &:= (5 - 1 + T(T(9))) \times 5 \\
 &:= (5 + T(T(9)) - 1) \times 5 \\
 5196 &:= 5 \times T(T((1 \times 9))) + T(6) \\
 &:= T(6) + T(T(9)) \times 1 \times 5 \\
 5226 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(2 + T(6)) \\
 &:= T(T(6) + 2) + T(-T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5))) \\
 5235 &:= (T(T(5)) - 2 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (T(5 + T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(5) \\
 5244 &:= (T(5) + T(T(2))^4) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4)) - 2) - T(T(5))) \\
 5248 &:= (5 + T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(T(8))) \\
 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(4)) \times (T(2) + 5) \\
 5259 &:= -T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) + T(T(5)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(T(2))) - T(T(5)) \\
 5265 &:= 5 \times T(2) \times T(T(6) + 5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(-6 + 2^5) \\
 5272 &:= (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(2)) \\
 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(7)) \times (-2 + T(5)) \\
 5274 &:= (T(5) - 2) \times T(T(7)) - 4 \\
 &:= -4 - T(T(7)) \times (2 - T(5)) \\
 5287 &:= -5 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(8) \times 7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 7 \times T(8) \times T(T(T(2))) - 5$$

$$\mathbf{5292} := T(T(T(5) - T(2))) + T(T(9 + 2))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(9)) - T(2 + T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{5295} := T(5)/T(2) \times T(T(9)) + T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(59) \times T(2) - T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5297} := 5 + T(T(T(2))) \times 9 \times T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) \times 9 \times T(T(T(2))) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{5313} := T(T(5) + T(3) + 1) \times T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) \times T(1 + T(3) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5328} := (5 - 3)^{T(2)} \times T(T(8))$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T(2 \times 3) + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5368} := (5 + T(36)) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(6 \times T(3)) + 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5382} := (T(T(5) + T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3) + T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{5385} := (T(5 + T(T(3))) + 8) \times T(5)$$

$$:= (T(T(5)) + 8 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5395} := T(5 \times 3) \times T(9) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(9) \times T(3 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5415} := T(T(5)) \times T(T(4) - 1) + T(5)$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times T(-1 + T(4)) + T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5432} := (T(T(5) + T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 2$$

$$:= 2 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4))) + (T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{5433} := T(T(5)) + (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))) + T(T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5434} := (T(5) + 4) \times (T(T(T(3))) + T(T(4)))$$

$$:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3)))) \times (4 + T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5448} := (T(5) + T(T(4 + 4))) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times T(T((4 + 4))) + T(T(5))$$

$$\mathbf{5475} := T(5) \times (-T(T(4)) + T(7) \times T(5))$$

$$:= (T(5) \times T(7) - T(T(4))) \times T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5487} := (T(5) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times 7$$

$$:= (7 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(4)) \times T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5488} := 5 \times 4 + T(T(8)) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) + 4 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5497} := -T(5) + 4 \times T(T(9) + 7)$$

$$:= T(7 + T(9)) \times 4 - T(5)$$

$$\mathbf{5523} := T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(3))$$

$$:= (-T(T(3)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(5)))/5$$

$$\mathbf{5525} := T(5 \times 5) \times (2 + T(5))$$

$$:= (T(5) + 2) \times T(5 \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5534} := T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4)$$

$$:= -T(4) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))/5$$

$$\mathbf{5535} := (T(T(5)) \times 5 - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times (-T(T(T(3))) + T(T(5)) \times 5)$$

$$\mathbf{5537} := T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(T(3))) - 7$$

$$:= -7 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(5))/5$$

$$\mathbf{5544} := T(T(5))/5 \times T(T(-4 + T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(-4 + T(4))) \times T(T(5))/5$$

$$\mathbf{5568} := (T(T(5) + T(5)) + T(T(6))) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(5) + T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{5597} := (5 + T(T(5))) \times T(9) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) + T(9) \times (5 + T(T(5)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5625 &:= 5 \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(2))) \times 5 &:= 4^{T(2)} \times T(8 + 5) \\
 &:= 5^{T(2)} \times T(-6 + T(5)) \\
 5655 &:= 5 \times T(T(6)) \times 5 - T(T(5)) &5832 := ((-5 + 8) \times T(3))^{T(2)} \\
 &:= 5 \times 5 \times T(T(6)) - T(T(5)) &:= (T(2) \times T(3))^{8-5} \\
 5658 &:= (T(5) + T(T(6))) \times (T(5) + 8) &5845 := T(T(5)) \times T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - T(5) \\
 &:= (8 + T(5)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(5)) &:= -T(5) + T(T(T(4))) + T(8) \times T(T(5)) \\
 5664 &:= (5 + T(T(6))) \times 6 \times 4 &5848 := (T(T(5)) + T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) \times 8 \\
 &:= 4 \times 6 \times T(T(6)) + T(T(5)) &:= -8 \times (T(T(4)) - T(T(8)) - T(T(5))) \\
 5676 &:= T(T(5) + T(6) + 7) \times 6 &5852 := T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 6 \times T(7 + T(6) + T(5)) &:= 2 \times T(T(5 + 8) - T(5)) \\
 5688 &:= (T(T(5) - 6) + T(T(8))) \times 8 &5865 := 5 \times T(8 \times 6) - T(5) \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) + T(-6 + T(5))) &:= 5 \times T(6 \times 8) - T(5) \\
 5724 &:= T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) - 2 + T(T(T(4))) &5868 := (-5 + 8 \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) - 2 + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) &:= T(8) \times (T(6) \times 8 - 5) \\
 5726 &:= T(T(-T(5) + T(7))) + T(T(T(-2 + 6))) &5894 := (-5 + T(T(8))) \times 9 - T(T(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(6 - 2))) + T(T(T(7) - T(5))) &:= -T(T(4)) + 9 \times (T(T(8)) - 5) \\
 5733 &:= (-T(5) + T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) &5895 := (T(5) + T(T(8) - 9)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \times (T(7) - T(5)) &:= T(5) + T(-9 + T(8)) \times T(5) \\
 5745 &:= -T(5) + (-7 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(5)) &5922 := (-T(T(5)) + T(T(9 + T(2)))) \times 2 \\
 &:= -T(5) + (T(T(4)) - 7) \times T(T(5)) &:= 2 \times (T(T(T(2) + 9)) - T(T(5))) \\
 5747 &:= T(5) \times 7 \times T(T(4)) - T(7) &5925 := T(T(5) + T(9)) + T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(T(4)) \times 7 \times T(5) &:= T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) + T(T(9) + T(5)) \\
 5795 &:= (-5 + T(7) \times T(T(9)))/5 &5928 := T(-5 + T(9) - 2) \times 8 \\
 &:= (-5 + T(T(9)) \times T(7))/5 &:= 8 \times T(-2 + T(9) - 5) \\
 5796 &:= T(-5 + T(7)) \times T(T(9 - 6)) &5949 := 9 \times (T(4 \times 9) - 5) \\
 &:= T(6) \times T(T(9) - 7 - T(5)) &:= (-5 + T(9 \times 4)) \times 9 \\
 5824 &:= (T(T(5)) - 8) \times (-T(2) + T(T(4))) &5955 := -T(T(5)) + T(9) \times (T(T(5)) + T(5)) \\
 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(5)) \times T(9) - T(T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5976 &:= T(5) \times (-9 + T(T(7))) + T(6) \\
 &:= T(6) + (T(T(7)) - 9) \times T(5) \\
 5982 &:= -T(5) + 9 \times T(T(8)) + T(2) \\
 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 9 + T(5) \\
 5983 &:= -5 + 9 \times T(T(8)) - T(3) \\
 &:= -T(3) + T(T(8)) \times 9 - 5 \\
 5998 &:= -5 + 9 + 9 \times T(T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(8)) \times 9 + 9 - 5 \\
 5999 &:= 5 + 9 \times T(T(9) - 9) \\
 &:= 9 \times T(T(9) - 9) + 5 \\
 6125 &:= T((6 + 1)^2) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) + T(1 + 6) \\
 6135 &:= (T(T(6 + 1)) + 3) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (3 + T(T(1 + 6))) \\
 6154 &:= -6 + (-1 + 5) \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times (5 - 1) - 6 \\
 6162 &:= T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \times 2 \\
 &:= 2 \times T(T(6 \times 1 + 6)) \\
 6192 &:= -6 \times (1 - T(T(9)) + 2) \\
 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(9))) \times 1 \times 6 \\
 6194 &:= 6 \times (-1 + T(T(9))) - T(4) \\
 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(9)) - 1) \times 6 \\
 6195 &:= 6 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) - T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(T(9)) \times 1 \times 6 \\
 6197 &:= 6 \times (-1 + T(T(9))) - 7 \\
 &:= -7 + (T(T(9)) - 1) \times 6 \\
 6216 &:= (T(T(6 + T(2))) + 1) \times 6 \\
 &:= 6 \times (1 + T(T(T(2) + 6))) \\
 6222 &:= (-6 + T(2^{T(T(2))})) \times T(2) \\
 &:= T(2) \times (-T(T(2)) + T(2^6)) \\
 6225 &:= 6 \times T(T(T(2)^2)) + T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) + T(2) \times T(2^6) \\
 6227 &:= T(T(T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))) \times T(2) - T(T(7)) \\
 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(2) \times T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(6))) \\
 6228 &:= (T(T(6) - T(2)) + 2) \times T(8) \\
 &:= T(8) \times (2 + T(T(2) \times 6)) \\
 6229 &:= T(6) - 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9)) \times T(T(2)) - 2 + T(6) \\
 6234 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(2) \times 3)) + 4) \\
 &:= T(4^3) \times T(2) - 6 \\
 6237 &:= T(T(6)) \times (2 - 3 + T(7)) \\
 &:= (T(7) - 3 + 2) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6244 &:= (T(T(6/2)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(T(-T(2) + 6))) \\
 6258 &:= 6 \times (T(T(2) \times T(5)) + 8) \\
 &:= (8 + T(T(5) \times T(2))) \times 6 \\
 6272 &:= (6 + 2) \times T(7)^2 \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(7)^{T(2)} / T(6) \\
 6279 &:= T(T(6)) + T(2) \times T(7 \times 9) \\
 &:= T(9 \times 7) \times T(2) + T(T(6)) \\
 6285 &:= T(6) \times T(T(2) \times 8) - T(5) \\
 &:= (-T(5) + T(8 \times T(2))) \times T(6) \\
 6288 &:= 6 + T(T(2) + T(8)) \times 8
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(T(8) + T(2))) + 6$$

$$\mathbf{6295} := T(6) \times T(-T(T(T(2))) + T(9)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(T(9) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6321} := T(T(6) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(2)) + 1)$$

$$:= (1 + T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)) + T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6327} := 6 + T(T(T(3)) \times 2) \times 7$$

$$:= 7 \times T(2 \times T(T(3))) + 6$$

$$\mathbf{6342} := T(6) \times (T(T(3) \times 4) + 2)$$

$$:= (2 + T(4 \times T(3))) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6363} := T(6) \times (3 + T(T(6) + 3))$$

$$:= (3 + T(T(6) + 3)) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6374} := (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(7) - T(4)$$

$$:= -T(4) + T(7) \times (-3 + T(T(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{6375} := T(T(6 + T(3)) - T(7)) \times 5$$

$$:= 5 \times T(-T(7) + T(T(3) + 6))$$

$$\mathbf{6377} := (T(T(6)) - 3) \times T(7) - 7$$

$$:= -7 + T(7) \times (-3 + T(T(6)))$$

$$\mathbf{6384} := T(6) \times (T(3 \times 8) + 4)$$

$$:= (4 + T(8 \times 3)) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6391} := T(T(6)) \times T(T(3)) + T(T(9 + 1))$$

$$:= T(T(1 + 9)) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6399} := (T(6 \times T(3)) + T(9)) \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times (T(9) + T(36))$$

$$\mathbf{6426} := T(T(6) - 4) \times 2 \times T(6)$$

$$:= (6 + T(24)) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6435} := T(6 + 4) \times (-3 + T(T(5)))$$

$$:= (T(T(5)) - 3) \times T(4 + 6)$$

$$\mathbf{6437} := -T(6) - T(4) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(4) - T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6447} := -T(6) + T(T(-4 + T(4))) \times T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) \times T(T(-4 + T(4))) - T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6453} := (6 + T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5)))) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) + 6)$$

$$\mathbf{6468} := T(6) \times (T(4 \times 6) + 8)$$

$$:= (8 + T(6 \times 4)) \times T(6)$$

$$\mathbf{6472} := -6 + T(4) + T(7) \times T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(7) + T(4) - 6$$

$$\mathbf{6474} := 6 \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7)) - T(T(4)))$$

$$:= (-T(T(4)) - T(T(7)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 6$$

$$\mathbf{6483} := 6 \times T(T(4) + T(8)) - 3$$

$$:= -3 + (T(T(8) + T(4))) \times 6$$

$$\mathbf{6484} := -T(T(6)) + T(4) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(4))$$

$$:= T(4) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) - T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6486} := 6 \times T(4 + T(8)) + 6$$

$$:= 6 \times T(T(8) + 4) + 6$$

$$\mathbf{6489} := (T(6 + 4) + T(T(8))) \times 9$$

$$:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(4 + 6))$$

$$\mathbf{6492} := (T(T(T(6) - T(4))) + T(T(9))) \times 2$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times T(-9 + T(T(4))) + 6$$

$$\mathbf{6496} := (T(T(6)) + T(T(4))) + T(T(9)) \times 6$$

$$:= 6 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(4)) + T(T(6))$$

$$\mathbf{6517} := T(6) + (T(5) + 1) \times T(T(7))$$

$$:= T(T(7)) \times (1 + T(5)) + T(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6524 &:= -T(6) + 5 \times (-T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) &:= 4 \times T(2 + T(6)) \times 6 \\
 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5 - T(6) \\
 6525 &:= T(T(6) + 5 + T(2)) \times T(5) &:= T(66) \times (-3 + T(3)) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(T(2) + 5 + T(6))) &:= (-3 + T(3)) \times T(66) \\
 6528 &:= T(T(6) - 5) \times T(T(2)) \times 8 &:= (T(T(6) + 6 \times T(4))) \times 2 \\
 &:= 8 \times T(T(2)) \times T(-5 + T(6)) &:= 2 \times T(T(4) \times 6 + T(6)) \\
 6534 &:= -T(T(6)) + (T(T(5)) + 3) \times T(T(4)) &:= T(6 \times 6) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times (3 + T(T(5))) - T(T(6)) &:= -T(5) + T(4) \times T(6 \times 6) \\
 6545 &:= (-T(6 + T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 &:= T(6 \times 6) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(4))) - 5 \times T(T(6)) &:= -T(5) + T(4) \times T(6 \times 6) \\
 6549 &:= -6 + (T(T(5)) \times T(T(4)) - T(9)) &:= -6 - 6 + T(4) \times T(T(8)) \\
 &:= -T(9) + T(T(4)) \times T(T(5)) - 6 &:= T(T(8)) \times T(4) - 6 - 6 \\
 6552 &:= (6 + T(T(5))) \times 52 &:= -6 + T(T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= (-T(2) + T(T(5))) \times 56 &:= T(4) \times T(T(5) + T(6)) - 6 \\
 6567 &:= -T(6) + T(T(5)) + T(T(6)) \times T(7) &:= (T(T(6)) + 6 \times T(T(5))) \times 7 \\
 &:= T(7) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(5)) - T(6) &:= 7 \times (T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(T(6))) \\
 6573 &:= T(6) \times 5 + T(7) \times T(T(T(3))) &:= -T(6) + T(T(6)) \times (-7 + T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times T(7) + 5 \times T(6) &:= (87 + T(T(6))) \times T(6) \\
 6574 &:= T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) + T(T(7)) \times 4 &:= 6 \times (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 6 \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5)) - T(6)) &:= (T(T(6)) - T(9)) \times 6 \times 6 \\
 6579 &:= -T(T(6) + T(5)) + 7 \times T(T(9)) &:= T(T(6)) \times (6 + T(T(9))/T(9)) \\
 &:= T(T(9)) \times 7 - T(T(5) + T(6)) &:= (T(T(9))/T(9) + 6) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6594 &:= -6 + T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(4)) &:= T(T(6)) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\
 &:= (T(4) + T(9)) \times T(T(5)) - 6 &:= T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6615 &:= T(6) \times T(6) \times 15 &:= T(T(6)) \times T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(1 \times 6) \times T(6) &:= T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6624 &:= 6 \times T(T(6) + 2) \times 4 &:= T(T(T(6))/7) \times T(3) \times 2 \\
 & &:= 2 \times T(T(T(T(3)))/7) \times 6 \\
 6742 &:= -6 + T(7) \times (T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) &:= -6 + T(7) \times (T(4) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times T(7) - 6 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times T(7) - 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6744 &:= 6 \times (-T(T(7)) - T(4) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 &:= (-4 + T(47)) \times 6 \\
 6754 &:= -T(T(6)) + (7 + T(T(5))) \times T(T(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(4)) \times (T(T(5)) + 7) - T(T(6)) \\
 6756 &:= 6 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(5))) \times 6 \\
 &:= (6 \times T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 6 \\
 6762 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(7 + 6)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (T(T(6)) + T(7 + 6)) \\
 6825 &:= T(6) \times T((8 - T(2)) \times 5) \\
 &:= T(5^2) \times T(T(8)/6) \\
 6828 &:= T(T(6)) + T(8) + T(2)^8 \\
 &:= T(8) + T(2)^8 + T(T(6)) \\
 6843 &:= T(T(6) + T(8)) \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times T(T(8) + T(6)) \\
 6844 &:= T(6 \times 8 + T(4)) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(4)) + 8 \times 6 \\
 6855 &:= (T(6) + T(8)) \times T(T(5)) + T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) + T(T(5)) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 6864 &:= -6 + (T(T(8)) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= T(4) \times (T(6) + T(T(8))) - 6 \\
 6873 &:= -T(T(6) + T(8)) + T(T(7)) \times T(T(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)) - T(T(8) + T(6)) \\
 6888 &:= (T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) - T(8)) \times 8 \\
 &:= 8 \times (T(T(8)) - T(8) + T(T(6))) \\
 6891 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \times (9 + 1) \\
 &:= (1 + 9) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) \\
 6894 &:= 6 + 8 \times T(T(9)) - 4 \\
 &:= T(-4 + T(9)) \times 8 + 6 \\
 6925 &:= T(T(6)) \times (9 + T(T(T(2)))) - 5 \\
 &:= -5 + (T(T(T(2))) + 9) \times T(T(6)) \\
 6948 &:= (T(6) \times 9 + 4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= T(8) \times (4 + 9 \times T(6)) \\
 6954 &:= 6 \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(5)) + 4) \\
 &:= (4 + T(T(5)) + T(T(9))) \times 6 \\
 6966 &:= 6 \times (T(T(9)) + 6 \times T(6)) \\
 &:= (6 \times T(6) + T(T(9))) \times 6 \\
 6972 &:= (-6 + T(T(9))) \times 7 - T(T(T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + 7 \times (T(T(9)) - 6) \\
 6978 &:= -T(T(6)) + T(T(9)) \times 7 - T(8) \\
 &:= -T(8) + 7 \times T(T(9)) - T(T(6)) \\
 6987 &:= -6 + (T(T(9)) - T(8)) \times 7 \\
 &:= -7 \times (T(8) - T(T(9))) - 6 \\
 6993 &:= T(6) \times (-T(9) + T(9 \times 3)) \\
 &:= (T(3 \times 9) - T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 7112 &:= T(7) \times (1 + T(1 + T(T(T(2)))))) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) + 1) \times T(7) \\
 7129 &:= T(7) \times T(1 + T(T(T(2)))) + T(9) \\
 &:= T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 1) \times T(7) \\
 7182 &:= 7 \times T(18) \times T(T(2)) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times (-T(8) + T(-1 + T(7))) \\
 7189 &:= 7 \times (-1 \times 8 + T(T(9))) \\
 &:= (T(T(9)) - 8) \times 1 \times 7 \\
 7196 &:= 7 \times (-1 + T(T(9)) - 6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (-6 + T(T(9)) - 1) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7223} := (T(7) + T(2)) \times (2 + T(T(T(3))))$$

$$:= (T(T(T(3))) + 2) \times (T(2) + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7224} := T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times 2 \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times 2 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7245} := 7 \times T(T(2) \times T(4) + T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(5) \times T(4 - 2)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7248} := T(7) \times T(T(T(2))) + (T(4) \times T(T(8)))$$

$$:= T(T(8)) \times T(4) + T(T(T(2))) \times T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7252} := (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T((5 + 2))$$

$$:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(5 + 2)) \times T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7259} := 7 \times (2 + T(5 \times 9))$$

$$:= (T(9 \times 5) + 2) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7266} := (T(T(7) - T(2)) + T(6)) \times T(6)$$

$$:= T(6) \times (T(6) + T(-T(2) + T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7273} := (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(7) + T(T(3))$$

$$:= T(T(3)) + (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7279} := T(7) + T(T(2)) + 7 \times T(T(9))$$

$$:= T(T(9)) \times 7 + T(T(2)) + T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7288} := (T(7 \times T(T(2))) + 8) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (8 + T(T(T(2))) \times 7)$$

$$\mathbf{7293} := 7 \times (T(T(2)) + T(T(9))) + T(3)$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(9)^2 + T(T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7294} := 7 \times (T(2) + T(T(9)) + 4)$$

$$:= (T(4) + T(T(9)) - T(2)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7296} := (T(7^2) - 9) \times 6$$

$$:= 6 \times (-9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7298} := -T(7) + (2 + 9) \times T(T(8))$$

$$:= T(T(8)) \times (9 + 2) - T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{7299} := T(T(7)) \times 2 \times 9 - 9$$

$$:= -9 + 9 \times 2 \times T(T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7308} := (-T(7) + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(08)$$

$$:= T(8) \times (T(T(T(03))) - (T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7326} := (T(T(7)) \times 3 + T(2)) \times 6$$

$$:= 6 \times (T(2) + 3 \times T(T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7329} := 7 \times (T(3) \times 2 + T(T(9)))$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) + 2 \times T(3)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7332} := (T(T(7) + T(T(3))) - 3) \times T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times (-3 + T(T(T(3)) + T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7335} := (T(T(7) + T(T(3)))) \times T(3) - T(5)$$

$$:= -T(5) + T(3) \times T(T(T(3)) + T(7))$$

$$\mathbf{7343} := -7 - (-T(3) \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3)))$$

$$:= T(3) \times T(T(T(4)) - T(3)) - 7$$

$$\mathbf{7353} := (T(T(7)) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(5) + T(3) \times T(T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7362} := (T(T(7)) + 3) \times (T(6) - T(2))$$

$$:= T(2) \times 6 \times (3 + T(T(7)))$$

$$\mathbf{7365} := 7 \times T(T(3 + 6)) + T(T(5))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) + T(T(6 + 3)) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7391} := 7 \times (T(T(3)) + T(T(9))) - 1$$

$$:= -1 + (T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) \times 7$$

$$\mathbf{7392} := T(7) \times (T(3) \times T(9)) - T(T(2))$$

$$:= (T(T(2)) \times T(9) - T(3)) \times T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7394 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(39) \times T(4) & &:= T(2) \times T(T(3)) \times T(T(5)) - T(7) \\
 &:= T(4) \times T(T(9) - T(3)) - T(T(7)) \\
 7395 &:= (T(7) + T(T(T(3)) + 9)) \times T(5) & &7548 := T(7) + 5 \times (T(T(T(4)))) - T(8) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (T(9 + T(T(3)))) + T(7) & &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(4))) \times 5 + T(7) \\
 7425 &:= T((T(7) - T(4)) \times T(2)) \times 5 & &7568 := T(7 + T(5) + T(6)) \times 8 \\
 &:= 5 \times T(T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7))) & &:= 8 \times (T(T(6) + T(5) + 7)) \\
 7427 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) \times T(2) - T(7) & &7595 := 7 \times (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 5) \\
 &:= -T(7) + T(2) \times T(T(4) \times 7) & &:= (T(T(5)) \times 9 + 5) \times 7 \\
 7428 &:= (T(7) + 4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8) & &7596 := T(T(7 - 5)) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(6))) \\
 &:= T(8) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4 - T(7)) & &:= (T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(-5 + 7)) \\
 7435 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) + T(-T(T(3)) + T(T(5))) & &7599 := T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) + T(9 \times 9) \\
 &:= T(5)^3 + T(4) \times T(T(7)) & &:= T(9 \times 9) + T(T(T(5)) - T(7)) \\
 7443 &:= (T(7 \times T(4)) - 4) \times 3 & &7623 := T(T(7)) \times T(6) - T(2 \times T(T(3))) \\
 &:= 3 \times (-4 + T(T(4) \times 7)) & &:= T(T(3 \times 2)) \times T(T(6))/7 \\
 7452 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(4)) \times T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))))) & &7627 := (T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))/7 \\
 &:= T(T(T(T(2))) - 5) \times T(T(4)) - T(7) & &:= (T(7) + T(T(6))^2)/7 \\
 7455 &:= T(7 \times T(4)) \times T(5)/5 & &7672 := T(7) \times (T(6) + T(T(7) - T(T(2)))) \\
 &:= T(5)/5 \times T(T(4) \times 7) & &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(T(7) - 6)) \times T(7) \\
 7482 &:= T(T(7) + T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)) & &7714 := T(T(7)) \times (T(7) + 1 - T(4)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(T(8)) + T(T(T(4)) + T(7)) & &:= (-T(4) + 1 + T(7)) \times T(T(7)) \\
 7483 &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(T(4)) - T(8)) - T(T(T(3))) & &7728 := T(7) \times T(7 + 2 \times 8) \\
 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + (-T(8) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7)) & &:= T(8 \times 2 + 7) \times T(7) \\
 7485 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4))) - T(8)) \times 5 & &7735 := (7 + T(T(7 + 3))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (-T(8) + T(T(T(4))) - 7) & &:= 5 \times (T(T(3 + 7)) + 7) \\
 7514 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(T(5)) \times T(1 + T(4)) & &7749 := T(-7 - 7 + T(T(4))) \times 9 \\
 &:= T(T(4) + 1) \times T(T(5)) - T(T(7)) & &:= 9 \times T(T(T(4)) - 7 - 7) \\
 7532 &:= -T(7) + T(T(5)) \times T(T(3)) \times T(2) & &7784 := (7 + 7) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4))) \\
 & & &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times (7 + 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7819 &:= 7 \times (T(8) + T(1 + T(9))) \\
 &:= (T(T(9) + 1) + T(8)) \times 7 \\
 7826 &:= -T(7) + (T(8) - 2) \times T(T(6)) \\
 &:= T(T(6)) \times (-2 + T(8)) - T(7) \\
 7833 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(8) + 3) \times T(T(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (3 - T(8) + T(T(7))) \\
 7839 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(8) - T(3))) \times 9 \\
 &:= 9 \times (T(-T(3) + T(8)) + T(T(7))) \\
 7845 &:= (-7 + T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5 \\
 &:= 5 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(8) - 7) \\
 7847 &:= (-7 + T(T(T(4)) - 8)) \times 7 \\
 &:= (-7 + T(-8 + T(T(4)))) \times 7 \\
 7848 &:= (T(7) + T(-T(8) + T(T(4)))) \times T(8) \\
 &:= T(8) \times (T(T(T(4)) - T(8)) + T(7)) \\
 7867 &:= 7 - T(T(8)) + T(6) \times T(T(7)) \\
 &:= T(T(7)) \times T(6) - T(T(8)) + 7 \\
 7893 &:= (T(7 \times 8) + T(T(9))) \times 3 \\
 &:= 3 \times (T(T(9)) + T(8 \times 7)) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times T(8 + T(9) - 6) \\
 &:= T(-6 + T(9) + 8) \times 7 \\
 7918 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9)) + 1) + T(T(8)) \\
 &:= T(T(8)) + (1 + T(T(9))) \times 7 \\
 7924 &:= 7 \times (T(T(9) + 2) + 4) \\
 &:= (4 + T(2 + T(9))) \times 7 \\
 7963 &:= 7 + T(T(9) + 6) \times T(3) \\
 &:= T(3) \times T(6 + T(9)) + 7 \\
 7965 &:= 7 \times T(T(9)) + 6 \times T(T(5)) \\
 &:= T(T(5)) \times 6 + T(T(9)) \times 7 \\
 8028 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(T(02)))) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (-8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(08) \\
 8127 &:= (8 + 1) \times T(T(T(2))) \times 7 \\
 &:= T(7 \times T(T(2))) \times (1 + 8) \\
 8136 &:= T(8) \times (1 - T(3) + T(T(6))) \\
 &:= (T(T(6)) - T(3) + 1) \times T(8) \\
 8223 &:= T(T(8)) \times 2 \times T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) \times 2 \times T(T(8)) \\
 8225 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-2 + T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(T(5) - 2) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\
 8228 &:= T(8) + 2^{T(T(T(2))) - 8} \\
 &:= T(8) + 2^{T(T(T(2))) - 8} \\
 8232 &:= (8 + T(T(2)))^3 \times T(2) \\
 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(3^2))) \times 8 \\
 8234 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(T(3)))) - T(4) \\
 &:= -T(4) + (T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(8) \\
 8235 &:= (T(T(8) + T(2)) - T(T(T(3)))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) \times (T(T(T(3))) - T(T(2) + T(8))) \\
 8237 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(T(3)))) - 7 \\
 &:= -7 + (T(T(T(3))) - 2) \times T(8) \\
 8238 &:= -T(T(8)/T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -T(T(8)/3) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\
 8244 &:= T(8) \times (-2 + T(T(-4 + T(4)))) \\
 &:= (T(T(-4 + T(4))) - 2) \times T(8) \\
 8245 &:= (T(T(8) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \times 5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= 5 \times (-4 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8))$$

$$\mathbf{8256} := 8 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(5) - 6)))$$

$$:= (T(T(-6 + T(5))) - T(2)) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{8265} := 8 \times T(T(T(2) + 6)) - T(5)$$

$$:= 5 \times T(T(T(6/2)) + T(8))$$

$$\mathbf{8267} := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(6) - T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) - T(6) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8268} := -8 \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6)) \times T(8)$$

$$:= T(8) \times T(T(6)) - T(T(2)) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{8275} := 8 \times T(T(2 + 7)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(T(7 + 2)) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{8279} := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(7) - 9$$

$$:= -9 - T(7) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8292} := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(9) + T(T(T(2)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(2))) - T(9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8293} := 8 \times (2 + T(T(9))) - 3$$

$$:= 3 + (T(T(9)) + 2) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{8294} := -T(4) + (T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 8$$

$$:= 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - T(4)$$

$$\mathbf{8295} := T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(-9 + T(5))$$

$$:= -T(T(5) - 9) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8297} := 8 \times (T(2) + T(T(9))) - 7$$

$$:= -7 + (T(T(9)) + T(2)) \times 8$$

$$\mathbf{8308} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 08$$

$$:= T(8) \times T(T(T(03))) - 8$$

$$\mathbf{8312} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1 - T(2)$$

$$:= -T(2) - 1 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8313} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1 \times 3$$

$$:= -3 + 1 \times T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8316} := T(8) \times T(3 \times (1 + 6))$$

$$:= T((6 + 1) \times 3) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8321} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(2)) - 1$$

$$:= -1 + T(T(2)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8322} := T(8) \times T(T((3 \times 2))) + T(T(2))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) + T(T(2 \times 3)) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8323} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(2)))/3$$

$$:= T(T(3))/T(2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8324} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 2 \times 4$$

$$:= T(4 \times 2) \times T(T(T(3))) + 8$$

$$\mathbf{8325} := (T(T(8) - 3) - T(T(2))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= -T(5) \times (T(T(2)) - T(-3 + T(8)))$$

$$\mathbf{8326} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(-2 + 6)$$

$$:= T(6 - 2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8328} := T(8)/3 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8)$$

$$:= T(8)/T(2) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8331} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(3) - 1)$$

$$:= T(-1 + T(3)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8337} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 3 \times 7$$

$$:= 7 \times 3 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\mathbf{8343} := -T(T(8)) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3)))$$

$$:= T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(3))) - T(T(8))$$

$$\mathbf{8344} := T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4)))/T(T(4)) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8345 &:= T(T(8)) - T(T(3)) + T(T(T(4))) \times 5 \\ &:= 5 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(3)) + T(T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (T(T(6)) + 9 - 4) \times T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8348 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 4 \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times 4 + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8523 &:= T(T(-8 + T(5))) \times T(T(T(2))) - 3 \\ &:= (-3 + T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8352 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(5 + T(2)) \\ &:= (T(T(2)) - 5 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8526 &:= (T(T(8) - 5 - T(2))) \times T(6) \\ &:= T(6) \times T(T(T(2) \times 5 - 8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8364 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(T(T(3)) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\ &:= T(4) \times T(T(6) + T(T(3))) - T(T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8532 &:= T(8) \times (T(T(5) + T(3)) + T(T(2))) \\ &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(3) + T(5))) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8372 &:= T(T(8) + T((3 + 7))) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times T(T(7 \times 3 - 8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8544 &:= -T(8) + T(T(T(5)) - T(T(4))) \times 4 \\ &:= 4 \times T(-T(T(4)) + T(T(5))) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8379 &:= (T(T(8) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times 9 \\ &:= 9 \times (T(7) + T(T(3) + T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8567 &:= T(8) + 5 + T(6) \times T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) \times T(6) + 5 + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8382 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8 + T(2)) \\ &:= T(T(2) + 8) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8568 &:= (T(8) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times 8 \\ &:= 8 \times T(6) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8385 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(T(3))) \times (8 + 5) \\ &:= (5 + 8) \times (-T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8572 &:= (8 + T(T(T(5)) - T(7))) \times 2 \\ &:= 2 \times (T(-T(7) + T(T(5))) + 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8388 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + ((T(8) + T(8))) \\ &:= T(8) + T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8574 &:= -T(T(8)) + T(T(-5 + 7)) \times T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(7 - 5)) - (T(T(8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8415 &:= T(8 \times 4 + 1) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times T(1 + 4 \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8592 &:= 8 \times (T(T(5)) \times 9 - T(T(2))) \\ &:= (-T(T(2)) + 9 \times T(T(5))) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8423 &:= 8^4 \times 2 + T(T(T(3))) \\ &:= T(T(T(3))) + 2^{T(4)} \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8624 &:= 8 \times (-T(T(6)) \times 2 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) - 2 \times T(T(6))) \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8424 &:= T(T(8) - T(4)) \times 24 \\ &:= 4 \times T(T(2)) \times T(-T(4) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8646 &:= T(8) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(4)) \times 6 \\ &:= 6 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(6)) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8458 &:= 8 - T(T(T(4))) + T(5) \times T(T(8)) \\ &:= T(T(8)) \times T(5) - T(T(T(4))) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8648 &:= 8 \times T(6 + 4 + T(8)) \\ &:= 8 \times T(4 + 6 + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$8496 := T(8) \times (-4 + 9 + T(T(6)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8658 &:= T(T(8)) \times (6 + T(5) - 8) \\ &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(5) + 6 - 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 8673 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(-6 + T(7))) \times T(T(3)) \\
 &:= T(T(3)) \times (-T(T(7) - 6) + T(T(8))) \\
 8674 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(6)) \times T(7)) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(7) \times T(T(6)) + T(T(8)) \\
 8679 &:= -T(8) + T(6) \times (T(T(7)) + 9) \\
 &:= (9 + T(T(7))) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 8739 &:= (8 + T(T(7))) \times T(T(3)) + T(9) \\
 &:= T(9) + T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + 8) \\
 8742 &:= -T(T(8)) + (T(7) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(T(2)) \\
 &:= T(T(2)) \times (T(T(T(4))) + T(7)) - T(T(8)) \\
 8745 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(7) - T(T(4))) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times (-T(T(4)) - T(7) + T(T(8))) \\
 8749 &:= (T(T(8)) + 7) \times (4 + 9) \\
 &:= (9 + 4) \times (7 + T(T(8))) \\
 8764 &:= 8 \times T(7 \times 6) + T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(6 \times 7) \times 8 \\
 8784 &:= 8 \times (-T(T(7)) - T(8) + T(T(T(4)))) \\
 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(8) - T(T(7))) \times 8 \\
 8824 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(8 + 2))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times (T(T(2 + 8)) + T(T(8))) \\
 8827 &:= (T(T(8)) + T(T(8) - 2)) \times 7 \\
 &:= 7 \times (T(-2 + T(8)) + T(T(8))) \\
 8834 &:= -T(-8 + T(8)) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(3) - T(-8 + T(8)) \\
 8844 &:= T(T(8 + T(8/4))) \times 4 \\
 &:= 4 \times T(T(4 \times 8)/8) \\
 8848 &:= 8 \times (8 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \\
 &:= (8 \times T(T(4)) + T(T(8))) \times 8 \\
 8856 &:= T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 6 \\
 &:= 6 \times (5 + T(8)) \times T(8) \\
 8895 &:= T(8 + T(8)) \times 9 - T(5) \\
 &:= -T(5) + 9 \times T(8 + T(8)) \\
 8925 &:= T((8 + 9) \times 2) \times T(5) \\
 &:= T(5) \times T(2 \times (9 + 8)) \\
 8928 &:= (8 + 9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (8 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 9) \times T(8) \\
 8991 &:= (-T(8) + T(T(9))) \times 9 \times 1 \\
 &:= 1 \times 9 \times (T(T(9)) - T(8)) \\
 9129 &:= (T(9) - 1) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(9)) \\
 &:= -T(T(9)) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-1 + T(9)) \\
 9195 &:= 9 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) - T(T(5)) \\
 &:= -T(T(5)) + 9 \times T(T(1 \times 9)) \\
 9222 &:= T(T(9 + T(2))) \times T(2) - T(T(T(2))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(2)))^{T(2)} + T(T(2)) - T(9) \\
 9225 &:= T(T(9)) + 2 \times T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) \\
 &:= T(T(5) \times T(T(2))) \times 2 + T(T(9)) \\
 9231 &:= -9 + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(3 + 1))) \\
 &:= T(T(T(1 + 3))) \times T(T(2)) - 9 \\
 9233 &:= -T(9 - 2) + T(T(3))^3 \\
 &:= T(T(3))^3 - T(-2 + 9) \\
 9234 &:= -9 + T(2) \times T(T(3 \times 4)) \\
 &:= T(T(4 \times 3)) \times T(2) - 9 \\
 9252 &:= -9 + (T(T(2)) + T(5))^{T(2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= (T(T(2)) + T(5))^{T(2)} - 9$$

$$\mathbf{9264} := T(9) - T(T(T(2))) + 6 \times T(T(T(4)))$$

$$:= T(T(T(4))) \times 6 - T(T(T(2))) + T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9276} := T(T(9) + T(T(2))) \times 7 - 6$$

$$:= -6 + 7 \times T(T(T(2)) + T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{9279} := (T(T(9)) + T(2) - 7) \times 9$$

$$:= (T(T(9)) - 7 + T(2)) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{9282} := (T(T(9 - 2)) + T(8)) \times T(T(T(2)))$$

$$:= T(T(2)) \times (8^{T(2)} + T(T(9)))$$

$$\mathbf{9285} := (-T(9) - 2 + T(T(8))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - 2 - T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{9288} := (-9 + T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) \times T(8)$$

$$:= T(8) \times (T(8) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 9)$$

$$\mathbf{9294} := (-T(T(9)) - T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(9)) \times T(4)$$

$$:= (T(T(T(4))) + 9) \times (-T(2) + 9)$$

$$\mathbf{9312} := (T(T(9)) \times 3 - 1) \times T(2)$$

$$:= T(2) \times (-1 + 3 \times T(T(9)))$$

$$\mathbf{9315} := 9 \times T(3 \times 15)$$

$$:= (5 + 1 + 3) \times T(T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{9333} := (T(T(9)) \times 3 + T(3)) \times 3$$

$$:= 3 \times (T(3) + 3 \times T(T(9)))$$

$$\mathbf{9336} := 9 \times T(T(3 \times 3)) + T(6)$$

$$:= T(6) + T(T(3 \times 3)) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{9355} := T(9 + 3) \times T(T(5)) - 5$$

$$:= (-5 + T(T(5)) \times T(3 + 9))$$

$$\mathbf{9369} := (T(T(9)) + T(-3 + 6)) \times 9$$

$$:= ((T(T(9)) + T((6 - 3))) \times 9)$$

$$\mathbf{9387} := T(9) \times T(T(T(3))) - T(8) \times T(7)$$

$$:= -T(7) \times T(8) + T(T(T(3))) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9396} := 9 \times (3 + T(T(9)) + 6)$$

$$:= (6 + T(T(9)) + 3) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{9397} := (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9 + T(7)$$

$$:= T(7) + (T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 9$$

$$\mathbf{9424} := (9 + T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)$$

$$:= T(T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(4) + 9)$$

$$\mathbf{9426} := -T(9) + T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(2)) + T(T(6))$$

$$:= T(T(6)) + T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9435} := (T(T(9)) - T(T(4 + 3))) \times T(5)$$

$$:= -T(5) + T(T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9444} := (T(T(9)) + T(-4 + T(T(4)))) \times 4$$

$$:= 4 \times (T(-4 + T(T(4))) + T(T(9)))$$

$$\mathbf{9445} := T(9) \times T(T(4) + T(4)) - 5$$

$$:= -5 + T(T(4) + T(4)) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9462} := -9 + T(T(T(4))) \times 6 + T(T(T(T(2))))$$

$$:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + 6 \times T(T(T(4))) - 9$$

$$\mathbf{9465} := T(9) \times T(4) \times T(6) + T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) + T(6) \times T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{9471} := (T(9) - 4) \times T(T(7 - 1))$$

$$:= T(T(-1 + 7)) \times (-4 + T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{9485} := T(T(9)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(8)) \times T(5)$$

$$:= T(5) \times T(T(8)) - T(T(T(4))) + T(T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{9495} := T(9) \times (T(4 + 9) + T(T(5)))$$

$$:= T(T(5)) \times T(9) + T(T(4) \times 9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9546 &:= 9 \times T(T(5+4)) + T(T(6)) \\ &:= T(T(6)) + T(45) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9567 &:= 9 \times (T(T(T(5)-6)) + T(7)) \\ &:= (T(7) + T(T(-6+T(5)))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9576 &:= (T(9) + 5 + T(T(7))) \times T(6) \\ &:= T(6) \times T(T(7)) + T(5) + T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9585 &:= (T(9) \times T(5) - T(8)) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times (-T(8) + T(5) \times T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9586 &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(-8+T(6))) \\ &:= T(T(T(6)-8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9594 &:= 9 \times (-T(5) + T(-9+T(T(4)))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))-9) - T(5)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9624 &:= -T(T(-9+T(6))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4)) \\ &:= T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(6)-9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9639 &:= 9 \times T(6) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\ &:= (T(9) + T(3)) \times T(6) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9648 &:= (T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times (4+8) \\ &:= (8+4) \times (-T(T(6)) + T(T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9672 &:= (T(9) - T(6)) \times (T(T(7)) - T(2)) \\ &:= (-T(2) + T(T(7))) \times (-T(6) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9693 &:= 9 \times (T(6) + T(T(9)) + T(T(3))) \\ &:= (T(T(3)) + T(T(9)) + T(6)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9724 &:= -T(T(9)) + 7 \times (-T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ &:= (T(T(T(4))) - T(2)) \times 7 - T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9728 &:= (T(9) - 7) \times 2^8 \\ &:= 8^{T(2)} \times (T(7) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9729 &:= 9 \times T(T(7) + 2 \times 9) \\ &:= T(9 \times 2 + T(7)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9742 &:= -T(T(9)) + 7 \times T(T(T(4))) - T(2) \\ &:= -T(2) + T(T(T(4))) \times 7 - T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9747 &:= (-T(9) + T(T(7))) \times (T(T(4)) - T(7)) \\ &:= (-T(7) + T(T(4))) \times (T(T(7)) - T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9765 &:= T(T(9)) \times 7 + T(6) \times T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) \times T(6) + 7 \times T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9795 &:= T(T(9)) + (T(7) + T(9)) \times T(T(5)) \\ &:= T(T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(7)) + T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9825 &:= (-9 + T(T(8)) - 2) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times (-2 + T(T(8)) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9837 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) \\ &:= (T(T(7)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(8))) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9852 &:= (-9 + T(T(8))) \times T(5) - T(2) \\ &:= -T(2) + T(5) \times (T(T(8)) - 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9882 &:= (T(9 \times 8) + T(T(8))) \times T(2) \\ &:= T(2)^8 + T(T(8) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9884 &:= (T(T(9)) + 8) \times 8 + T(T(T(4))) \\ &:= T(T(T(4))) + 8 \times (8 + T(T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9927 &:= -T(T(9)) + 9 \times T(2) \times T(T(7)) \\ &:= T(T(7)) \times (T(2) \times 9) - T(T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9936 &:= T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \times 36 \\ &:= 6 \times T(3) \times T(T(T(9))/T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9945 &:= -T(9) + T(9 \times 4) \times T(5) \\ &:= T(5) \times T(4 \times 9) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9963 &:= T(9 \times 9) \times (6 - 3) \\ &:= (-3 + 6) \times T(9 \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9981 &:= 9 \times T(T(9)) + T(T(8 \times 1)) \\ &:= T(T(1 \times 8)) + T(T(9)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9985 &:= T(T(9)/9) \times T(T(8)) - 5 \\ &:= T(5) \times T(T(8)) - T(9)/9 \end{aligned}$$

6.2 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned} 153 &:= T(-1 + T(5) + 3) \\ 205 &:= T(20) - 5 \\ 210 &:= T(2 \times 10) \\ 240 &:= T(T(2)) \times 40 \\ 297 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 9/7 \\ 360 &:= T(3) \times 60 \\ 442 &:= T(-4 + T(T(4)))/T(2) \\ 495 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(9)/5 \\ 629 &:= -T(T(T(6)/T(2))) + T(T(9)) \\ 630 &:= T(6) \times 30 \\ 638 &:= -T(T(6)/3) + T(T(8)) \\ 742 &:= (-T(7) + T(T(T(4))))/2 \\ 784 &:= T(7)^{8/4} \\ 945 &:= T(9) \times T(T(T(T(4)/5))) \\ 1024 &:= 1 \times 02^{T(4)} \\ 1025 &:= -10 + T(T(2) \times T(5)) \\ 1029 &:= -T(1 + 02) + T(T(9)) \\ 1035 &:= T(10 + 35) \\ 1036 &:= 1 + T(T(03 + 6)) \\ 1039 &:= 1 + 03 + T(T(9)) \\ 1045 &:= 10 + T(45) \\ 1049 &:= 10 + 4 + T(T(9)) \\ 1056 &:= T(10) \times T(5) + T(T(6)) \\ 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) \\ 1081 &:= T(1 + T(08 + 1)) \\ 1088 &:= -T(T(10)) + T(T(8) + T(8)) \\ 1149 &:= 114 + T(T(9)) \\ 1210 &:= (1 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(10) \\ 1284 &:= -1 \times 2^8 + T(T(T(4))) \\ 1310 &:= 1 - T(T(T(3))) + T(T(10)) \\ 1339 &:= 13 + T(T(3) + T(9)) \\ 1395 &:= 1 \times 3 \times T(T(9) - T(5)) \\ 1470 &:= T(T(-1 + 4)) \times 70 \\ 1489 &:= T(-1 + T(T(4))) + T(8)/9 \\ 1498 &:= T(1 + T(T(4))) - 98 \\ 1499 &:= 14 + T(9 + T(9)) \\ 1506 &:= T(1 \times 50) + T(T(6)) \\ 1520 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - 20 \\ 1537 &:= T(T(T(-1 + 5))) - T(T(3))/7 \\ 1554 &:= -1^5 + T(5) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 1567 &:= -1 + T(56) - T(7) \\ 1632 &:= T(16) \times T(3) \times 2 \\ 1661 &:= 1 - T(T(6)) + T(61) \\ 1665 &:= T(-1 + 6) \times (T(T(6)) - T(T(5))) \\ 1668 &:= T(-1 + 6) + T(T(6) + T(8)) \\ 1824 &:= T(18) + T(2 + T(T(4))) \\ 1850 &:= (1 + T(8)) \times 50 \\ 1892 &:= 1 + T(T(T(T(8)/9)) + T(T(2))) \\ 1899 &:= -T(18) + T(T(9)) + T(T(9)) \\ 1912 &:= 1 + 91 \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 1962 &:= 1 \times 9 + T(62) \\ 2036 &:= 20 + T(3 \times T(6)) \\ 2065 &:= (T(2^{06}) - T(5)) \\ 2082 &:= 2 + T(08^2) \\ 2100 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times 100 \\ 2165 &:= T(T(T(2))) - 1 + T(65) \\ 2250 &:= T(T(2)^2) \times 50 \\ 2267 &:= -T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))) + T(67) \\ 2372 &:= -2^{T(3)} + T(T(7)) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2400 &:= T(T(2)) \times 400 \\ 2410 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(4)) \times 10 \\ 2417 &:= 2 + T(41 + T(7)) \\ 2430 &:= T(2)^4 \times 30 \\ 2440 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 40 \\ 2450 &:= (-T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times 50 \\ 2458 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(T(T(4)))/5 \times 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2480 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + T(4)) \times 80 & 3597 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + T(59 + T(7)) \\ 2489 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(T(4)) + T(T(T(8)))/9 & 3600 &:= T(3) \times 600 \\ 2494 &:= -T(2)^4 + T(T(9)) + T(T(T(4))) & 3807 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(80 + 7) \\ 2510 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 10 & 3819 &:= T(T(3) + 81) - 9 \\ 2519 &:= T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(5)) - 1^9 & 3877 &:= T(T(3)) + T(87) + T(7) \\ 2550 &:= (-T(2) + 5) \times T(50) & 3879 &:= T(3) + T(87) + T(9) \\ 2571 &:= T(2) \times 5 + T(71) & 3898 &:= T(3) \times T(T(8)) - 98 \\ 2582 &:= 2 \times (-5 + T(8)^2) & 3913 &:= -3 + T(91 - 3) \\ 2640 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6) \times 40 & 3951 &:= 3 \times (-9 + T(51)) \\ 2649 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + 64 \times T(9) & 3954 &:= -T(T(T(3))) + 9 \times T(T(T(5)))/4 \\ 2703 &:= 2 + T(70 + 3) & 3960 &:= (T(T(3)) + T(9)) \times 60 \\ 2709 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + 70) \times 9 & 3970 &:= T(T(3) \times 9) + T(70) \\ 2730 &:= T(T(T(2)) + 7) \times 30 & 4065 &:= (40 + T(T(6))) \times T(5) \\ 2750 &:= T(T(2) + 7) \times 50 & 4095 &:= T(40 + T(9) + 5) \\ 2781 &:= T(T(2)) + T(-7 + 81) & 4190 &:= 4 + T(1 + 90) \\ 2790 &:= (T(2) + T(7)) \times 90 & 4191 &:= 4 + 1 + T(91) \\ 2824 &:= -2^8 + 2 \times T(T(T(4))) & 4192 &:= T(T(T(4)) + T(-1 + 9)) + T(T(2)) \\ 2825 &:= -2^8 + T(T(-T(2) + T(5))) & 4194 &:= T(T(4)) - 1 + T(T(9)) \times 4 \\ 2878 &:= T(28) \times 7 + T(8) & 4196 &:= T(4) + T(T(19 - 6)) \\ 2953 &:= -2^9 + T(5) \times T(T(T(3))) & 4216 &:= 4^{T(T(2))} + T(T(-1 + 6)) \\ 2958 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times 58 & 4233 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - T(3))/3 \\ 2974 &:= -2^9 + T(T(7) + T(T(4))) & 4256 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T(T(2)))) \times 56 \\ 3033 &:= 30 + T(T(T(T(3))))/3 & 4286 &:= T(4)^2 + T(T(-8 + T(6))) \\ 3102 &:= T(T(3)) + T(T(10 + 2)) & 4288 &:= 4 \times (T(28) + T(T(8))) \\ 3112 &:= 31 + T(T(12)) & 4312 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3))) \times 12 \\ 3129 &:= 3 + T(T(12)) + T(9) & 4330 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(3) \times T(30) \\ 3142 &:= T(3) + (1 + T(T(4)))^2 & 4333 &:= 4^{T(3)} + T(3) + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3197 &:= T(31) + T(T(9) + T(7)) & 4350 &:= T(4) \times T(-T(T(3)) + 50) \\ 3282 &:= (3 + T(2)^8)/2 & 4386 &:= (-T(4) + T(38)) \times 6 \\ 3289 &:= -32 + T(T(8) + T(9)) & 4388 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(38) \times 8 \\ 3341 &:= T(T(3)) + T(3^4) - 1 & 4468 &:= 4 \times (T(46) + T(8)) \\ 3375 &:= T(3 \times 3) \times 75 & 4476 &:= T(T(T(4))) + T(4) + T(76) \\ 3382 &:= -T(3 + 3) + T(82) & 4679 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(6) + T(79) \\ 3387 &:= -T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) + T(87) & 4690 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(6)) + T(90) \\ 3417 &:= T(T(T(3)) \times 4) - T(17) & 4780 &:= T(T(4)) \times T(7) + T(80) \\ 3441 &:= -3 + 4 \times T(41) & 4897 &:= 4 \times T(8) + T(97) \\ 3445 &:= T(3^4) + 4 + T(T(5)) & 5236 &:= T(-5 + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(T(3)))/6 \\ 3510 &:= T(T(T(3)) + 5) \times 10 & 5250 &:= 5 \times T(T(T(2))) \times 50 \\ 3583 &:= T(T(3) \times T(5)) - 8^3 & 5262 &:= T(5) \times T(26) - T(2) \\ & & 5280 &:= T(5 + T(T(2))) \times 80 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5288 &:= (-T(5)/T(2) + T(T(8))) \times 8 & 7410 &:= (T(T(7) + T(4))) \times 10 \\
 5324 &:= (5 + T(3))^{T(2)} \times 4 & 7420 &:= T(7) \times (T(T(4)) + T(20)) \\
 5375 &:= 5^3 \times (T(7) + T(5)) & 7438 &:= T(7) + T(4) \times T(38) \\
 5423 &:= 5 + T(42) \times T(3) & 7442 &:= (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4)) - 4)/T(2) \\
 5485 &:= T(5 + T(T(4))) + T(85) & 7462 &:= T(T(7)) + (4 \times T(6))^2 \\
 5616 &:= T(5 + T(6)) \times 16 & 7567 &:= T(T(T(7) - 5)/6) \times 7 \\
 5640 &:= (T(T(5)) + T(6)) \times 40 & 7653 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(65)) \times 3 \\
 5720 &:= (-T(T(5)) + T(T(7))) \times 20 & 8120 &:= T(T(8 - 1)) \times 20 \\
 5929 &:= (T(T(T(5) - 9)))^2/9 & 8214 &:= T(T(8))^2/(-1 + T(T(4))) \\
 6132 &:= (61 + T(T(T(3)))) \times T(T(T(2))) & 8258 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 58 \\
 6249 &:= (-T(6) + T(T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(T(9)))) & 8298 &:= T(8)/2 + T(T(9)) \times 8 \\
 6300 &:= T(6) \times 300 & 8315 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) - 1^5 \\
 6324 &:= T(T(T(6))/3) + T(T(2)^4) & 8317 &:= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 1^7 \\
 6459 &:= T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))/5 - 9 & 8436 &:= T(T(8)) \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))/6 \\
 6480 &:= (6 - 4) \times T(80) & 8637 &:= T(T(8))/6 + T(T(3)) \times T(T(7)) \\
 6783 &:= T(6) \times (T(T(7)) - 83) & 8640 &:= T(8) \times 6 \times 40 \\
 6804 &:= T(6) \times T(80)/T(4) & 8694 &:= T(8) \times T(69)/T(4) \\
 6819 &:= -T(6) + T(8) \times T(19) & 8955 &:= (T(T(8)) - T(T(9)))/T(5) \times T(5) \\
 7203 &:= 7^{T(2)} \times T(T(03)) & 9227 &:= T(T(9)) + 2^{T(T(2))+7} \\
 7280 &:= T(7 + T(T(2))) \times 80 & 9522 &:= (((T(T(9)))/T(5))^2) \times 2) \\
 7350 &:= 7 \times T(T(3)) \times 50 & 9613 &:= -T(T(9)) + (T(6) + 1)^3 \\
 7355 &:= -T(T(7)) + T(3)^5 - T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

6.3 Reverse Order of Digits

$$\begin{aligned}
 191 &:= T(19) + 1 & 0105 &:= 50 + T(10) \\
 246 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(4))/2 & 0122 &:= 2 \times (T(T(2)) + T(10)) \\
 247 &:= T(T(7) + T(4))/T(2) & 0124 &:= 4 \times (T(T(T(2))) + 10) \\
 337 &:= 7^3 - T(3) & 0127 &:= 72 + T(10) \\
 339 &:= T(T(9))/3 - T(3) & 0128 &:= 8 \times (T(T(2)) + 10) \\
 356 &:= T(T(6)) + 5^3 & 0133 &:= -3 + T(T(3) + 10) \\
 522 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(2^5) & 0136 &:= T(6) \times T(3) + 10 \\
 523 &:= T(32) + 5 & 0137 &:= -T(7) + 3 \times T(10) \\
 524 &:= -4 + T(2^5) & 0138 &:= 83 + T(10) \\
 526 &:= T(T((T(6)/T(2)))) + T(T(5)) & 0143 &:= T(T(T(3)) - 4) - 10 \\
 576 &:= T((T(T(6))/7)) + T(5) & 0144 &:= T(T(T(4)))/T(4) - 10 \\
 703 &:= T(30 + 7) & 0146 &:= T(6 + T(4)) + 10 \\
 729 &:= 9^{T(T(2))}/7 & 0149 &:= 94 + T(10) \\
 & & 0165 &:= T(5) \times (T(6) - 10)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 0182** := $2 \times (T(8) + T(10))$
0184 := $4 \times (T(8) + 10)$
0189 := $9 \times T(T(T(-8 + 10)))$
0205 := $-5 + T(020)$
0231 := $T(1^3 + 20)$
0234 := $4 \times T(3) + T(20)$
0251 := $T(T(1 + 5)) + 20$
0253 := $T(-3 + 5 + 20)$
0273 := $3 \times T(-7 + 20)$
0276 := $T(T(6)/7 + 20)$
0288 := $8 \times T(8 + 2 \times 0)$
0296 := $T(T(6)) + T(9) + 20$
0297 := $-T(7) + T(T(9) - 20)$
0351 := $T(1 - 5 + 30)$
0355 := $T(5 \times 5) + 30$
0369 := $-96 + T(30)$
0376 := $T(T(6) + 7) - 30$
0378 := $-87 + T(30)$
0387 := $-78 + T(30)$
0396 := $-69 + T(30)$
0397 := $T(T(7)) - 9 - 3 \times 0$
0422 := $2 \times T(T(T(T(2)))) - 40$
0425 := $T(T(5) \times 2) - 40$
0462 := $2 \times T(T(6 + 4 \times 0))$
0465 := $T(5 \times 6 + 4 \times 0)$
0467 := $T(T(7)) + T(6) + 40$
0493 := $-3 + T(-9 + 40)$
0528 := $T(82 - 50)$
0546 := $T(T(6) + T(4)) + 50$
0562 := $2 \times (T(T(6)) + 50)$
0568 := $8 \times (T(6) + 50)$
0579 := $T(T(9)) - T(T(7)) - 50$
0633 := $3 \times T(T(T(3))) - 60$
0637 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(T(3 + 6 \times 0)))$
0729 := $9^{T(2+7 \times 0)}$
0736 := $T(6 \times T(3)) + 70$
0763 := $3 \times T(T(6)) + 70$
0823 := $T(T(T(3)) \times 2) - 80$
0924 := $4 \times T(T(T(T(2 + 9 \times 0))))$
0945 := $T(T(5 + 4)) - 90$
0963 := $3 \times (T(T(6)) + 90)$
1147 := $T(7) \times 41 - 1$
1288 := $-8 + T(8)^2 \times 1$
1334 := $T(T(4) \times T(3)) - T(31)$
1359 := $9 \times (T(T(5)) + 31)$
1369 := $-9 + T(T(6) + 31)$
1427 := $-T(7)^2 + T(T(T(4) + 1))$
1444 := $T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - 41$
1452 := $T(T(T(2))) + T(54 - 1)$
1465 := $-T(T(5))/6 + T(T(T(4)) - 1)$
1528 := $-T(8)/T(2) + T(T(T(5 - 1)))$
1536 := $T(T(6)) - T(T(3)) + T(51)$
1557 := $T(T(T(T(7 - 5)))) + T(51)$
1563 := $T(3) + T(T(6)) + T(51)$
1578 := $T(8) \times 7 + T(51)$
1591 := $T(T(1 + 9)) + 51$
1601 := $T(T(10)) + 61$
1647 := $(-T(7) + T(T(4))) \times 61$
1675 := $T(57) + T(6) + 1$
1724 := $T(T(T(4)) + 2) + 71$
1739 := $T(T(9)) + T(37) + 1$
1759 := $T(T(9) + T(5)) - 71$
1876 := $67 \times T(8 - 1)$
1911 := $T(T(T(1 + 1))) \times 91$
1934 := $43 \times T(9) - 1$
2018 := $T(8 + T(10)) + 2$
2025 := $(T(5) \times T(2))^{02}$
2061 := $T(1 \times 60) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
2063 := $T(T(T(3))) + T(60) + 2$
2075 := $-5 + T(70 - T(T(2)))$
2077 := $-T(T(7)) + T(70) - 2$
2133 := $T(T(T(T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) - T(12)$
2164 := $(T(46) + 1) \times 2$
2172 := $T(2)^7 - T(-1 + T(T(2)))$
2174 := $-T(4) + T(7) \times T(12)$
2201 := $(-10 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2)))/T(T(T(2))))))$
2257 := $T(T(7)) + T(T(T(5))/2) + T(T(T(2)))$
2276 := $T(67) - T(T(2))/T(2)$
2294 := $-T(4) + (T(9) + T(2))^2$
2297 := $-7 + (T(9) + T(2))^2$

$$\begin{aligned} 2396 &:= T(69) - T(T(3)) + 2 \\ 2407 &:= T(70) - T(T(4) + 2) \\ 2418 &:= T(81) - T(42) \\ 2425 &:= T(T(T(5))/2) + T(T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2456 &:= T(6) \times T(T(5)) - 4^{T(2)} \\ 2538 &:= (T(T(8)) - 3^5) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2588 &:= T(T(8) + T(8)) - T(T(5))/T(2) \\ 2592 &:= T(T(2))^{9-5} \times 2 \\ 2618 &:= T(T(8)) - 1 + T(62) \\ 2627 &:= T(72) - 6/T(T(2)) \\ 2675 &:= T(T(5 + 7)) - T(T(T(6)/T(2))) \\ 2698 &:= T(T(T(8))/9) - T(T(6))/T(2) \\ 2719 &:= 91 + T(72) \\ 2737 &:= -7 + (T(T(3)) - 7)^{T(2)} \\ 2755 &:= 5 \times T(57)/T(2) \\ 2765 &:= 5 \times (-T(T(6)) + T(7)^2) \\ 2799 &:= T(9 + 9) + T(72) \\ 2809 &:= (T(9) + 08)^2 \\ 2832 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/3) - T(T(8)/2) \\ 2837 &:= T(73) + T(8 \times 2) \\ 2846 &:= -T(T(6)) - 4 + T(T(T(8)/T(2))) \\ 2865 &:= T(5) - T(T(6)) + T(T(T(8)/T(2))) \\ 2868 &:= (8 + T(T(6))) \times T(8)/T(2) \\ 2891 &:= -T(19) + T(T(T(8)/T(2))) \\ 2994 &:= 499 \times T(T(2)) \\ 2997 &:= (T(7) + 9) \times 9^2 \\ 3024 &:= T(T(T(T(4)))/20) + T(T(3)) \\ 3087 &:= T(78) + T(03) \\ 3178 &:= -T(8) \times T(7) + T(T(13)) \\ 3179 &:= -T(T(9)) + T(7) + T(T(13)) \\ 3236 &:= T(T(T(6))/3) + 2 + T(T(T(3))) \\ 3294 &:= T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)/T(T(T(2))) - T(3) \\ 3295 &:= -5 + T(9^2) - T(T(3)) \\ 3318 &:= T(81) + 3 - T(3) \\ 3352 &:= -2 + T(5)^3 - T(T(3)) \\ 3354 &:= (T(4) + 5)^3 - T(T(3)) \\ 3367 &:= T(76) + T(T(3)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 3369 &:= (9 + 6)^3 - T(3) \\ 3427 &:= 7^{T(2)} \times T(4) - 3 \\ 3428 &:= T(82) + 4 + T(T(3)) \\ 3429 &:= T(T(9))/T(2) \times T(4) - T(T(3)) \\ 3466 &:= 6 \times T(T(6)) + T(4^3) \\ 3589 &:= -T(9) + T(85) - T(T(3)) \\ 3619 &:= (T(T(9)) - 1) \times T(6)/T(3) \\ 3628 &:= T(82) + T(T(6)) - T(3) \\ 3728 &:= T(82) + T(T(7)) - 3 \\ 3736 &:= T(T(6 + 3)) + T(73) \\ 3752 &:= T(T(T(2)) \times T(5)) - 7^3 \\ 3767 &:= T(7) \times T(T(6)) - T(73) \\ 3779 &:= T(T(9)) + (7 + 7)^3 \\ 3892 &:= T(T(-2 + 9)) + T(83) \\ 3925 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(2)) + T(T(9)) \times 3 \\ 3928 &:= 8 \times (2^9 - T(T(3))) \\ 3967 &:= T(76) + T(T(9)) + T(3) \\ 3972 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(-7 + 93) \\ 3982 &:= -2 + T(89) - T(T(3)) \\ 4045 &:= 5 \times T(40) - T(T(4)) \\ 4091 &:= T(1 \times 90) - 4 \\ 4093 &:= -T(3) + T(90) + 4 \\ 4109 &:= T(90) + 14 \\ 4172 &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 7)) - 14 \\ 4204 &:= (T(40) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \times 4 \\ 4268 &:= T(86 + T(T(2))) - T(4) \\ 4285 &:= -5 + T(T(8)/T(2)) \times T(T(4)) \\ 4389 &:= -T(98) + T(3) \times T(T(T(4))) \\ 4449 &:= T(94) - 4 \times 4 \\ 4486 &:= T(6) + T(84 + T(4)) \\ 4496 &:= T(6) + T(94) + T(4) \\ 4524 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(2)) \times T(T(T(5))/T(4)) \\ 4542 &:= T(2) \times T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(5))/T(4)) \\ 4559 &:= T(95) - 5 + 4 \\ 4593 &:= 3 \times (-T(9)/5 + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 4789 &:= T(98) - 7 - T(T(4)) \\ 4799 &:= -9 + T(97) + T(T(4)) \\ 4845 &:= T(5 \times T(4)) + T(84) \\ 4896 &:= T(6 + T(9)) + T(84) \\ 4921 &:= (1 + T(2)^9)/4 \\ 4926 &:= (T(6) + T(2)^9)/4 \\ 4968 &:= 8 \times 6 \times T(T(9))/T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5256 &:= -T(6) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(2))^5 \\
 5372 &:= 2 \times (T(73) - T(5)) \\
 5376 &:= T(T(6)) + 7^3 \times T(5) \\
 5405 &:= T(50 - 4) \times 5 \\
 5673 &:= 3 \times T(76 - T(5)) \\
 5725 &:= T(T(T(5))/T(2)) \times 7 - T(5) \\
 5735 &:= T(T(T(5))/3) \times 7 - 5 \\
 5793 &:= -3 + T(T(9)) \times T(7)/5 \\
 5794 &:= (-T(4) + T(T(9)) \times T(7))/5 \\
 5859 &:= T(9)/5 \times (T(T(8)) - T(5)) \\
 5866 &:= T(66) + T(85) \\
 5984 &:= -T(4) + T(T(8)) \times T(9)/5 \\
 5985 &:= T(T(T(5)) - T(8)) + T(T(T(9))/T(5)) \\
 5987 &:= -7 + T(T(8)) \times T(9)/5 \\
 5994 &:= T(4 \times 9) \times T(9)/5 \\
 6027 &:= 7 \times T(20 + T(6)) \\
 6235 &:= -5 + 3 \times T(2^6) \\
 6246 &:= T(64) \times T(2) + 6 \\
 6249 &:= (T(T(9)) + T(4)) \times T(T(2)) - T(6) \\
 6278 &:= 8 \times T(7)^2 + 6 \\
 6318 &:= 81 \times T(T(3) + 6) \\
 6438 &:= T(T(8)) \times (3 + T(T(4)))/6 \\
 6456 &:= 6 \times (-5 + T(46)) \\
 6582 &:= T(2)^8 + T(5) + 6 \\
 6636 &:= T(T(6)/3) \times (6 + T(T(6))) \\
 6822 &:= T(T(2 \times T(T(2)))) + T(86) \\
 6924 &:= T(T(T(4)))/2 \times 9 - 6 \\
 7133 &:= T(T(T(3))) \times 31 - T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7157 &:= (T(T(7)) + T(5)) \times 17 \\
 7289 &:= T(9) \times T(T(8)/2) - T(T(7)) \\
 7356 &:= 6 \times (T(T(T(5))/3) + T(T(7))) \\
 7484 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + 8 \times T(47) \\
 7626 &:= (T(T(6))^2 + T(6))/7 \\
 7776 &:= 6^{(T(7)+7)/7} \\
 7982 &:= 2 \times T(89) - T(7) \\
 8273 &:= (T(T(3) + 7))^2 - 8 \\
 8452 &:= T(T(2))^5 + T(4) + T(T(8)) \\
 8525 &:= 5 \times (-T(T(2)) + T(58)) \\
 8552 &:= -T(2) + 5 \times T(58) \\
 8576 &:= 67 \times (T(T(5)) + 8) \\
 8642 &:= -T(T(2)) + T(46) \times 8 \\
 8644 &:= -4 + T(46) \times 8 \\
 8968 &:= (86 + T(T(9))) \times 8 \\
 9216 &:= T(6)^{1+2} - T(9) \\
 9232 &:= T(T(T(2)))^3 - 29 \\
 9261 &:= T(1 \times 6)^{-T(T(2))+9} \\
 9265 &:= -5 + T(6)^{T(2)} + 9 \\
 9297 &:= T(7) \times T(T(9)) - T(2)^9 \\
 9306 &:= T(6)^{03} + T(9) \\
 9324 &:= 42 \times (T(T(T(3))) - 9) \\
 9644 &:= 4 \times (-4 + T(69)) \\
 9645 &:= -T(5) + 4 \times T(69) \\
 9667 &:= T(T(7)) + T(6)^{-6+9}
 \end{aligned}$$

7 Complete Selfie Numbers

This section brings selfie numbers in terms of T in such a way that all the operations are inside T . There are very few values of this kind. For simplicity, let us call it **complete selfie numbers**

7.1 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 15 &:= T(1 \times 5) & 105 &:= T(-1 + T(05)) \\
 21 &:= T(T(2 + 1)) & 120 &:= T(T(-1 + T(T(2 + 0)))) \\
 45 &:= T(4 + 5) & 136 &:= T(T(1 + 3) + 6) \\
 55 &:= T(5 + 5) & 153 &:= T(-1 + T(5) + 3) \\
 66 &:= T(T(T(6))/T(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$154 := T(T(T(-1 + 5)))/T(4)$$

$$171 := T(17 + 1)$$

$$190 := T(19 + 0)$$

$$210 := T(2 \times 10)$$

$$231 := T(T(2 \times 3 \times 1))$$

$$253 := T(25 - 3)$$

$$325 := T((3 + 2) \times 5)$$

$$435 := T(4 \times T(3) + 5)$$

$$465 := T(4 + T(6) + 5)$$

$$561 := T(5 + T(6 + 1))$$

$$666 := T(-6 + T(6) + T(6))$$

$$861 := T(T(8) + 6 - 1)$$

$$903 := T(T(9) - 03)$$

$$946 := T(T(9) + 4 - 6)$$

$$1035 := T(10 + 35)$$

$$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$1128 := T(-1 + 12 + T(8))$$

$$1176 := T((1 \times 1 + 7) \times 6)$$

$$1225 := T(-1 + 2 \times 25)$$

$$1275 := T((1 + 2 + 7) \times 5)$$

$$1326 := T(-13 + 2^6)$$

$$1378 := T(-1 - 3 + 7 \times 8)$$

$$1485 := T(1 + 48 + 5)$$

$$1540 := T(1 + 54 + 0)$$

$$1596 := T(1 \times 5 + T(9) + 6)$$

$$1711 := T(-1 - 7 + T(11))$$

$$1770 := T(1 + T(T(7)))/7 + 0$$

$$1830 := T(-T(18) + T(T(T(3) + 0)))$$

$$1953 := T(1 \times 9 + 53)$$

$$2145 := T(-2 + 1 + T(-4 + T(5)))$$

$$2211 := T(T(2 - 2 + 11))$$

$$2415 := T(T(2) + T(-4 + 15))$$

$$2565 := T((-2 + 5) \times 6) \times T(5)$$

$$2628 := T(2 + 62 + 8)$$

$$2701 := T(2 + 70 + 1)$$

$$2775 := T(2 + 77 - 5)$$

$$2850 := T((-T(2) + 8) \times T(5) + 0)$$

$$3003 := T(T(T(T(3))))/003$$

$$3081 := T(T(3 + 08 + 1))$$

$$3240 := T((T(3) + 2) \times T(4 + 0))$$

$$3321 := T((3 \times 3)^2 \times 1)$$

$$3570 := T(T(3) + T(5 + 7 + 0))$$

$$3655 := T(3 \times 6 \times 5 - 5)$$

$$3828 := T(-3 + 82 + 8)$$

$$3916 := T(3 + 91 - 6)$$

$$4095 := T(40 + T(9) + 5)$$

$$4186 := T(4 + 1 + 86)$$

$$4371 := T(T(T(4)) + 37 + 1)$$

$$4465 := T(T(T(4) + 4) - 6 - 5)$$

$$4560 := T(-T(4) + 5 \times T(6 + 0))$$

$$4851 := T(T(T(4)) - 8 + 51)$$

$$4950 := T(4 + 95 + 0)$$

7.2 Reverse Order of Digits

$$15 := T(5 \times 1)$$

$$21 := T(T(1 + 2))$$

$$45 := T(5 + 4)$$

$$55 := T(5 + 5)$$

$$66 := T(T(T(6)))/T(6)$$

$$105 := T(T(5) - 01)$$

$$120 := T(T((T(T(02)) - 1)))$$

$$136 := T(6 + T(3 + 1))$$

$$171 := T(17 + 1)$$

$$210 := T(-01 + T(T(T(2))))$$

$$231 := T(T(1 \times 3 \times 2))$$

$$253 := T(-3 + 5^2)$$

$$325 := T(5 \times (2 + 3))$$

$$435 := T(-5 + 34)$$

$$561 := T(T(1 + 6) + 5)$$

$$666 := T(-6 + T(6) + T(6))$$

$$703 := T(30 + 7)$$

$$861 := T(-1 + 6 + T(8))$$

$$903 := T(-3 + T(09))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 946 &:= T(-6 + 49) & 2145 &:= T(5 \times (T(4) \times 1 + T(2))) \\ 0231 &:= T(1^3 + 20) & 2278 &:= T(-8 + 72 + T(2)) \\ 0253 &:= T(-3 + 5 + 20) & 2415 &:= T(5 + 1 \times 4^{T(2)}) \\ 0276 &:= T(T(6)/7 + 20) & 2485 &:= T(5 \times (8 + 4 + 2)) \\ 0351 &:= T(1 - 5 + 30) & 2556 &:= T(T(6) + 5 \times 5 \times 2) \\ 0465 &:= T(5 \times 6 + 4 \times 0) & 2628 &:= T(8 + 2 + 62) \\ 0528 &:= T(82 - 50) & 2701 &:= T(1 + 072) \\ 1035 &:= T(T(5 + 3 + 01)) & 2775 &:= T(-5 + 7 + 72) \\ 1081 &:= T(1 + T(8 + 01)) & 2850 &:= T(T(05) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 1128 &:= T(8 \times T(2 + 1) - 1) & 2926 &:= T(T(6 - 2) + T(9 + 2)) \\ 1176 &:= T(6 \times (7 + 1 \times 1)) & 3081 &:= T(1 + 80 - 3) \\ 1225 &:= T((5 + 2)^2 \times 1) & 3234 &:= T(T(4 \times 3) + 2) - (T(3)) \\ 1275 &:= T(5 \times (7 + 2 + 1)) & 3240 &:= T(T(04) \times 2^3) \\ 1326 &:= T(6 + T(2^3 + 1)) & 3321 &:= T((1 + 2)^3 \times 3) \\ 1378 &:= T(8 \times 7 - 3 - 1) & 3486 &:= T(6 + 8 \times T(4) - 3) \\ 1431 &:= T(13 \times 4 + 1) & 3570 &:= T(T(07) \times T(5 - 3)) \\ 1485 &:= T(5 + 8 + 41) & 3655 &:= T(-5 + 5 \times 6 \times 3) \\ 1540 &:= T(04 + 51) & 3828 &:= T(8/2 + 83) \\ 1653 &:= T(T(3 + 5) + T(6 \times 1)) & 3916 &:= T(61 + 9 \times 3) \\ 1711 &:= T(T(11) - 7 - 1) & 4186 &:= T(6 + 81 + 4) \\ 1770 &:= T(T(T(07))/7 + 1) & 4465 &:= T((T(5) + 6) \times 4 + T(4)) \\ 1830 &:= T(-T(T(03)) + 81) & 4560 &:= T(T(06) \times 5 - T(4)) \\ 1953 &:= T(3 + 59 \times 1) & 4851 &:= T(-1 + T(5) + 84) \\ 2016 &:= T(61 + 02) & 4950 &:= T(05 + 94) \\ 2080 &:= T(08^{02}) \end{aligned}$$

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to T.J. Eckman, Georgia, USA (email: jeek@jeek.net) in programming the script to develop these representations.

References

- [1] J. BARTON, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.virtuescience.com/centered-polygonal.html>.
- [2] H.E. DUDENEY, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [3] R. KNOTT, Polygonal Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Figurate/figurate.html>.
- [4] J.S. MADACHY, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlars Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.

- [5] N.J.A. SLONE, Triangular numbers: $a(n) = \text{binomial}(n + 1, 2) = n(n + 1)/2 = 0 + 1 + 2 + \dots + n$, The On-Line Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences, <https://oeis.org/A000217>.
- [6] WOLFRAM MATH WORLD, Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/PolygonalNumber.html>
- [7] WOLFRAM MATH WORLD, Centered Polygonal Numbers, <http://mathworld.wolfram.com/CenteredPolygonalNumber.html>
- [8] TANEJA, I.J., Selfie Numbers: Consecutive Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **17**(2014), Article 140, pp. 1-57. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v17/v17a140.pdf>.
- [9] I.J. TANEJA, Different Types of Pretty Wild Narcissistic Numbers: Selfie Representations - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 32, pp.1-43. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a32.pdf>.
- [10] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers: Representations in Increasing and Decreasing Orders of Non Consecutive Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 70, pp.1-104. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a70.pdf>.
- [11] I.J. TANEJA, Unified Selfie Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 153, pp. 1-14. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a153.pdf>.
- [12] I.J. TANEJA, Patterns in Selfie Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 154, pp. 1-41. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a154.pdf>.
- [13] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - I: Symmetrical and Unified Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 174, pp.1-94. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a174.pdf>.
- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - II: Six Digits Symmetrical, Unified and Patterned Representations Without Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **18**(2015), Article 175, pp.1-41. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a175.pdf>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - III: With Factorial and Without Square-Root - Up To Five Digits, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 16, pp.1-52, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a16.pdf>.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Power Representations, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 17, pp. 1-20, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a17.pdf>.
- [17] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 142, pp. 1-59, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a142.pdf>.
- [18] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers - II, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 143, pp. 1-47, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a143.pdf>.
- [19] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers - III, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Art 156, pp. 1-72, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a156.pdf>.
- [20] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - IV: Addition, Subtraction and Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 163, pp.1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a163.pdf>.

- [21] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers - V: Six Digits Symmetrical Representations with Factorial, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **19**(2016), Article 164, pp.1-60, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a164.pdf>.
- [22] I.J. TANEJA, Binomial Coefficients Type Selfie Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 102, pp.1-113, <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a102.pdf>.
- [23] I.J. TANEJA, S-gonal and Centered Polygonal Selfie Numbers, and Connections with Binomials Coefficients, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), pp. 1-42, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a43.pdf>.
- [24] I.J. TANEJA, Triangular Selfie Numbers - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 54, pp. 1-78, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a54.pdf>.
- [25] I.J. TANEJA, Hardy-Ramanujan Number - 1729, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), pp.1-50, Art 6, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a06.pdf>
- [26] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **21**(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>.
- [27] I.J. TANEJA, 2019 In Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access, December 31, 2019, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2529103>.
-